

**INVASIVE WOODY PLANTS: A DOUBLE-EDGED SWORD
FOR INVERTEBRATE CONSERVATION**

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Invasive Woody Plants: A Double-Edged Sword for Invertebrate Conservation

Charmaine Uys

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ABSTRACT

While the Cape Peninsula (South Africa) is renowned for its exceptional plant and invertebrate diversity and endemism, extensive alien plant invasion and exotic pine plantations reduce native species richness, and may facilitate alien invertebrate invasions. This study examines the impact of planting and felling pine on litter invertebrate communities, by comparing invertebrate diversity and faunal exchange between pine plantations and two types of native vegetation (Afrotemperate forest and fynbos). Impacts of the worst invasive alien invertebrate (Argentine ant, *Linepithema humile*) and other alien invertebrate species are investigated. This is one of the first attempts to inventory and quantify impacts of non-ant alien invertebrates in Table Mountain National Park. The entire ground-dwelling invertebrate community was sampled at 31 sites in summer 2008/2009, using soil cores, leaf litter samples, pitfall traps, sugar-baited ant traps, and decayed logs. A total of 112 404 individuals representing 728 species (10 classes and 38 orders), including nine Cape Peninsula endemic and 19 alien invertebrate species, was collected. Pine plantations supported lower species richness and abundance, and different community assemblages, compared to Afrotemperate forest, but similar species richness to fynbos. Pine plantations shared fewer species with fynbos than forest, thus negatively affected fynbos-specialist invertebrates, because afforestation reduces available fynbos habitat. Alien species richness was similar across habitats. Argentine ants, like most other alien species identified, were present in all habitats, but were the most abundant ant species at only four forest, two fynbos and two pine plantation sites. The impact of Argentine ant invasion on native ant communities was evaluated using species richness and community composition analyses, the functional group approach, and species co-occurrence patterns, and provided evidence for displacement, impoverishment, and community disassembly. No clear impacts of the 18 non-ant alien species on the abundance, species richness, or community composition of corresponding native taxa were detected. However, carnivorous molluscs and European wasps (*Vespula germanica*) require careful monitoring. Using a reiterative process, ant species and functional groups were selected as the best ecological indicators of restoration progress in fynbos following clear-felling of pine. These findings have application to other Mediterranean-type ecosystems impacted by exotic pine.

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CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

Setting the scene

Invasive alien species are the second leading cause of global biodiversity loss (Wilcove *et al.*, 1998; Simberloff, 2001), and interact additively or synergistically with the most important driver of loss, habitat destruction (Didham *et al.*, 2005). Alien species are those that did not originate from a geographic region in question (Richardson *et al.*, 2000; Pyšek *et al.*, 2004). Alien species span a naturalisation-invasion continuum (reviewed in Pyšek & Richardson, 2010), and become invasive when they spread widely in the newly occupied region (Kolar & Lodge, 2001). As such, biological invasions are recognised as global drivers of environmental change (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Biological invasions are on par with climate change as one of the hottest contemporary research topics within ecology, with a recent exponential increase in interest in the discipline of invasion ecology, to match the escalating global biological invasion crisis (Pyšek *et al.*, 2006; Richardson & Pyšek, 2008; Davis, 2009).

It is the accelerated rate of human-mediated spread, distances traversed, and numbers of species involved that set current biological invasions apart from natural long-distance colonisations and range expansions (Cassey *et al.*, 2005). Consequently, many landscapes and seascapes in various parts of the world are now dominated by alien species (Cassey *et al.*, 2005; Didham *et al.*, 2005). Coastal ecosystems, inland waters, islands, and Mediterranean-climate regions are most threatened by biological invasions (Pyšek & Richardson, 2010). This thesis will focus on biological invasions in the Mediterranean-climate region of the Western Cape Province, South Africa, and more specifically on the ecological impacts of terrestrial biological invasions.

The impacts of alien species on native biota are of particular concern, and have received a great deal of attention from researchers (Richardson, 2006). An impact may be defined as 'the description or quantification of how an alien species affects other organisms and the environment' (Pyšek & Richardson, 2010). Invasive alien species can displace native species, reduce their abundance, rapidly disassemble communities, alter community organisation, and disrupt ecosystems (Vitousek *et al.*, 1996; Mack *et al.*, 2000; O'Dowd *et al.*, 2003; Sanders *et al.*, 2003; Blackburn *et al.*, 2004; Gaertner *et al.*, 2009). Impacts of the vast majority of alien species have not been quantified (Parker *et al.*, 1999), although most are assumed to have some ecological impact on the invaded ecosystem (Ricciardi & Kipp, 2008). Most such impacts are observed at the population or community level, but some invasive alien species also cause

impacts at an ecosystem level (Parker *et al.*, 1999; Pyšek & Richardson, 2010), where they disrupt major trophic networks and other ecological processes. The focus of this thesis is on population and community level ecological impacts on terrestrial invertebrates, resulting from pine invasions.

Ecological impacts of pine invasions in South Africa

South Africa is well advanced in the field of biological invasion, certainly in comparison with the rest of Africa, because it has robust national legislation for tackling the biological invasion problem, and a relatively well-developed research information infrastructure (McGeoch *et al.*, 2010). South Africa accounts for roughly two-thirds of all published research on biological invasions produced on the African continent (Pyšek *et al.*, 2008). The country has a long history of research on plant invasions (reviewed in Chown, 2010), and is a global leader in the application of pine invasion research (Richardson, 2006). Unfortunately, South Africa also has one of the highest levels of alien plant invasion, compared to other countries (Richardson & van Wilgen, 2004).

Invasive alien trees have major impacts on native species richness. Pines (*Pinus* species) and Australian wattles (*Acacia* species) are among the alien invasive plants that cause the most significant declines in native species richness in South Africa (Richardson & van Wilgen, 2004; Gaertner *et al.*, 2009). These species are particularly problematic in fynbos, the Mediterranean-climate shrubland in the Western Cape Province, where dense stands are known to reduce native plant diversity and abundance at small spatial scales (Richardson *et al.*, 1989). The Fynbos Biome is the most heavily invaded and best-studied of South Africa's eight terrestrial biomes (Richardson & van Wilgen, 2004), with the highest proportion of endemic plant species. Given the severe impacts of pine invasions, especially in fynbos, this thesis is set in the Fynbos and Forest Biomes, South Africa's smallest and most heavily invaded biomes (Henderson, 1998). At least 21 *Pinus* species have become invasive, with severe impacts in South Africa and other Southern Hemisphere countries (Richardson *et al.*, 1994; Richardson, 2006). Pines represent a model taxon for studies on alien plant invasions, and many of the important insights gained from pine invasion studies are also relevant for other plant taxa (Richardson, 2006).

Most invasive pine species in South Africa are also commercially important forestry species (Richardson, 2006). Over 80 species of *Pinus* have been introduced to South Africa, seven of which now form the backbone of commercial forestry industries in the Southern

Hemisphere (reviewed in Richardson *et al.*, 1994). Pine plantations (the main focus of this study) are regularly spaced monocultures (Hartley, 2002). Although plantations are sometimes referred to as plantation forests or pine forests, to avoid confusion the term “forest” is used here to refer only to native (indigenous) forest, and not also to planted or invasive stands of pine trees. Afforestation, the planting of large numbers of trees on previously non-forested land, is equivalent to a dense invasion. Therefore, studies of the effects of plantation forestry offer insights into the impacts of invasive alien trees. Afforestation has striking impacts on biodiversity in certain parts of South Africa, with numerous plant and animal species threatened, or forced to local extinction (Armstrong *et al.*, 1998).

Ecological impacts of invertebrate invasions in South Africa

Biological invasions by alien animals in South Africa have received far less attention than those by alien plants (Chown, 2010). Despite the large number of alien animal species (spanning most major taxonomic groups) in South Africa (Macdonald *et al.*, 2003; Musil & Macdonald, 2007), few have been well-studied. Consequently, most insights on the mechanisms and impacts of invasion come from studies of a few of the most harmful invasive alien species (Pyšek *et al.*, 2008).

Locally, the Argentine ant (*Linepithema humile*) has received more attention than most other alien invertebrate species, because its invasion into fynbos has caused the disruption and collapse of an ant-plant mutualism, viz. myrmecochory, the dispersal of seeds by ants (Bond & Slingsby, 1984). Argentine ants have also been reported to reduce ant species richness and to replace dominant native ants, in particular, ground-foraging, seed-dispersing ant guilds in fynbos (Bond & Slingsby, 1984; Parker-Allie *et al.*, 2008).

The Argentine ant and four other invasive ant species are listed among the *100 of the world's worst invasive species*, chosen for their serious impact on biodiversity and/or human activities, and their illustration of important issues surrounding biological invasion (Lowe *et al.*, 2000). Invasive ants are a globally pervasive ecological problem, due to their expanding geographic ranges, high propagule pressure, high local abundances, and ability to disrupt ecosystems (Holway *et al.*, 2002). High competitive ability, polygyny, dependent colony foundation, and unicoloniality characterise these successful invasive ant species (Suarez *et al.*, 2010). Throughout the world, invasive ants also readily spread from human-modified habitats into undisturbed natural areas, under suitable abiotic conditions (reviewed in Krushelnycky *et*

al., 2010). Therefore, Argentine ants, like pine plantations, are a focus of this thesis, given the conservation concern associated with their invasion, both locally and globally.

Non-ant alien invertebrates may also impact native invertebrate diversity either directly through predation and parasitism, or indirectly by disease transmission, disrupting mutualisms, and through interference competition (Kenis *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, in addition to the impacts of Argentine ants, the ecological impacts of other alien invertebrates (particularly Mollusca and the European wasp, *Vespula germanica*) are investigated. This is one of the first attempts to inventory and quantify ecological impacts of non-ant terrestrial alien invertebrates on the Cape Peninsula, in the Western Cape Province.

Implications of felling pine for invertebrate communities

It's not enough to know the ecological impacts of planted or invasive stands of pine, or which invertebrate species survive under pine plantations. There is also an urgent need to start documenting and understanding the community compositional changes that take place post-felling of pine, in order to inform responsible and appropriate management decisions. Clearing invasive alien trees has tangible conservation benefits. For example, three species of endemic South African dragonflies that were feared extinct, are now known from sites from which invasive alien trees have been removed (Samways *et al.*, 2005; Samways & Sharratt, 2009). However, little is known about the recovery of invertebrate communities after clear-felling of pine. This study is one of the first attempts to fill this gap, and to identify potentially suitable invertebrate taxa to use as ecological indicators of restoration progress in fynbos following clear-felling of pine.

Broad aims and objectives

This study was undertaken on the Cape Peninsula in Table Mountain National Park (Cape Town), a World Heritage Site and global biodiversity hotspot in the Cape Floristic Region. Alien pine plantations on the Cape Peninsula are thought to act as a 'double-edged sword' for invertebrate conservation, firstly by supporting lower invertebrate species richness and different community assemblages, compared to neighbouring native forest, and secondly by facilitating the spread of alien invertebrates into surrounding native vegetation. The overall aim of this study is to assess the implications of planting and felling pine for ground-dwelling invertebrates. In doing so, this study frames invasion ecology theory in a regional conservation context, but the

findings also have application to other Mediterranean-type ecosystems impacted by invasive alien pines.

The broad objectives of this study are:

- 1) To determine the influence of exotic pine plantations on ground-dwelling invertebrate species richness and community composition (Chapter 3).
- 2) To assess invertebrate faunal exchange between exotic pine plantation and native forest and fynbos (Chapter 4).
- 3) To investigate the impacts of Argentine ants on native ants and other ground-dwelling invertebrates (Chapter 5).
- 4) To investigate the impacts of other (non-ant) alien invertebrate species on their corresponding native taxa (Chapter 6).
- 5) To identify and test potentially suitable ground-dwelling invertebrate taxa for use as ecological indicators of restoration progress in fynbos following clear-felling of pine plantations (Chapter 7).
- 6) To integrate the findings of this study, and to discuss their implications for invertebrate conservation and management, and propose future research (Chapter 8).

CHAPTER 2. STUDY SITES AND SAMPLING METHODS

Study area

Cape Peninsula

This study took place in Table Mountain National Park, which stretches from Signal Hill (33°55'4"S 18°24'10"E) to Cape Point (34°21'26"S 18°29'51"E) on the Cape Peninsula (area: 471 km²), in the south-western tip of the Cape Floristic Region, and surrounded by one of South Africa's fastest growing metropolises, greater Cape Town. The Cape Peninsula forms part of the Cape Fold Mountains, and is renowned for its topographical heterogeneity (Cowling *et al.*, 1996) and exceptional diversity and endemism, with 158 endemic angiosperms (Helme & Trinder-Smith, 2006) and at least 111 endemic invertebrates (Picker & Samways, 1996). Serious threats to Cape Peninsula biodiversity include land transformations, alien tree invasions, and altered fire regimes (Richardson *et al.*, 1996).

The Fynbos Biome, with a focus on Sandstone Fynbos and Granite Fynbos

The Fynbos Biome is one of five geographically distinct areas that together constitute the global Mediterranean Biome, the others being the Mediterranean Basin, Californian Floristic Province, a small region in North Chile, and two separate regions in Australia (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). The Fynbos Biome is subdivided into three main vegetation units: fynbos, renosterveld, and strandveld. The fynbos alone boasts some 7500 of the almost 9000 plant species found in the Cape Floristic Region, over 80% of which are endemic to the region (van Wyk & Smith, 2001).

Fynbos is characterised by nutrient-poor soils; hot, dry summers and cool, wet winters; recurrent fires at 5-50 year intervals; and complex plant-animal interactions, especially pollination and dispersal (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). Fynbos is both fire-prone and fire-dependent, with summer and early autumn fires necessary to maintain diversity and ecosystem processes (Forsyth & Bridgett, 2004). The current fynbos vegetation classification follows the underlying geology (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). Two of the fynbos vegetation groups found on the Cape Peninsula, namely Sandstone Fynbos and Granite Fynbos, were included in the experimental design of this study.

Sandstone Fynbos is the most extensive vegetation group within the Fynbos Biome, covering roughly one third (301 km²) of the biome. Peninsula Sandstone Fynbos (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006) was previously classified (among other names) as Mountain Fynbos (Low & Rebelo, 1996). It occurs on gentle to steep slopes (up to 1086 m a.s.l.) across the 50 km length of the

Cape Peninsula, on stony, often very sandy, acid lithosol soils derived from Ordovician sandstone of the Table Mountain Group, a subdivision within the Cape Supergroup rocks. Mean Annual Precipitation (MAP) ranges from 520-1690 mm, peaking from May to August. Vegetation comprises mainly proteoid, ericaceous and restioid fynbos, with some asteraceous fynbos. Comparatively little land transformation has taken place in the mountain habitat, affording Sandstone Fynbos the conservation status of 'Least Threatened'. Nevertheless, urban sprawl and alien plantations have transformed large parts of this vegetation group, and dense patches of woody invasives occur, despite a long history of conservation in the mountains.

Granite Fynbos covers only 2% of the Fynbos Biome. Peninsula Granite Fynbos (Rebello *et al.*, 2006) is found on gentle to steep lower slopes (up to 450 m a.s.l.), below the sandstone mountain slopes on the Cape Peninsula, almost entirely surrounding Table Mountain. Soils are deep loamy, sandy soils, derived from the Cape Granite Suite. Mean Annual Precipitation ranges from 590-1320 mm, peaking from May to August. This diverse vegetation group is dominated by asteraceous and proteoid fynbos. Peninsula Granite Fynbos is listed as 'Endangered'. Although it is conserved in Table Mountain National Park and Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, much of this fynbos is senescent and undergoing transformation into Afrotropical forest, as a result of the fire-exclusion policies in Orange Kloof and Kirstenbosch, and a reluctance to use fire on green belts and on the urban fringe.

The Forest Biome, with a focus on Southern Afrotropical Forest

Forest covers 32% of dry land globally, of which 17% is found on the African continent (Dajoz, 2000). Forest is the smallest biome in southern Africa (Rutherford & Westfall, 1994; Eeley *et al.*, 2001), covering less than 1% of the combined land area of South Africa, Lesotho, and Swaziland (Midgley *et al.*, 1997; Rutherford, 1997; Rouget *et al.*, 2004; Berliner, 2005). In southern Africa, there are over 20 000 patches of forest ranging in size from less than 1 ha to over 2000 ha, 71% of which are less than 10 ha (Berliner, 2005). Forest patches have a naturally fragmented distribution, scattered along the eastern and southern mountain ranges and coastal lowlands of southern Africa. This 'forest archipelago' is embedded in a matrix of temperate biomes, including fynbos, grassland, succulent thicket, and savanna (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006).

Despite their small size and fragmented distribution, South African forests are globally significant. A comparison of the plant species richness relative to the total area of each biome in South Africa shows that the forest biome contains the highest density of plant species: 3000 species in approximately 5052 km², compared to the next highest, fynbos, with 7500 species in

76 744 km² (Berliner, 2005). Southern African temperate forests are also between three and seven times richer in tree species than other forested regions of the Southern Hemisphere, with the richness of South African tree genera and families being unparalleled (Cowling, 2002).

Afrotemperate forests in southern Africa form part of the global warm-temperate Forest Biome (Rutherford *et al.*, 2006). Afrotemperate forests were previously known locally as Afromontane forests (*sensu* White, 1978). They share affinities with the Afromontane Region throughout sub-Saharan Africa, which occurs as a series of isolated patches constituting the Afromontane regional centre of endemism (White, 1983). Although most Afromontane communities in the tropics occur above 2000 m, forest occurs almost at sea level on the moist, sheltered, eastern slopes of Table Mountain, where latitude “compensates” for altitude, and the climate is influenced by the proximity to the Atlantic Ocean (Meadows & Linder, 1989).

Based on a biogeographic-floristic classification of South African indigenous forests (von Maltitz *et al.*, 2003), 26 forest types are currently recognised (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006). The Southern Afrotemperate Forest Group consists of three vegetation types: Southern Cape Afrotemperate Forest, Western Cape Talus Forest, and Western Cape Afrotemperate Forest (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006). This study focuses on Western Cape Afrotemperate Forest, which occurs on the Cape Peninsula. Forest patches occur in deep ravines on all sides of Table Mountain, and in steep, sheltered cliffs on the plateau, but only extend onto open slopes on the moist, sheltered eastern side (Adamson, 1927).

Southern Afrotemperate Forest currently has the conservation status of ‘Least Threatened’ (Rouget *et al.*, 2004), because over half of the extant patches have statutory conservation in national parks (including Table Mountain National Park) and nature reserves (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006). However, this classification represents forest only at the level of forest groups, not types, thereby not accounting for differences in conservation status among forest types. Western Cape Afrotemperate Forest is one of the rarest forest types in South Africa, covering only 4731 ha (Berliner & Benn, 2003; Berliner, 2005). It has historically been heavily exploited, although in the absence of detailed scientific documentation it is impossible to know the precise extent of forest in the past (McKenzie *et al.*, 1977). Consequently, Berliner (2005) recommended that the IUCN endangerment category for Western Cape Afrotemperate Forest should be ‘Vulnerable’. Berliner (2005) argued that, since no reliable scientific data are available to assess the levels of historic habitat loss for forest types, habitat loss (transformation) should not be used as the main criterion for assessing the ecosystem status of forests in South Africa.

Fynbos or forest on the Cape Peninsula?

Bioclimatically, most fynbos occurs in areas mesic enough to support Afrotropical forest. Bond *et al.* (2003), using a simulation study, argue that current levels of CO₂ (360 ppm) are potentially suitable for mesic fynbos to develop towards fire-sensitive forest, if fires were excluded. This is evident on the Cape Peninsula, in areas such as Kirstenbosch and Orange Kloof, where changes in fire management have allowed forest to colonise areas naturally covered with Granite Fynbos only a few decades ago (McKenzie *et al.*, 1977; Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). Succession to forest may be possible in areas of high rainfall, especially in old, moribund fynbos vegetation, where shading facilitates the establishment of forest species (Manders, 1990). However, under more natural conditions fynbos maintains dominance in the landscape through regular natural burning, since fire excludes forest species (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006 and references therein). Consequently, 'true' evergreen Afrotropical forest is naturally confined to large screes, deep kloofs, and fire refugia protected by cliffs and scarps. Fire is also responsible for the sharp (often only a few metres) ecotone between fynbos and forest (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006).

Nutrient availability also differs greatly between fynbos and forest. In fynbos, nutrient cycling is slow and fire acts as a mineralising agent, whereas in forest, nutrients are recycled in the litter layer (Stock & Allsopp, 1992; Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). The response of fynbos vegetation to low nutrient availability adds to its uniqueness and biological importance. This vegetation response includes serotiny, myrmecochory, obligate reseeding versus resprouting, lack of annuals, sclerophylly, lack of mycorrhiza and presence of cluster roots, carnivory and digestive mutualisms, low biomass of herbivores, and bird and mammal pollination (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). Many of these are absent in the Afrotropical forest flora. Afrotropical forest differs physiognomically and floristically from fire-prone fynbos shrublands, because it contains medium to tall, closed-canopy, broad-leaved, evergreen trees and shrubs with strong Afrotropical affinities, with most forest species widespread outside of the Cape Floristic Region (Cowling *et al.*, 1996). Southern Afrotropical Forest accounts for less than 5% of the plant species on the Cape Peninsula, with about half of the 150 plant species that are over 1.5 m tall occurring in fynbos (T. Rebelo pers. comm., 2008).

Pine plantation history on the Cape Peninsula

Large-scale planting of pine and other fast-growing alien trees, such as eucalypt and acacia, in the Western Cape began in the 1850s. However, it was not until the 1880s that pine plantations were established on the slopes of Table Mountain and the Cape Peninsula (Cowling *et al.*, 1996; Richardson & Higgins, 1998). Commercial plantations were established in the fynbos

surrounding forest patches, but rarely in areas cleared of evergreen forest (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006). Pine plantations on the eastern slopes are in Granite Fynbos, because Sandstone Fynbos productivity proved too low to sustain commercial plantations on the Cape Peninsula (T. Rebelo pers. comm., 2010).

Two species of pine (Family Pinaceae) have been widely planted for commercial timber production in the Western Cape. *Pinus pinaster* Ait. (Cluster pine) is native to Mediterranean areas of Europe (Henderson, 2001). It was introduced to South Africa in 1680 (Richardson *et al.*, 1992), soon after colonization of the Cape by the Dutch, and by 1772 was widespread on the Cape Peninsula (Richardson & Higgins, 1998). Cluster pine is now by far the most widespread invasive pine species in South Africa (Richardson *et al.*, 1994). It is also one of 15 woody plant species listed among the *100 of the world's worst invasive species* (Lowe *et al.*, 2000). *P. radiata* D. Don (Monterey pine or Radiata pine) is native to California in North America (Henderson, 2001). It was first recorded in the Western Cape in 1865 (Richardson & Higgins, 1998), where it quickly became the most commonly planted timber species (Lavery & Mead, 1998). Today, Monterey pine is the dominant exotic softwood used in plantations for commercial timber production in South Africa (Simberloff *et al.*, 2010), Australia (Sinclair & New, 2004), and New Zealand (Pawson *et al.*, 2008). Consequently, Monterey pine is the most widely planted alien conifer in the world, occupying over three million hectares of plantations outside of its natural range (Richardson *et al.*, 1994).

Both *P. pinaster* and *P. radiata* are successful alien invasives in Australia, New Zealand, Chile and South Africa (Richardson *et al.*, 1994), especially in fynbos (Richardson & Higgins, 1998). Both species are also declared invaders (category 2: commercially used plants) in South Africa (Henderson, 2001). Pines and other alien plants have been recognised as invasive species in fynbos since the 1920s (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). *P. radiata* is also known to invade forest gaps (Henderson, 2001), but severe disturbance is needed to assist seedling recruitment in native forest, since by virtue of their structure, forests resist invasion (Richardson *et al.*, 1994). Consequently, Afrotropical forest is less vulnerable to invasion by pine than fynbos, even when forest patches are adjacent to pine stands (Richardson *et al.*, 1994).

Although facilitated by their long planting history, the life history strategies of these two pine species have largely determined their invasion success. Their good dispersal ability (small seeds, low seed-wing loading, and long distance wind dispersal) facilitates invasion (Richardson *et al.*, 1990). In addition, their superior fire-resilience, compared with indigenous species, enables pines to persist and disrupt the natural non-equilibrium system (Richardson *et al.*, 1990). Fire-resilience is achieved by a combination of rapid growth to maturity and accumulation

of large seed reserves in the canopy (Richardson & Cowling, 1992). Pines have a tendency to form dense thickets, and often out-compete fynbos shrubs in areas recovering from fire (Richardson *et al.*, 1994). Most pine seedlings establish in the first two years after fire in fynbos, when native plant cover is low (Richardson & Cowling, 1992).

Increasing alien plant invasions pose the greatest threat to biodiversity on the Cape Peninsula (Richardson *et al.*, 1996). The invasive spread of alien woody species from commercial plantations into adjacent native vegetation threatens areas set aside for conservation (Armstrong *et al.*, 1998), such as Table Mountain National Park. This has important management implications where biodiversity conservation is a primary objective. Local extinction of many fynbos plant species has been reported following pine invasion (Richardson & van Wilgen, 1986; Richardson *et al.*, 1989). Most fynbos species are unable to withstand shading under pine, although some native geophytes, including *Ornithogalum* and *Moraea*, do persist (Adamson, 1927). This has implications for native plant and animal distributions, and for the rehabilitation of clear-felled pine areas.

Study sites

Thirty-two sites were selected at eight localities across the eastern slopes of Table Mountain National Park, which lies within the northern section of the Cape Peninsula (Fig. 2.1, Appendix 2a). These sites were located from north to south in Newlands Forest, Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, Cecilia Plantation, Orange Kloof Forest Station, and Tokai Plantation, with roughly 12 km between the northern- and southern-most sites. The eight clusters, each consisting of four sites, were selected to replicate each of the four 'vegetation types' or habitats: (1) Western Cape Afrotropical Forest, (2) Peninsula Sandstone Fynbos or Peninsula Granite Fynbos, (3) commercial pine plantation (*Pinus pinaster* or *P. radiata*), and (4) recently clear-felled pine plantation. The 'ideal' scenario of forest, fynbos, pine plantation and clear-felled pine sites together in one area was only possible at Rooikat and Spilhaus Ravines in Cecilia Plantation, and Tokai N (Boekenhoutkloof) and Tokai S (Prinskasteel) in Tokai Plantation. The remaining four areas had two sites of the same habitat to make up a total of eight replicates per habitat. Where two sites of the same habitat were sampled in an area, these sites were not contiguous, to avoid pseudoreplication.

Figure 2.1. Location of 32 study sites in Table Mountain National Park (right) on the Cape Peninsula, South Africa. Map of South Africa (top left) shows the Fynbos Biome (in grey). Cape Peninsula (bottom left) shows the distribution of native vegetation sampled: Peninsula Sandstone Fynbos (light grey), Peninsula Granite Fynbos (dark grey) and Western Cape Afrotemperate Forest (black). See Appendix 2a for site information.

Pilot study

A pilot study was conducted at Cecilia in mid May 2008 (late autumn, after the first winter rains) to refine the proposed collecting methods and sampling intensity. One site each in contiguous Afrotropical forest (Site 9, Rooikat Ravine), Sandstone Fynbos (site 10) and pine plantation (Site 11) was sampled for ground-dwelling invertebrates (see Appendix 2a for site details). At each site, five leaf litter samples, 10 soil samples, 10 pitfall traps, 10 sugar-baited ant traps and one decayed log sample were collected (see full-scale study sampling methods below for details).

Sample-based randomized species-accumulation curves (Gotelli & Colwell, 2001) were plotted using S_{obs} Mao Tau, calculated in EstimateS version 8 (Colwell, 2006), to test sampling saturation. Sampling intensity was fairly low and as a result sampling saturation was not fully achieved for all species combined, for higher invertebrate taxa, or sampling methods. However, it should be appreciated that sampling saturation is seldom achieved for multi-taxa terrestrial invertebrate surveys, even with intensive sampling (Gotelli & Colwell, 2001), and it is therefore a trade-off against logistical, time and cost constraints.

The pilot study thus achieved the objectives to (a) gain insight on the number and groups of invertebrates to be collected, and (b) refine the proposed collecting methods and sampling intensity (number of replicates per site). Besides doubling the number of leaf litter (from five to ten) and decayed log (from one to two) replicates per site, the same protocols from the pilot study were used in the full-scale study.

Sampling methods

Full-scale study sampling methods

Sites were selected in the approximate centre of a patch of vegetation, depending on accessibility. At each of the 32 sites (except Site 11), a range of sampling methods, both active and passive, was employed to sample ground-dwelling invertebrates. These methods included leaf litter samples, soil samples, pitfall traps, sugar-baited ant traps, and decayed logs. Twenty-five days were spent in the field, sampling between 08h00 and 14h00 (*i.e.* 150 sampling hours). The order in which the eight clusters of sites were sampled was randomly chosen and different in 2008 and 2009, to avoid possible unwanted spatial autocorrelation (Legendre, 1993) between the north-south alignment of sites and the date of sampling. Leaf litter and soil sampling took place from mid September to late November 2008 (*i.e.* spring to early summer). Pitfall trap,

sugar-baited ant trap, and decayed log sampling took place from early January to late February 2009 (*i.e.* late summer, dry season). The entire block of pine plantation at Site 11 (Rooikat, Cecilia) was unexpectedly felled in January 2009, so no pitfall traps, ant traps, or decayed logs were sampled, and this site was omitted from analyses.

Ten leaf litter samples per site were collected to sample leaf litter invertebrates, by filling a 2 l container with leaf litter every 5 m along a transect. Ten soil samples per site were collected to sample soil invertebrates. One 500 ml soil sample was taken every 5 m along a transect, by clearing away surface vegetation and litter, digging a hole with a small trowel, and removing soil from 150 mm depth. Litter and soil samples were stored in sealed plastic bags and kept cool (in a constant environment room set at 10°C) to minimize decomposition, prevent invertebrates from dying, and immobilize predaceous animals until samples were sorted. All samples were sorted within two weeks of collection, with survival of invertebrates not affected by this storage period.

Ten pitfall and ten ant traps per site were left in the field for seven days to collect ground-dwelling invertebrates not easily sampled using other methods. Pitfall traps were 450 ml round, clear plastic tubs (85 mm deep and 100 mm diameter opening), half filled with 50% ethylene glycol (antifreeze) and placed at 5 m intervals along a transect. Every second tub was covered with an inverted plastic flower pot drip tray (160 mm diameter), raised 100 mm above ground level on a wire frame, to reduce evaporation, prevent rain from flooding the traps, and limit the quantity of leaves and twigs that fell into the tub. Ten sugar-baited ant traps per site were set to specifically target ants that are attracted to a carbohydrate source. Ant traps used the same plastic tubs and covers as pitfall traps, and were left in the field for the same six days. Ant trap tubs were placed at 5 m intervals along a transect that ran parallel to, but 5 m from, the pitfall traps. Tubs were half filled with a 20% sucrose solution. All invertebrates collected in the pitfall and ant traps were thoroughly rinsed in tap water before preservation.

Two decayed logs of approximately 1.5 m length and 0.2 m diameter, in an advanced state of decay, were selected at each site to sample saproxylic invertebrates. Each log was transferred to a large, white, plastic sheet, and sorted in the field by systematically breaking apart the entire log, removing and preserving all invertebrates. Only two logs per site were sampled, because time constraints (logs had to be sorted on site) and availability of suitably decayed logs (especially in fynbos) limited this number.

Environmental variables

Basic environmental variables were recorded at all 32 sites. GPS coordinates were recorded in the field using a hand-held Garmin GPS and checked against Google Earth 5.0. Altitude (elevation) recorded in the field proved unreliable, so mean altitude was taken from the 1:20 000 Table Mountain hiking map (Slingsby, 2007). The habitat at each site (1000 m²) was visually scored according to canopy cover (%), ground cover (%), leaf litter (%), rocks (%), and shrubs less than 1 m (%).

Soil pH, moisture, and organic content were measured in the laboratory. Soil samples were weighed in their sealed bags within 24 hours of collection, using a 600 g balance, to determine “wet weight”. Soil pH was measured by mixing 12.5 ml of soil in 12.5 ml distilled water, shaking the mixture for 30 seconds, allowing it to settle for five minutes, and measuring the pH of the supernatant liquid with a hand-held Crison pH meter. Mean soil pH was calculated for five randomly chosen soil samples per site.

After removing all invertebrates from each sample, all soil was returned to the plastic bag and re-weighed to account for any loss (typically up to 10 g loss, largely due to removal for pH measurement). This new weight was used as the wet soil weight. Open plastic soil bags were dried in an oven at 60°C for at least 36 h, or until completely dried. Dry soil was weighed to determine weight loss due to moisture content of the soil. Soil moisture was calculated as:

$$\text{Soil moisture} = \frac{\text{wet weight} - \text{dry weight}}{\text{wet weight}}$$

Soil organic content was measured by further drying soil samples in a muffle furnace at 400°C for 4 h, to burn off all organic content (including roots, twigs, and leaves) in the soil. Soil was then cooled to room temperature and weighed. Soil organic content was calculated as:

$$\text{Soil organic content} = \frac{\text{dry weight} - \text{muffle dried weight}}{\text{dry weight}}$$

Despite the high range of values (Table 2.1), one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed significant differences among habitats for soil pH ($F = 36.654$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.001$) and soil moisture ($F = 19.062$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.001$). Due to technical failure of the muffle furnace, soil organic content was only calculated for Sites 1 to 11. No significant difference ($F = 0.471$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.641$) in soil organic content was found among forest ($n = 4$ sites), fynbos ($n = 4$ sites) and pine plantation ($n = 3$ sites), probably due to high variance within sites. Soil organic content was therefore considered an unreliable explanatory variable, and not used in further analyses.

Table 2.1. Descriptive statistics for soil pH, moisture and organic content in each habitat.

Habitat	pH				Moisture (%)				Organic content (%)			
	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD
Forest	4.6	6.9	6.15	0.53	9.2	70.9	32.19	13.80	2.6	74.8	24.57	18.50
Fynbos	4.2	6.7	5.56	0.55	2.3	56.5	18.04	11.90	4.8	85.3	18.31	19.19
Pine	4.5	6.5	5.50	0.48	5.2	71.4	33.33	14.95	9.1	81.5	28.12	16.06
Felled	4.3	5.9	4.99	0.42	2.1	70.4	25.71	16.70				

Invertebrate identification

All invertebrates, except earthworms and moths (for the full-scale study) and unidentifiable nymphs and larvae (for both the pilot and full-scale studies), were sorted to morphospecies using easily recognisable morphological differences (*sensu* Oliver & Beattie, 1996). As many taxa as possible were sent to specialists for further identification (Appendix 2b). Morphospecies are referred to as species hereafter. The reference collections for taxa identified by experts have been deposited in the respective museums of their home countries, while a reference collection of the remaining taxa has been deposited in the Iziko South African Museum, Cape Town.

Appendix 2a. Location of 32 study sites across the eight areas sampled in Table Mountain National Park, on the Cape Peninsula.

Site	Area	Landmark	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	GPS coordinates (WGS 84 Spheroid Standard)		Vegetation
1	Newlands	Above reservoir	230	33° 57' 58.3" S	18° 26' 31.6" E	Afrotemperate forest
2	Newlands	Above reservoir	200	33° 57' 51.9" S	18° 26' 25.1" E	Pine plantation
3	Newlands	Beyond weir	270	33° 58' 17.5" S	18° 26' 23.4" E	Sandstone Fynbos
4	Newlands	Beyond weir	260	33° 58' 24.5" S	18° 26' 27.1" E	Pine plantation
5	Kirstenbosch	Skeleton Gorge	400	33° 58' 55.0" S	18° 25' 25.0" E	Afrotemperate forest
6	Kirstenbosch	Skeleton Gorge	330	33° 59' 03.2" S	18° 25' 28.4" E	Granite Fynbos
7	Kirstenbosch	Nursery Ravine	380	33° 59' 12.6" S	18° 25' 18.7" E	Afrotemperate forest
8	Kirstenbosch	Nursery Ravine	350	33° 59' 17.8" S	18° 25' 19.2" E	Granite Fynbos
9	Cecilia, Rooikat	Rooikat Ravine	400	33° 59' 33.8" S	18° 25' 12.0" E	Afrotemperate forest
10	Cecilia, Rooikat	Rooikat Ravine	430	33° 59' 36.9" S	18° 25' 11.0" E	Sandstone Fynbos
11*	Cecilia, Rooikat	Rooikat Ravine	320	33° 59' 46.0" S	18° 25' 20.8" E	Pine plantation
12	Cecilia, Rooikat	Rooikat Ravine	300	33° 59' 42.9" S	18° 25' 21.6" E	Clear-felled pine
13	Cecilia, Spilhaus	Cecilia Waterfall	400	33° 59' 43.5" S	18° 25' 05.4" E	Afrotemperate forest
14	Cecilia, Spilhaus	Spilhaus Ravine	520	33° 59' 53.7" S	18° 24' 51.6" E	Sandstone Fynbos
15	Cecilia, Spilhaus	Spilhaus Ravine	450	33° 59' 55.7" S	18° 25' 01.4" E	Pine plantation
16	Cecilia, Spilhaus	Spilhaus Ravine	470	34° 00' 03.7" S	18° 24' 45.6" E	Clear-felled pine
17	Constantia Nek	Eagle's Nest	390	34° 00' 23.1" S	18° 24' 17.7" E	Sandstone Fynbos
18	Constantia Nek	Bridle Path	340	34° 00' 15.2" S	18° 24' 46.6" E	Pine plantation
19	Constantia Nek	Bridle Path	330	34° 00' 19.6" S	18° 24' 45.4" E	Clear-felled pine
20	Constantia Nek	Steps	280	34° 00' 31.6" S	18° 24' 19.4" E	Clear-felled pine
21	Orange Kloof	Above weir	130	34° 00' 12.3" S	18° 23' 25.8" E	Afrotemperate forest
22	Orange Kloof	Filtration plant	240	34° 00' 22.8" S	18° 24' 01.6" E	Pine plantation
23	Orange Kloof	Logging road	180	34° 00' 00.6" S	18° 23' 40.2" E	Clear-felled pine
24	Orange Kloof	Logging road	180	34° 00' 18.9" S	18° 23' 45.5" E	Clear-felled pine
25	Tokai N	Boekenhoutkloof	370	34° 02' 17.0" S	18° 23' 44.1" E	Afrotemperate forest
26	Tokai N	Boekenhoutkloof	360	34° 02' 15.9" S	18° 23' 48.8" E	Sandstone Fynbos
27	Tokai N	Boekenhoutkloof	330	34° 02' 23.5" S	18° 23' 53.3" E	Pine plantation
28	Tokai N	Boekenhoutkloof	280	34° 02' 23.1" S	18° 23' 52.5" E	Clear-felled pine
29	Tokai S	Prinskasteel	240	34° 03' 56.1" S	18° 24' 05.4" E	Afrotemperate forest
30	Tokai S	Prinskasteel	310	34° 04' 01.1" S	18° 24' 02.8" E	Sandstone Fynbos
31	Tokai S	Prinskasteel	300	34° 03' 54.3" S	18° 24' 10.2" E	Pine plantation
32	Tokai S	Prinskasteel	230	34° 03' 59.9" S	18° 24' 09.8" E	Clear-felled pine

* The entire pine block was unexpectedly felled in January 2009, and consequently no pitfall traps, sugar-baited ant traps or decayed logs were sampled.

Appendix 2b. Names, institutes and countries of taxonomic experts who assisted with species level identification of selected groups.

Taxon	Name	Institute	City, Country	Pilot	Full-scale
Amphipoda, Isopoda	Charles Griffiths	University of Cape Town	Cape Town, South Africa		*
Araneae (preliminary identification)	Norman Larsen	Iziko South African Museum	Cape Town, South Africa	*	
Araneae: Corrinidae, Salticidae	Charles Haddad	University of the Free State	Bloemfontein, South Africa	*	
Araneae	Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman	ARC - Plant Protection Research Institute	Pretoria, South Africa	*	*
Blattodea	Horst Bohn	Zoologische Staatssammlung München	München, Germany	*	*
Coleoptera	Peter Hammond	The Natural History Museum	London, England		*
Coleoptera: Pselaphinae	Peter Hlaváč	Private	Košice, Slovakia		*
Coleoptera: Scarabaeoidea	Francois Roets	University of Stellenbosch	Stellenbosch, South Africa		*
Collembola	Ernest Bernard	University of Tennessee	Knoxville, USA		*
Diplopoda	Michelle Hamer	South African National Biodiversity Institute	Pretoria, South Africa	*	*
Diplopoda: Penicillata	Monique Nguyen Duy-Jacquemin	Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle	Paris, France		*
Hemiptera: Cicadellidoidea, Fulgoroidea	Michael Stiller	ARC - Plant Protection Research Institute	Pretoria, South Africa		*
Hemiptera: Reduviidae	Patrick Reavell	University of Stellenbosch	Stellenbosch, South Africa		*
Hymenoptera: Formicidae	Nokuthula Mbanyana	Iziko South African Museum	Cape Town, South Africa		*
Hymenoptera: Amiseginae	Simon van Noort	Iziko South African Museum	Cape Town, South Africa		*
Mollusca	Dai Herbert	Natal Museum	Pietermaritzburg, South Africa	*	*
Oligochaeta	Danuta Plisko	Natal Museum	Pietermaritzburg, South Africa	*	
Onychophora, Coleoptera, Hemiptera, Hymenoptera, Orthoptera	Mike Picker	University of Cape Town	Cape Town, South Africa	*	*
Psocoptera	Charles Lienhard	Museum of Natural History	Geneva, Switzerland	*	*
Scorpiones, Solifugae	Lorenzo Prendini	American Museum of Natural History	New York, USA		*

CHAPTER 3. THE INFLUENCE OF ALIEN PINE PLANTATIONS ON INVERTEBRATE SPECIES RICHNESS AND COMMUNITY COMPOSITION ON THE CAPE PENINSULA

Introduction

Plantations are popularly considered 'biological deserts' (Bonham *et al.*, 2002; Hartley, 2002; Brockerhoff *et al.*, 2008), and perceived to support impoverished faunal diversity compared to nearby native forests (Lachat *et al.*, 2006). A global review of biodiversity in plantations revealed a general trend (94% of studies) of lower diversity of invertebrates, birds, mammals, and plants in single-species exotic plantations compared to natural forests (Stephens & Wagner, 2007). Furthermore, 57% of studies comparing exotic plantations to non-forested natural ecosystems, such as grasslands and fynbos, also report lower diversity in plantations (Stephens & Wagner, 2007). In the Brazilian Amazon, lower species richness in exotic plantations compared to primary rainforest has been reported for birds (Barlow *et al.*, 2007a), lizards and amphibians (Gardner *et al.*, 2007), and dung beetles (Gardner *et al.*, 2008). Lower species richness in exotic conifer plantations, compared to native *Nothofagus* forest, has also been reported for native birds in New Zealand (Clout & Gaze, 1984), and for understory plants, epigeal beetles, and birds in Argentinean Patagonia (Paritsis & Aizen, 2008).

Similar trends are apparent for South African plantations. Ant diversity (Donnelly & Giliomee, 1985) and bird diversity (Armstrong & van Hensbergen, 1994) are lower in pine plantations than in fynbos. On the Cape Peninsula, pine plantations support low native plant diversity (Cowling *et al.*, 1979) and low invertebrate diversity (Pryke & Samways, 2009b). Species richness of litter invertebrate communities in pine plantations may be half that of contiguous Afrotropical forest (Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002; Rahinjanahary, 2007). In KwaZulu-Natal Province, similar trends of reduced diversity in plantations have been reported for grasshoppers (Samways & Moore, 1991), butterflies (Wood & Samways, 1991), ground-dwelling invertebrates (Samways *et al.*, 1996), spiders (van der Merwe *et al.*, 1996), and birds (Armstrong & van Hensbergen, 1995; 1996). Likewise, in Mpumalanga Province, plantations have a negative impact on grassland bird diversity, especially globally threatened species (Allan *et al.*, 1997). However, it should be noted that diversity in plantations is not always as low as expected. Samways *et al.* (1996) report lower (but not significantly so) species richness under several invasive alien plant species, compared to native vegetation.

In addition to impoverished species richness, the composition of invertebrate community assemblages in exotic plantations often differ from those of adjacent native vegetation (e.g.

Samways *et al.*, 1996; Barlow *et al.*, 2007b). Plantation communities are often dominated by widespread, generalist species (Magura *et al.*, 2000; Sinclair & New, 2004; Gardner *et al.*, 2007; Brockerhoff *et al.*, 2008), and several native species may be absent in exotic plantations (Tattersfield *et al.*, 2001; Bonham *et al.*, 2002). This is relevant for conservation, especially when the species absent in plantations include rare, endemic taxa. The impact of woody invasives is particularly severe in areas supporting exceptional invertebrate endemism, such as the Cape Peninsula (Picker & Samways, 1996).

The aim of this study is to assess the impact of pine plantations on the species richness and community composition of ground-dwelling invertebrates in Table Mountain National Park on the Cape Peninsula. Pine plantations are hypothesized to support lower invertebrate species richness, compared to surrounding (often contiguous) native forest and fynbos. Based on the findings of Ratsirarson *et al.* (2002) and Rahinjanahary (2007), species richness in pine plantations is predicted to be at least half that of Afrotropical forest. Plantations are known to provide litter and dead wood microhabitats that broadly mimic those in forest, often supporting native forest invertebrate species. The invertebrate community in pine plantations is further hypothesized to be more similar to that of forest than fynbos, even though these pine plantations originally replaced Peninsula Granite Fynbos (T. Rebelo pers. comm., 2010).

To appropriately assess the impacts of pine plantations on invertebrate diversity, species richness and community composition should both be assessed. Species richness is intuitively the simplest metric for biodiversity assessments, and has been widely employed to explain spatial patterns of diversity, such as latitudinal and altitudinal gradients, species-area curves and island assemblages (Magurran, 2004). Yet, species richness alone may be inadequate as a diversity measure (Ma, 2005). In its simplest form, richness ignores the taxonomic identity of species, and thus their rarity, endemism, threat status, or conservation value. Community analyses take into account both the identity and abundance of species, thereby adding value to the overall assessment of community composition. Species richness measures only α diversity (diversity within habitats), and does not account for changes in diversity across environmental gradients, or species turnover (β diversity) among habitats (Magurran, 2004).

Methods

Study sites and collecting methods

Refer to Chapter 2 for the location of the sites sampled and collecting methods used in Western Cape Afrotropical Forest (n = 8 sites), fynbos (n = 8 sites: six Peninsula Sandstone Fynbos

and two Peninsula Granite Fynbos), and pine plantation (n = 7 sites) in Table Mountain National Park. Site 11 (pine plantation in Cecilia) was omitted from all analyses, because it was clear-felled in January 2009 (ahead of the Mountain to Ocean (MTO) Forestry Pty (Ltd) proposed felling schedule). Consequently, no pitfall traps, sugar-baited ant traps or decayed logs were sampled at Site 11, compromising its comparability with other sites. For each of the other 23 sites, data from the replicates (10 leaf litter, 10 soil, 10 pitfall trap, 10 sugar-baited ant trap, and two decayed log samples) were pooled for a single species richness value per site to avoid problems of pseudoreplication (Hurlbert & Hurlbert, 2004), inherent spatial autocorrelation within sites (Legendre & Legendre, 1998), and differences in catches amongst collecting methods.

Species richness analyses

Species-accumulation curves for the observed species richness of forest, fynbos and pine plantation were calculated using S_{obs} Mao Tau sample-based rarefaction curves, randomised 50 times in EstimateS version 8 (Colwell, 2006). Estimated species richness based on abundance (ACE and Chao 1) and incidence (ICE and Chao 2) was also calculated for forest, fynbos and pine plantation in EstimateS. The coverage-based species richness estimators, ACE (abundance-based coverage estimator) and ICE (incidence-based coverage estimator) recognise the contribution of rare (less than 10 individuals) species (Magurran, 2004). Chao's classic species richness estimators, like coverage estimators, are non-parametric and provide a minimum estimate of richness, with the assumption of homogeneity amongst samples (Magurran, 2004). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to test for differences in the species richness amongst forest, fynbos and pine plantation, using STATISTICA version 9 (StatSoft, Inc., 2009).

Community composition analyses

A triangular matrix of Bray-Curtis similarity of $\log_e(x + 1)$ transformed community composition between sites was used to map the interrelationships of invertebrate communities in cluster analysis using complete linkage clustering, and ordination by non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), in PRIMER version 6 (Clarke & Gorley, 2006). Data were log transformed to down-weight highly abundant species. Matrices were also constructed for alternative transformations (square root, fourth-root, and presence-absence), but all gave similar results to log transformed distance, and hence results from those analyses are not reported. Cluster analysis is a simple and intuitively meaningful method used to find natural grouping of samples or sites (Magurran, 2004). MDS is also widely used for graphical representation of community

relationships because of its conceptual simplicity, flexibility, dependence only on a biologically meaningful view of the data, independence of normally distributed data with equal variance between samples, and its distance preserving properties (Clarke, 1993; Clarke & Warwick, 2001). In an MDS plot, the x-axis represents the direction of maximum variation, with the position of samples (or sites in this case) reflecting their similarity. The stress value acts as a measure of reliability, since the risk of drawing false inferences from an ordination increases with greater stress. Stress values of less than 0.2 are considered reliable.

Invertebrate diversity was related to normalised environmental variables using BEST, BIOENV (Clarke & Ainsworth, 1993) in PRIMER. Two nominal (area and vegetation type) and five continuous (latitude, longitude, elevation, soil pH, and soil moisture) variables were tested. BIOENV calculates the Spearman rank correlation (ρ) between the similarity matrix and corresponding environmental variables, to identify which environmental variables best explain the community pattern.

The same Bray-Curtis similarity matrix of log transformed data was used for pairwise analysis of similarity (ANOSIM), to test the null hypothesis of no difference in invertebrate community composition amongst forest, fynbos and pine plantation. ANOSIM is the non-parametric, multivariate equivalent of ANOVA, applied to the rank similarity matrix using a permutation procedure (999 permutations) in PRIMER (Clarke & Green, 1988). It calculates the R statistic, which provides a relative measure of separation of predefined groups, and ranges from zero (no difference among groups) to one (all samples within groups are more similar to one another than to any samples from another group). ANOSIM was used to confirm whether the cluster patterns identified in the dendrogram and ordination were statistically significant.

Results

Species richness

A total of 92 109 individuals from 670 species was collected from the 23 sites sampled. These species spanned five invertebrate phyla (Annelida, Arthropoda, Mollusca, Onychophora, and Platyhelminthes), 10 classes, and 38 orders. Species richness ranged from 132-180 species in forest, 65-118 in fynbos, and 83-135 in pine plantation. Mean species richness was higher in forest (154.6 ± 16.3 SD species) than in both fynbos (99.9 ± 16.7) and pine plantation (107.9 ± 20.6).

Cumulative observed species richness was also higher in forest (455 ± 15.5 SD species) than in both fynbos (365 ± 14.3) and pine plantation (311 ± 14.0). Sampling, as expected,

approached, but did not achieve, saturation (Fig. 3.1). Consequently, estimated species richness was higher than observed species richness in all three habitats for all richness estimators used (Fig. 3.2). Estimated species richness based on incidence (ICE and Chao 2) was higher in all habitats than when based on abundance (ACE and Chao 1), reflecting the high percentage of singletons. Species richness was 1.4-1.5 times higher in forest than in pine plantation, 1.2-1.5 times higher in forest than in fynbos, and 1.0-1.2 times higher in fynbos than in pine plantation. Ratios varied marginally between observed and estimated species richness, and among estimators. Nevertheless, the pattern of highest species richness in forest persisted across all estimators, suggesting that the sampling methods employed accurately represented the true pattern of ground-dwelling invertebrate species richness.

Figure 3.1. Sample-based species-accumulation curves of observed invertebrate species richness in forest, fynbos, and pine plantation. Curves were calculated using S_{obs} Mao Tau and randomised 50 times.

ANOVA showed a highly significant difference ($F = 21.693$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$) between forest, fynbos and pine plantation species richness. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov test confirmed that the residuals were normally distributed ($p = 0.936$), and a Levene's test confirmed that the variance of the residuals was equal among the three habitats ($F = 0.855$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.440$). Tukey HSD for unequal N post hoc tests showed that the species richness of forest differed significantly from that of fynbos and pine plantation ($p < 0.001$), but fynbos and pine plantation

did not differ significantly in species richness ($p = 0.668$). This confirms the patterns of observed and estimated species richness (Figs 3.1 and 3.2).

Figure 3.2. Mean \pm SD observed species richness (S_{obs} Mao Tau) and estimated species richness based on abundance (ACE and Chao 1) and incidence (ICE and Chao 2).

Community composition

Invertebrate community composition differed among sites within habitats, and among habitats (forest, fynbos, and pine plantation). However, sites clustered into distinct groups according to habitat, with low (ca. 15-25%) similarity among habitats, and with forest and pine plantation communities more similar to each other than to fynbos (Fig. 3.3a). Similarly, the MDS plot (Fig. 3.3b) showed forest and pine plantation sites clustered in two distinct groups close to, but not overlapping, each other. Fynbos sites separated from forest and pine plantation on the x-axis, but showed little similarity to one another, separating out across the y-axis into three clusters: Granite Fynbos (Sites 6 and 8), Sandstone Fynbos (Sites 10, 14, 17 and 26), and recovering Sandstone Fynbos that was previously under pine (Sites 3 and 30). BIOENV identified vegetation type as the strongest driver of invertebrate community composition ($\rho = 0.670$), followed by a combination of vegetation type and soil moisture ($\rho = 0.553$). All top ten BEST, BIOENV results included vegetation type as an explanatory variable for community composition.

Figure 3.3. (a) Cluster analysis and (b) ordination from non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), applied to a Bray-Curtis similarity matrix of log transformed invertebrate community composition amongst sites. Numbers refer to sites (see Chapter 2) and symbols to habitats.

ANOSIM confirmed that community composition differed significantly among habitats. Forest community composition differed the most compared to pine plantation ($R = 0.927$, $p = 0.001$) and fynbos ($R = 0.768$, $p = 0.001$), with little difference between fynbos and pine plantation habitats ($R = 0.589$, $p = 0.001$), as seen in the MDS ordination. Fynbos supports the least distinctive invertebrate community, because it shares species with both forest and pine plantation, and is the most heterogeneous habitat, with the highest plant diversity.

Discussion

Species richness

Pine plantations supported a surprisingly rich ground-dwelling invertebrate assemblage, albeit less rich than in surrounding native habitats (311 species in pine plantation compared to 365 in fynbos and 455 in forest). Species richness was significantly lower in pine plantation than in forest, but not significantly lower than in fynbos. This finding is not entirely unexpected. According to Stephens & Wagner (2007), the worldwide literature reports generally lower biodiversity in plantations compared to natural forests (94% of studies), but relatively comparable richness compared to non-forested natural ecosystems (only 57% of studies report lower diversity in plantations).

Contrary to prediction based on previous work done in the same area on litter invertebrates, species richness in pine plantations was not half that of Afrotropical forest. Forest was on average only 1.5 times richer than pine plantation, compared to the 2.2 times (Rahinjanahary, 2007) and 2.4 times (Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002) reported in earlier studies, and on which this prediction was based. Interestingly, for the same sites sampled in Newlands Forest, the observed species richness was 1.3 times higher in forest than in pine plantation for both this study and Ratsirarson *et al.* (2002), despite their limited suite of taxa sampled (Hymenoptera, Opiliones, and Amphipoda) and single sampling method (Winkler bag sifted leaf litter extractions). It was previously not known whether Newlands Forest, the only area sampled by Ratsirarson *et al.* (2002) and Rahinjanahary (2007), is indeed representative of forest ground-dwelling invertebrate diversity patterns across the Cape Peninsula. Newlands Forest does appear to be fairly representative (at least in forest and pine plantation), since invertebrate species richness estimates for the eight areas sampled across the Cape Peninsula suggest Afrotropical forests were 1.5 times richer than pine plantations. However, species richness varied considerably across sites for all three habitats.

Fynbos supported comparatively low species richness, and is generally considered to support low diversity of ground-dwelling invertebrates (Giliomee, 2003), although quantitative, comparative studies are rare. Procheş & Cowling (2006) suggest that fynbos is not as insect-poor as previously thought, because previous generalisations were based on a handful of insect taxa, which appear to be under-represented in fynbos. In their comparative study of fynbos, grassland, thicket, and karoo vegetation, Procheş & Cowling (2006) found that fynbos insect diversity was comparable to grassland and subtropical thicket, and richer than Nama-Karoo. This study is also not in agreement with previous findings of higher species richness in fynbos

than in forest for epigaeic invertebrates (147 species in fynbos and 123 in forest; Pryke & Samways, 2010) and aerial invertebrates (126 species in fynbos and 62 in forest; Pryke & Samways, 2008). Pryke & Samways' findings are likely to be artefacts of the high heterogeneity in fynbos vegetation types sampled around the Cape Peninsula. The present study attempted to circumvent possible confounding abiotic and biotic heterogeneity in fynbos by controlling (as far as possible) for aspect, elevation and vegetation type.

Community composition

Community composition was significantly different in forest, fynbos and pine plantation, with 15-25% similarity among habitats. Distinct faunal assemblages associated with different habitats have been recorded in a range of forest/plantation habitats. Samways *et al.* (1996) found different invertebrate assemblages in exotic plantations and invasive plants compared to native woodland and grassland, with many species restricted to native vegetation, as in this study. Lachat *et al.* (2006) found different arthropod communities in natural forest, young plantations, and old plantations in Lama Forest reserve (South Benin), with the lowest species richness recorded in young plantations. Hopp *et al.* (2010) also found different litter-inhabiting beetle communities in young secondary and old-growth forests in the Atlantic Forest of Southern Brazil, suggesting that time since disturbance strongly influences community composition. Older plantation stands, like primary, old-growth forests, generally offer more spatial and vertical heterogeneity, well developed soil organic layers, and accumulated litter and dead wood than young stands or young secondary forests, and consequently can support higher diversity (Brockerhoff *et al.*, 2008). In this study, forest had the longest "time since disturbance", having been protected from logging since 1888. Forest supported the most distinctive invertebrate assemblage (based on ANOSIM results), with fynbos and pine plantation probably having roughly equivalent disturbance histories based on time since last fire (in fynbos) and time since last planting (in pine). Actual dates of last fire and planting were not available for all sites sampled, and so disturbance history was not included as an explanatory variable in analyses, although the relationship is intuitively evident.

The invertebrate communities of pine plantations were more similar to those of forest than fynbos. Pine plantations, by offering a comparable litter and dead wood microhabitat to that of forest, extend the distribution range of numerous forest invertebrates, including rare and endemic species. Plantations may also buffer edge effects for small forest patches and increase connectivity (Brockerhoff *et al.*, 2008). Although increased available habitat and connectivity between patches is often desirable in biodiversity conservation, connectivity may have negative

consequences. Afrotemperate forest patches across the Cape Peninsula are naturally small and fragmented (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006), and so the connectivity provided by plantations has several possible disadvantages. Plantations may facilitate the spread of weeds, pathogens, pests, and inappropriate genetic material (MacDonald, 2003). Providing connectivity between diverging metapopulations of habitat-restricted taxa may facilitate genetic mixing between populations, and thus reduce the evolutionary potential of such populations, which is not desirable for biodiversity conservation. For many forest species, the fynbos matrix surrounding forest islands may be an effective barrier to migration and gene flow. Under natural conditions, these Afrotemperate forest patches also characteristically have sharp edges maintained by frequent fires in the fynbos matrix. The establishment of pine plantations has altered the natural fire regime in fynbos (van Wilgen, 2009), with knock-on effects for invertebrate communities.

The impact of pine plantations may also be negative for many fynbos invertebrates, which cannot colonise and persist in the dense litter and closed canopy tree environment of plantations. Of particular concern is the impact of pine on Peninsula Granite Fynbos and its associated invertebrate community, because this vegetation type is listed as 'Endangered', with very little remaining (Granite Fynbos covers only 2% of the Fynbos Biome), and most of the Peninsula Granite Fynbos is senescent and invaded by Afrotemperate forest trees (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). All pine plantation sites sampled originally replaced Granite Fynbos, which generally occurs at lower altitudes and on richer soil than Sandstone Fynbos. However, pine plantation sites clustered closer to Sandstone Fynbos sites than to Granite Fynbos sites in the MDS ordination. The Granite Fynbos invertebrate community (at Sites 6 and 8) was very different from communities in other vegetation types. This suggests that the fynbos invertebrate species that have established in these pine plantations come from the surrounding, often contiguous, Sandstone Fynbos patches. The true Peninsula Granite Fynbos invertebrate community may already be lost on the Cape Peninsula.

Vegetation type (or structure) was the most important environmental variable explaining invertebrate community composition among habitats. Vegetation structure (forest and fynbos) and elevation have also previously been identified as the most important variables for both surface-active invertebrates (Pryke & Samways, 2010) and aerial and foliage invertebrates (Pryke & Samways, 2008) on Table Mountain. Fynbos type (namely Granite Fynbos and Sandstone Fynbos) appears to strongly influence the invertebrate community, with fynbos sites separating into three clusters: Peninsula Granite Fynbos, Peninsula Sandstone Fynbos and recovering Peninsula Sandstone Fynbos. Sites 6 and 8 were the only Granite Fynbos sites sampled. They were also the only fynbos sites not in close proximity to pine plantations, as

there are no plantations in or above Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden. By comparison, other areas sampled had pine plantation on the lower slopes, buffering the National Park from the suburbs and/or vineyards. A possible further explanation for differences in community composition between the two Granite Fynbos sites above Kirstenbosch Botanical Garden, compared to other sites, could be the influence of the botanical garden itself. Pryke & Samways (2009b) report very high species richness and abundance of both ground-dwelling and aerial invertebrates in Kirstenbosch Botanical Garden. They attribute this difference to the fact that the botanical garden is cultivating many indigenous plants, which provide habitat for a wide range of invertebrate species, and comprises a pesticide-free, well-watered and well-managed source of invertebrates to colonise adjacent areas of Table Mountain. To confound matters further, Sites 6 and 8 were moribund and invaded by some Afrotropical forest trees as a result of the long-reigning fire exclusion policy in place in Kirstenbosch. Under more natural conditions fynbos maintains dominance in the landscape through regular natural burning, since fire excludes forest tree species (Rebello *et al.*, 2006 and references therein). Nevertheless, they showed very little community similarity with either forest or pine plantation. Sandstone Fynbos communities also formed a separate cluster, as did recovering Sandstone Fynbos communities previously under pine. Interestingly, the latter clustered closer to pine plantation communities than to other fynbos sites, suggesting that they share more taxa in common with pine plantation than with other fynbos sites. The impacts of pine plantations appear to persist long after clear-felling, as seen from the community composition of Sandstone Fynbos sites previously under pine. Afforestation of natural non-forest land, such as fynbos, is generally viewed as detrimental to conservation (Brockerhoff *et al.*, 2008).

Conclusion

Studies assessing both species richness and community composition often show more negative impacts of plantations on community composition, even though the literature is biased towards assessing species richness, rather than community composition (Su *et al.*, 2004). Inferences on the impacts of plantations based on species richness assessments alone should be interpreted with caution, especially in assessments of arthropod diversity (Basset *et al.*, 2008). Nevertheless, this study adds to the growing body of evidence showing that exotic plantations have lower species richness and different community assemblages, compared to neighbouring native forest, in South Africa and globally. Pine plantations on the Cape Peninsula may also have negative impacts on the fynbos-specialist invertebrate community, whose available habitat has diminished through afforestation.

CHAPTER 4. FAUNAL EXCHANGE BETWEEN ALIEN PINE PLANTATIONS AND NATIVE FOREST AND FYNBOS ON THE CAPE PENINSULA

Introduction

A recent global review of plantations and biodiversity (Stephens & Wagner, 2007) showed that most studies examining the impact of plantations on biodiversity make inappropriate comparisons, because they do not compare plantations to the land use or vegetation that they are replacing. On the Cape Peninsula, exotic pine plantations were established in the 1880's for commercial timber production (Cowling *et al.*, 1996; Richardson & Higgins, 1998). These pine plantations were largely established in Granite Fynbos (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006), making the comparison of impacts and change in faunal community structure complicated.

There is currently no published inventory of the total number of invasive alien invertebrate species in South Africa, although it is unlikely to exceed 2500 introduced species, based on inventories from other regions: 1590 terrestrial alien invertebrates recorded in Europe (Roques *et al.*, 2009), over 2000 alien arthropod species from the continental USA, over 2500 species recorded in Hawaii (Pimentel, 2002), and 2200 from New Zealand (Barlow & Goldson, 2002). Knowledge of alien faunas also varies among invertebrate taxa. Molluscs, like arthropods, are a comparatively well-studied taxon. In South Africa, there are 34 introduced species of terrestrial mollusc, of which 28 have established and 20 have been collected in the greater Cape Town area (Herbert, 2010). Rahinjanahary (2007) recorded 16 species of alien saproxylic (wood-inhabiting) invertebrates in Newlands Forest on the Cape Peninsula, including earthworms, snails, slugs, woodlice, earwigs and ants. These alien invertebrates may further impact the native invertebrate diversity, either directly through predation and parasitism, or indirectly by disease transmission, disrupting mutualisms, and through interference competition (Kenis *et al.*, 2009).

Facilitative and mutualistic interactions among introduced species can lead to ecological impacts on native species that are more pronounced and accelerated than would be expected if the invasive species did not act in concert; and there are many examples illustrating this in the invasion literature (Simberloff, 2006). Woody invasive stands modify habitat, may support lower invertebrate species richness than adjacent vegetation types and exclude many endemic invertebrates, and may also facilitate the establishment and spread of invasive alien invertebrates (Lawrence, 1953). These alien invertebrate species could subsequently penetrate pristine ecosystems through corridors of invasive plants. For example, invasive ants throughout

the world readily spread from human-modified habitats into undisturbed natural areas, when abiotic conditions are suitable (reviewed in Krushelnycky *et al.*, 2010). In South Africa the forestry industry is recognized as a chief agent in the dispersal of terrestrial alien mollusc species into remote areas, where they have subsequently spread into pristine habitats (Herbert, 2010). In contrast to data for plants and vertebrates, few, if any, historical records document the spread of alien invertebrates into indigenous vegetation (Borges *et al.*, 2006). The Argentine ant is one local exception, possibly because its invasion into fynbos has caused the disruption and collapse of an ant-plant mutualism, viz. myrmecochory, the dispersal of seeds by ants (Bond & Slingsby, 1984; Witt *et al.*, 2004).

The Argentine ant, *Linepithema humile* Mayr (Formicidae: Dolichoderinae), is an opportunistic, highly invasive 'tramp' species that disperses to new areas by human-assisted transportation of colonies, and has established on six continents and many oceanic islands (Suarez *et al.*, 2001; Harris, 2002). It is native to the Paraná River basin in subtropical South America (Wild, 2004). The Argentine ant is thought to have reached South Africa around 1900 in fodder imported from Argentina during the Anglo Boer War, was first recorded in Stellenbosch in 1901 (Prins *et al.*, 1990), and was recognised as a pest in Cape Town by 1908 (Skaife, 1961; 1962; Richardson *et al.*, 1992). It is now a significant pest in agricultural and most urban areas, occurs in six of the nine provinces in South Africa, and occupies roughly half of the country's land surface area (Luruli, 2007). The first distribution records in undisturbed fynbos come from the 1970s and 1980s (Bond & Slingsby, 1984), and it is now well established in protected areas (Luruli, 2007). In the Western Cape Province, Argentine ants have established in Helderberg Nature Reserve (Boonzaaier, 2006), Jonkershoek Nature Reserve (Witt *et al.*, 2004), Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (Christian, 2001), and Table Mountain National Park (Skaife, 1961; Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002; Rahinjanahary, 2007; Pryke & Samways, 2010). Although Argentine ant sub-colonies are known to spread into Afrotemperate forest (Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002; Rahinjanahary, 2007) and mountain fynbos (Bond & Slingsby, 1984; Christian, 2001), it remains unclear whether they can establish more permanent colonies in undisturbed fynbos (Macdonald & Jarman, 1984; De Kock & Giliomee, 1989), as the majority of native habitats that it has invaded are in close proximity to plantations or other sites subject to anthropogenic change.

Argentine ants prefer shade and cool soil temperatures, and appear to be more reliant on permanent water sources than native ant species (Parker-Allie *et al.*, 2008). They thrive in moist riparian corridors, which allow penetration into otherwise unsuitable adjacent habitats (Holway, 2005). Rainfall also influences the distribution and spread of Argentine ants (Heller *et al.*, 2008). Temperature tolerance probably limits the distribution of Argentine ants, because

they are seldom able to forage when surface temperatures drop below 15°C or exceed 32°C, and if unable to return to a nest, they die quickly when exposed to high temperatures (Witt & Giliomee, 1999; Harris, 2002; Holway *et al.*, 2002). This may prevent Argentine ants establishing colonies in undisturbed fynbos, where exposure is generally high. However, Argentine ants may be able to overcome the limitations of high midday summer temperatures in fynbos, since they are known to forage for longer periods throughout the day than most native ants (Human & Gordon, 1997) and to forage at night (Witt & Giliomee, 1999). In areas with high native species richness, and where resource availability is not a limiting factor, biotic resistance (especially in the form of competition with native ants) may also influence invasion success (Elton, 1958; Walters & Mackay, 2005; Rowles & Silverman, 2009), at best, slowing the advance of Argentine ant supercolonies (Krushelnycky *et al.*, 2010).

The rate of expansion of Argentine ants into fynbos appears to be slow. Over a period of about 20 years, the front only expanded by roughly 160 m eastward in the Swartboskloof Valley in Jonkershoek Nature Reserve (Luruli, 2007). On the north-eastern Iberian Peninsula, the rate of spread in natural environments with low human disturbance is equally slow, at 7.94 ± 2.99 m yr⁻¹ (Roura-Pascual *et al.*, 2010). Under ideal climatic and habitat conditions, Argentine ants only spread at an average rate of 150 m per year (Suarez *et al.*, 2001). Bolger (2007) found that the invasion of Argentine ants acts as an urban edge effect. In large patches of coastal sage scrub in southern California, Argentine ant densities decreased 250 m from the edge, with no indication of increases in abundance or spatial extent in the core sage scrub habitat over time. This spatial limit to invasion is good news for native ant communities in large (over 1 km in diameter) contiguous patches, which might theoretically be protected in their native habitat from invasion by Argentine ants. The rate of spread is also highly variable, both seasonally and annually (Heller *et al.*, 2006; 2008). Colonies tend to aggregate in winter and disperse in summer, covering a larger area when it is hot and dry (Heller & Gordon, 2006), and when worker numbers increase (Heller *et al.*, 2006). These temporal patterns may influence the penetration of the invasion front into undisturbed fynbos and Afrotropical forest, producing a seasonally-fluctuating invasion front, rather than a one-way diffusion process.

In assessing faunal exchange between exotic pine plantations, native forest and fynbos, consideration must be given to both alien and native invertebrates, especially endemic species. The Cape Peninsula's distinctive terrestrial invertebrate diversity is of global significance (Cowling *et al.*, 1996) and zoogeographic importance (Jarvis, 1979). Picker & Samways (1996) identified 111 endemic invertebrate species on the Cape Peninsula, with strong patterns of endemism evident in certain invertebrate groups, such as harvestmen, velvet worms, and cave

Crustacea. The Cape Peninsula boasts the second highest (after Pietermaritzburg) millipede species richness and site endemism in South Africa (Hamer & Slotow, 2002), although this may be an artefact of collection bias, as previous researchers have been based at these locations. Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates are mostly palaeo-endemic, Gondwanan relictual taxa, with few surviving relatives (Picker & Samways, 1996). The majority of Table Mountain endemics are associated with palaeogenic zones: sandstone caves, forested slopes and streams (Picker & Samways, 1996). Sandstone caves on the Cape Peninsula alone support 21 endemic invertebrate species, far more than any other cave system in southern Africa (Sharratt *et al.*, 2000).

The aim of this study is to assess faunal exchange between pine plantations, native forest and fynbos on the Cape Peninsula, by comparing the abundance, species richness and species turnover of ground-dwelling invertebrates. Pine plantations are predicted to (a) provide a lower quality habitat for litter invertebrates than both forest and fynbos, with reduced species richness and number of Cape Peninsula endemics, but with a greater representation of alien species, and (b) support a mixed invertebrate community derived from both native vegetation types, but showing a closer similarity to the forest community than the original habitat, fynbos.

Methods

Study sites and collecting methods

Refer to Chapter 2 for the location of the sites sampled in Table Mountain National Park on the Cape Peninsula, and the collecting methods used in Western Cape Afrotropical Forest (n = 8 sites), Peninsula Granite and Sandstone Fynbos (n = 8 sites) and pine plantation (n = 7 sites; Site 11 omitted). For each of the 23 sites, data from the replicates (10 leaf litter, 10 soil, 10 pitfall trap, 10 sugar-baited ant trap, and two decayed log samples) were pooled to obtain a single abundance or species richness value per site. Refer to Appendix A for a list of species collected in forest, fynbos and pine plantation.

Abundance and species richness analyses

Abundance (number of individuals) and species richness (number of species) in each habitat were tallied for all invertebrate taxa combined, individual insect orders, and non-insect classes. Mean abundance per site was calculated for each habitat, and compared between sites using a Kruskal-Wallis (ANOVA by ranks) test in STATISTICA version 9 (StatSoft, Inc., 2009), since the data were not normally distributed. Relative abundance and relative species richness in each

habitat were each expressed as a percentage of the total number of individuals collected. The number of species, Cape Peninsula endemics, and alien species unique to each habitat, shared between two habitats, and common to all three habitats, were illustrated in Venn diagrams. Similarity between habitats was assessed using the Jaccard index of similarity based on shared species presence-absence data (Magurran, 2004). The Jaccard index was calculated as:

$$C_j = \frac{j}{a + b - j}$$

where j is the number of species present in both habitats, a is the number of species in habitat A and b is the number of species in habitat B. The total and mean (\pm SD) numbers of Cape Peninsula endemic and alien species were tallied, and the numbers of endemic and alien species per site plotted. Mean numbers of endemic and alien species per site were compared using Kruskal-Wallis tests. The percentage contribution of aliens to the total number of species and individuals collected in each habitat was calculated for each group of alien invertebrates.

Species turnover analyses

Beta diversity or turnover relates to species identities and how they change across a gradient (Whittaker, 1975), and is therefore a different measure to alpha diversity or local species richness (Gray, 2000). The beta diversity measure, β_{sim} was chosen as a measure of species turnover, because it is suited to situations where there are large differences in species richness counts between sites (Magurran, 2004). This is because β_{sim} is based on actual compositional differences (species gains and losses) between assemblages, and is not influenced by local species richness gradients (Lennon *et al.*, 2001; Koleff *et al.*, 2003). β_{sim} was used to compare species turnover within and between habitats, based on pooled species presence-absence data for all taxa combined. To calculate β_{sim} , a (the number of species common to both habitats), b (the number of species present in the neighbouring habitat, but not in the focal habitat, *i.e.* species gain) and c (the number of species present in the focal habitat, but not in the neighbouring habitat, *i.e.* species loss) were first calculated for each pair of sites. The original β_{sim} equation (Lennon *et al.*, 2001) was re-expressed by Koleff *et al.* (2003) in terms of these matching/mis-matching components (a , b and c) as:

$$\beta_{sim} = \frac{\min(b, c)}{\min(b, c) + a}$$

Using the smaller value of b or c in the denominator reduces the impact of large differences in species richness (Magurran, 2004). Mean species turnover was calculated for each habitat and between pairs of habitats, and differences tested for using Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA. Turnover

within and between habitats was regressed against distance between pairs of sites to determine whether there was a relationship between spatial gradients and turnover.

Results

Abundance

A total of 92 109 individual invertebrates was collected from the 23 sites sampled (Table 4.1). Total abundance was lower in pine plantation (19 614 individuals) than in forest (38 131) or fynbos (34 364). Mean abundance per site was also lower in pine plantation (2802.0 ± 1063.6 SD individuals) than in forest (4766.4 ± 3005.3) or fynbos (4295.5 ± 2432.1), although these differences were not significant (Kruskal-Wallis $H_{(2, N=23)} = 2.526$, $p = 0.273$), due to the high variance among sites within each habitat.

Relative abundance in each habitat varied among insect orders (Fig. 4.1a). Of the three insect orders most abundant in forest (Lepidoptera, Archaeognatha and Dermaptera), only Dermaptera was also abundant in pine plantation. The three most abundant insect orders in fynbos were Blattodea, Hymenoptera and Orthoptera. Hemiptera and Psocoptera were numerically dominant in pine plantation, and appear to be tolerant of this exotic monoculture. Coleoptera and Diptera had similar abundances in each habitat, suggesting that they include both forest and fynbos specialists, and many widespread generalist species. Mantodea, Neuroptera, Phasmatodea, Thysanoptera and Thysanura were discounted from comparisons, because each was represented by very few individuals and only one or two species. The abundance of all non-insect classes was highest in forest and lowest in fynbos (Fig. 4.1b), while Malacostraca had similar numbers in fynbos and pine plantation.

Table 4.1. Total abundance (number of individuals) and species richness (number of species) of invertebrate taxa collected in each habitat, with the number of species unique to each habitat in parentheses.

Common name	Taxon	Abundance			Species richness			
		Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Total	Forest	Fynbos	Pine
Ants	Formicidae	26 819	29 878	13 546	17	11	17 (4)	12
Bees	Hymenoptera	0	5	0	3	0	3 (3)	0
Beetles	Coleoptera	1401	1174	1221	135	98 (34)	75 (17)	69 (12)
Bristletails	Thysanura	167	22	7	1	1	1	1
Bugs	Hemiptera	454	123	843	75	46 (24)	44 (21)	19 (4)
Centipedes	Chilopoda	134	40	74	11	10	7	9 (1)
Cockroaches	Blattodea	122	397	24	12	7	11 (4)	6 (1)
Crickets	Orthoptera	154	532	290	15	9 (1)	11 (5)	8
Earthworms	Oligochaeta	1113	75	263	1	1	1	1
Earwigs	Dermaptera	135	5	64	5	5 (1)	2	3
Bristletails	Archaeognatha	0	4	0	1	0	1 (1)	0
Flatworms	Turbellaria	34	5	22	1	1	1	1
Flies	Diptera	714	630	658	70	43 (25)	28 (12)	26 (12)
Harvestmen	Opiliones	811	50	101	7	7 (2)	5	5
Lacewings	Neuroptera	0	0	1	1	0	0	1 (1)
Landhoppers	Amphipoda	1619	168	235	2	2	2	2
Millipedes	Diplopoda	852	169	649	10	8 (1)	8	8
Mites	Acari	359	249	374	17	14 (2)	10	15 (2)
Moths	Lepidoptera	151	14	8	1	1	1	1
Praying mantids	Mantodea	1	4	1	2	1	1 (1)	1
Pseudoscorpions	Pseudoscorpiones	28	14	8	5	4 (1)	2	3 (1)
Psocids/barklice	Psocoptera	47	18	55	11	5 (1)	7 (2)	7 (2)
Scorpions	Scorpiones	9	22	7	2	1	2	2
Slugs	Gastropoda	166	37	157	4	4 (1)	3	3
Snails	Gastropoda	527	54	91	16	14 (7)	5 (1)	8 (1)
Spiders	Araneae	215	280	138	106	68 (24)	67 (28)	41 (4)
Springtails	Collembola	1528	121	444	19	9	13 (4)	13 (4)
Stick insects	Phasmatodea	0	13	1	2	0	2 (1)	1
Sun-spiders	Solifugae	0	7	0	1	0	1 (1)	0
Thrips	Thysanoptera	2	0	0	1	1 (1)	0	0
Velvet worms	Udeonychophora	6	0	2	1	1	0	1
Wasps	Hymenoptera	380	85	269	108	77 (48)	30 (14)	42 (14)
Woodlice	Isopoda	183	169	61	7	6 (3)	4 (1)	2
	Total	38 131	34 364	19 614	670	455 (176)	365 (120)	311 (59)

Figure 4.1. Relative abundance in each habitat, expressed as a percentage of the total abundance in each taxon for (a) insect orders and (b) non-insect classes.

Species richness

A total of 670 invertebrate species was collected from the 23 sites sampled (Table 4.1). Total species richness was lower in pine plantation (311 species) than in forest (455) or fynbos (365). Species richness was also lowest in pine plantation for most insect orders (Fig. 4.2a). The relative species richness in each habitat varied among non-insect classes, but was never highest in pine plantation (Fig. 4.2b).

Figure 4.2. Relative species richness in each habitat, expressed as a percentage of the total species in each taxon for (a) insect orders and (b) non-insect classes. Taxa represented by only one or two species (Archaeognatha, Mantodea, Neuroptera, Phasmatodea, Thysanoptera, Thysanura, Turbellaria and Udeonychophora) and unidentified taxa (Lepidoptera and Clitellata) are omitted.

Over half (355) of the 670 species collected were found in one habitat only, while 146 (21.8%) were common to all three habitats sampled (Fig. 4.3). Forest and fynbos shared 63 species (9.4% of the 670 collected) and had a low Jaccard index of similarity ($C_j = 0.27$). Limited invertebrate faunal exchange was evident between these native habitats. Pine plantation supported considerably fewer unique species (59) than either forest (176) or fynbos (120). The number of species shared between forest and pine plantation (70) was almost double the number shared between fynbos and pine plantation (36). The Jaccard index of similarity was also noticeably higher between forest and pine plantation ($C_j = 0.42$) than between fynbos and pine plantation ($C_j = 0.25$), confirming that pine plantations on the Cape Peninsula have exchanged more invertebrate species with forest than with fynbos. In forest, 103 of the 176 unique species were represented by only one individual (singletons) and 24 by two individuals (doubletons). In fynbos, 55 of the 120 unique species were singletons and 24 were doubletons. In pine plantation, 43 of the 59 unique species were singletons and four were doubletons. Of these unique species, 124 species in forest, 76 in fynbos, and 51 in pine plantation were collected from one site only. Snails, spiders, bugs, beetles, flies and wasps contributed the highest number of unique species in all habitats (Table 4.1).

Figure 4.3. Venn diagram illustrating the number of unique species in each habitat and the number shared between habitats. The number of species is also expressed as a percentage of the total 670 species (values in parentheses). The Jaccard index of similarity (C_j) is shown between each pair of habitats.

Cape Peninsula endemics

Nine species were identified by taxonomists and/or were amongst those listed in Picker & Samways (1996) as being endemic to the Cape Peninsula (Table 4.2). Of these, seven were collected in forest, six in fynbos, and only one (*Uroplectes insignis*) in pine plantation, although it also occurred in both native habitats. Three Cape Peninsula endemic species were unique to forest (*Trachycystis perplicata*, *Spermophora peninsulae* and *Bohepilissus nitidus*), and two to fynbos (*Dipteretrum brinckae* and *Hoplophoropyga unicolor*). None of the endemic species was collected at all sites within a habitat, and most were rare and only collected from a few sites. Only two of the seven pine plantation sites, both in Newlands Forest, supported the endemic scorpion *U. insignis* (Fig. 4.4). Forest generally had the greatest number of endemic species per site (Fig. 4.4). The mean number of endemics in forest (3.5 ± 1.3 SD species), fynbos (2.1 ± 0.8) and pine plantation (0.3 ± 0.5) was significantly different between habitats (Kruskal-Wallis $H_{(2, N=23)} = 15.657$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 4.2. Distribution of Cape Peninsula endemic species by habitat. Total abundance (in bold), mean abundance per site (\pm SD) and number of sites (both in parentheses) are given for each species in each habitat.

Order	Endemic species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine
Eupulmonata	<i>Trachycystis perplicata</i> (Benson, 1851)	6 (0.8 ± 1.4 , n = 3)	0	0
Araneae	<i>Spermophora gordimeriae</i> Huber, 2003	6 (0.8 ± 1.8 , n = 2)	3 (0.4 ± 0.7 , n = 2)	0
Araneae	<i>Spermophora peninsulae</i> Lawrence, 1964	1 (0.1 ± 0.4 , n = 1)	0	0
Araneae	<i>Malaika longipes</i> (Purcell, 1904)	14 (1.8 ± 1.6 , n = 6)	2 (0.3 ± 0.7 , n = 1)	0
Araneae	<i>Moggridgea teresae</i> Griswold, 1987	8 (1.0 ± 1.1 , n = 5)	1 (0.1 ± 0.4 , n = 1)	0
Scorpiones	<i>Uroplectes insignis</i> Pocock, 1890	9 (1.1 ± 1.5 , n = 4)	13 (1.6 ± 2.4 , n = 3)	6 (0.9 ± 1.6 , n = 2)
Blattodea	<i>Dipteretrum brinckae</i> Princis, 1963	0	53 (6.6 ± 12.9 , n = 5)	0
Blattodea	<i>Hoplophoropyga unicolor</i> (Karny, 1908)	0	32 (4.0 ± 5.3 , n = 5)	0
Coleoptera	<i>Bohepilissus nitidus</i> Balthasar, 1965	115 (14.4 ± 26.3 , n = 7)	0	0

Three Cape Peninsula endemic species were unique to forest and two to fynbos, with a very low Jaccard index of similarity ($C_j = 1.5$) (Fig. 4.5). Only one endemic species was shared across all three habitats, and no endemics were shared between forest and pine plantation, or fynbos and pine plantation, reflected in the Jaccard index of similarity ($C_j = 0$) (Fig. 4.5). Cape Peninsula endemic species made a very low percentage contribution (1.35% cumulatively) to the total 670 species collected.

Figure 4.4. Number of Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrate species collected at each site, with mean (\pm SD) number per habitat in parentheses.

Figure 4.5. Venn diagram illustrating the number of Cape Peninsula endemic species unique to each habitat and shared between habitats. The number of Cape Peninsula endemics is also expressed as a percentage of the total 670 species (values in parentheses). The Jaccard index of similarity (C_j) is shown between each pair of habitats.

Alien invertebrate species

Nineteen alien species were identified, of which 16 were collected in forest, 11 in fynbos, and 15 in pine plantation (Table 4.3). Every site harboured at least two alien species (Fig. 4.6). The highest number of alien species at any one site was 12 (Site 1, forest – in Newlands Forest) (Fig. 4.6). The mean number of alien species in forest (7.5 ± 2.1 SD species), fynbos (4.8 ± 1.8), and pine plantation (6.1 ± 1.8) was not significantly different between habitats (Kruskal-Wallis $H_{(2, N=23)} = 6.215$, $p = 0.447$). Alien species contributed a very low percentage of the mean number of species collected per site in forest (4.86 ± 1.19 SD %), fynbos ($4.78 \pm 1.78\%$), and pine plantation ($5.80 \pm 1.80\%$).

Three alien molluscs were found only in forest (*Limax maximus*, *Cochlicopa* sp. and *Cornu aspersum*); with the first two restricted to one site each (Table 4.3). One alien springtail (*Tomocerus minor*) was restricted to a single site in fynbos. An alien snail (*Lauria cylindracea*) and another alien springtail (*Entomobrya nivalis*) were each restricted to a single site in pine plantation. The alien Portuguese millipede (*Ommatoiulus moreleti*) was abundant in all 23 sites, as was an alien slug (*Arion hortensis*); although the latter was less abundant in fynbos, it was present at 21 sites. *O. moreleti* was far more abundant in all habitats than any of the native millipede species. The European wasp (*Vespula germanica*) was present in all habitats, although far less abundant in pine plantation than in forest or fynbos. The Argentine ant (*Linepithema humile*) was present at 16 of the 23 sites and in all three habitats. Mean abundance per site of Argentine ants was higher in forest (1978.6 ± 2571.1 SD individuals) than in both fynbos (568.3 ± 1277.6) and pine plantation (834.4 ± 1507.3). Total abundance of Argentine ants was also higher in forest (15 829 individuals) than in fynbos (4546) or pine plantation (5841), although these differences were not significant (Kruskal-Wallis $H_{(2, N=23)} = 0.178$, $p = 0.915$). The number of individual Argentine ants collected at each site varied greatly within habitats, with over 1000 individuals (indicating a nest nearby) recorded in each of four forest, one fynbos, and two pine plantation sites.

Table 4.3. Total abundance (in bold), mean \pm SD abundance per site and number of sites (in parentheses) for alien invertebrate species collected in each habitat.

Order: Family	Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine
Eupulmonata: Arionidae	<i>Arion hortensis</i> aggregate Férussac, 1819	106 (13.3 \pm 8.1, n = 8)	29 (3.6 \pm 3.7, n = 7)	131 (18.7 \pm 23.4, n = 6)
Eupulmonata: Limacidae	<i>Deroceras panormitanum</i> (Lesson & Pollonera, 1882)	30 (3.8 \pm 5.5, n = 8)	4 (0.5 \pm 1.1, n = 2)	3 (0.4 \pm 1.1, n = 1)
Eupulmonata: Limacidae	<i>Lehmannia valentiana</i> (Férussac, 1821)	28 (3.5 \pm 3.0, n = 6)	4 (0.5 \pm 1.4, n = 1)	23 (3.3 \pm 5.8, n = 2)
Eupulmonata: Limacidae	<i>Limax maximus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	2 (0.3 \pm 0.7, n = 1)	0	0
Eupulmonata: Cochlicopidae	<i>Cochlicopa</i> sp. Férussac, 1821	16 (2.0 \pm 5.7, n = 1)	0	0
Eupulmonata: Cochlicopidae	<i>Cochlicopa</i> cf. <i>lubricella</i> Férussac, 1821	56 (7.0 \pm 19.8, n = 1)	0	3 (0.4 \pm 0.8, n = 2)
Eupulmonata: Pristilomatidae	<i>Vitrea contracta</i> (Westerlund, 1871)	13 (1.6 \pm 3.1, n = 2)	0	19 (2.7 \pm 5.5, n = 3)
Eupulmonata: Helicidae	<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (Müller, 1774)	6 (0.8 \pm 1.4, n = 3)	0	0
Eupulmonata: Punctidae	cf. <i>Punctum</i> sp.	35 (4.4 \pm 12.4, n = 1)	0	38 (5.4 \pm 5.5, n = 6)
Eupulmonata: Pupillidae	<i>Lauria cylindracea</i> (da Costa, 1778)	0	0	1 (0.1 \pm 0.4, n = 1)
Eupulmonata: Oxychilidae	<i>Oxychilus draparnaudi</i> (Beck, 1837)	60 (7.5 \pm 18.9, n = 3)	2 (0.3 \pm 0.7, n = 1)	13 (1.9 \pm 4.9, n = 1)
Eupulmonata: Oxychilidae	<i>Oxychilus</i> sp. Fitzinger, 1833	9 (1.1 \pm 2.4, n = 3)	10 (1.3 \pm 3.2, n = 2)	10 (1.4 \pm 3.4, n = 2)
Julida: Cambalidae	<i>Ommatoiulus moreleti</i> (Lucas, 1860)	508 (63.5 \pm 35.4, n = 8)	152 (19.0 \pm 25.6, n = 8)	546 (78.0 \pm 41.7, n = 7)
Isopoda: Porcellionidae	<i>Porcellio scaber</i> Latreille, 1804	49 (6.1 \pm 10.9, n = 6)	99 (12.4 \pm 27.2, n = 6)	8 (1.1 \pm 1.9, n = 3)
Collembola: Entomobryidae	<i>Entomobrya nivalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	0	0	16 (2.3 \pm 6.0, n = 1)
Collembola: Neanuridae	<i>Neanura muscorum</i> (Templeton, 1835)	1 (0.1 \pm 0.4, n = 1)	4 (0.5 \pm 1.4, n = 1)	2 (0.3 \pm 0.5, n = 2)
Collembola: Tomoceridae	<i>Tomocerus minor</i> (Lubbock, 1862)	0	1 (0.1 \pm 0.4, n = 1)	0
Hymenoptera: Vespidae	<i>Vespula germanica</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	15 (1.9 \pm 3.6, n = 3)	14 (1.8 \pm 3.3, n = 2)	3 (0.4 \pm 0.8, n = 2)
Hymenoptera: Formicidae	<i>Linepithema humile</i> Mayr, 1868	15 829 (1978.6 \pm 2571.1, n = 5)	4546 (568.3 \pm 1277.6, n = 7)	5841 (834.4 \pm 1507.3, n = 4)

Figure 4.6. Number of alien invertebrate species recorded at each site, with mean number (\pm SD) per habitat in parentheses.

The percentage contribution of alien species to the total number of species (Fig. 4.7a) and total number of individuals (Fig. 4.7b) collected in each habitat varied between taxa. The percentage contribution of alien species to the total number of species collected in each taxon in pine plantation was equal to, or higher than, in forest and fynbos (Fig. 4.7a). Snails and woodlice showed a higher percentage contribution of alien species in pine plantation than in native habitats. Alien species contributed only a small percentage of the species collected across habitats for most taxa, with the exception of molluscs, where all slug and half of the snail species collected were alien. Trends differed between species richness and abundance. Several alien species were numerically dominant, and made a disproportionately high contribution to the total number of individuals collected for slugs, snails and millipedes, especially in pine plantation (Fig. 4.7b).

Figure 4.7. Percentage contribution of alien taxa to the total (a) number of species and (b) number of individuals per taxon in each habitat.

Forest had the highest number of unique alien species (*i.e.* those species not collected in other habitats) (Fig. 4.8). Over half of the alien species collected were present in all three habitats, with a further three shared between forest and pine plantation (Fig. 4.8). No alien invertebrate species was shared only between forest and fynbos, or only between fynbos and pine plantation, reflected in their Jaccard index of similarity ($C_j = 0$). Cumulatively, alien species contributed only 2.84% to the total 670 invertebrate species collected.

Figure 4.8. Venn diagram illustrating the number of alien species unique to each habitat and shared between habitats. The number of alien species is also expressed as a percentage of the total 670 species (values in parentheses). The Jaccard index of similarity (C_j) is shown between each pair of habitats.

Species turnover

Species turnover or beta diversity, calculated as β_{sim} , was high and differed significantly both within habitats (Kruskal-Wallis $H_{(2, N=77)} = 23.825$, $p < 0.001$) and between habitats (Kruskal-Wallis $H_{(2, N=176)} = 69.462$, $p < 0.001$). Mean species turnover within habitats was slightly lower in pine plantation (0.473 ± 0.058 SD, $n = 21$) than in forest (0.522 ± 0.115 , $n = 28$) and fynbos (0.611 ± 0.078 , $n = 28$). Mean species turnover between habitats was also slightly lower between forest and pine (0.527 ± 0.068 SD, $n = 56$) than between forest and fynbos (0.646 ± 0.072 , $n = 64$), and fynbos and pine (0.652 ± 0.077 , $n = 56$). The high mean turnover between habitats reflects the contrasting invertebrate assemblages present in each habitat. Turnover did not increase with distance between sites within each habitat (all $R^2 \leq 0.130$, Fig. 4.9a), or between habitats (all $R^2 < 0.024$, Fig. 4.9b), ruling out spatial gradients as an explanation for the high species turnover observed. The furthest distance between any two sites was less than 12 km, which may be too close to show any meaningful trend in species turnover with distance. Factors such as site-specific environmental conditions, disturbance history, and vegetation composition may have stronger influences on species turnover at this localized spatial scale.

Figure 4.9. Species turnover with distance between sites (a) within and (b) between habitats.

Discussion

Abundance and species richness

Pine plantations on the Cape Peninsula supported an impoverished invertebrate fauna, with approximately 50% reduction in both numbers of individuals and species, compared to native forest and fynbos. Pine plantation had more species in common with forest than with fynbos, as was expected, since the litter and dead wood microhabitats, soil moisture levels, and shading

effects in pine plantation more closely resemble those in forest than in fynbos habitats. Pine plantations may therefore approximate a forest habitat for ground-dwelling invertebrates. However, while apparently mimicking forest, pine plantations in fact supported virtually no Cape Peninsula endemic species, with habitat generalists and ecologically-tolerant species possibly dominating the community. Plantations often support fewer forest specialist species (e.g. carabid beetles) than forest generalist species, which occur across various habitats (Magura *et al.*, 2000). Therefore, pine plantations are actually a low quality habitat for leaf litter invertebrate fauna in terms of assemblage composition.

The high number of unique species found in forest and fynbos (when compared to pine plantation), may reflect the presence of many true habitat specialists. Conversely, pine plantation relies on donor habitats (including urban and agricultural habitats) as a source of immigrants. However, most of these unique species in native habitats were represented by singletons or doubletons, and probably include tourists, incidental catches, or genuinely rare species. It may also reflect the lack of sampling saturation, despite the fairly extensive sampling effort. Nevertheless, the sampling methods employed targeted the litter fauna, which generally has low vagility and would be less impacted by visitors (typically flying insects).

The low species richness observed in fynbos, compared to forest, may reflect the low cover, shallow depth of litter, and low soil and litter moisture levels in summer in this habitat. Leaf litter depth and composition are known to affect abundance and assemblage composition of snails and other invertebrates (Martin & Sommer, 2004 and references therein), are often positively correlated with beetle diversity, and may be more important than soil moisture in explaining species richness patterns (Hopp *et al.*, 2010). The low rate of litter accumulation in fynbos has previously been used to explain the low number of soil and surface-dwelling invertebrates (Giliomee, 2003). Fynbos leaf litter production is affected by vegetation age (time since last fire) and the proportions of restioid, proteoid and ericoid species (Mitchell *et al.*, 1986). Fynbos litter also decomposes at a very slow rate (Mitchell *et al.*, 1986). Leaf litter is a highly specific microhabitat (Hopp *et al.*, 2010) and the fynbos leaf litter community has received insufficient attention in the literature, and remains poorly understood. The results here suggest that fynbos is not as good a habitat as forest for litter-dwelling invertebrates, which is unsurprising, as forest litter is undoubtedly a superior habitat for this fauna. Fynbos litter may also represent a more transient habitat, given that fire frequency in fynbos would have occurred at 5-50 year intervals (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006), consuming much of the litter. In contrast, forest is protected from fire (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006), and thus offers a stable litter habitat in ecological and evolutionary time.

Cape Peninsula endemics

The nine Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates recorded here are likely an underestimate of true invertebrate endemism at the study sites, since most taxa were only identified to morphospecies. Even within taxa identified by taxonomists, many morphospecies could not be assigned names, for a number of reasons. For example, the cockroach fauna of South Africa is incompletely known, only part of the fauna has been described, and these descriptions are often insufficient for a clear species determination (H. Bohn pers. comm., 2010). One new cockroach genus and a new species of *Ectobius* (Blattellidae) were collected in this study, and may well represent Cape Peninsula endemics. A similar taxonomic limitation and incompletely surveyed fauna applies to springtails (E. Bernard pers. comm., 2010). Less than half of the springtail species collected in this study could be assigned names by a collembolan taxonomist, and further study is required to determine how many of these are undescribed Cape Peninsula endemics. Most published papers on collembolan taxonomy in the region come from sporadic and scant collecting, and often represent by-catch from studies on other focal taxa (E. Bernard pers. comm., 2010).

The number of endemic species recorded is also likely to be underestimated, because endemic invertebrates may be rare and/or localized. The 111 invertebrate species recorded in the literature as being endemic to the Cape Peninsula (Picker & Samways, 1996) is also certainly an underestimate, because little or no information exists for several invertebrate taxa. The true number of Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates may also be underestimated, because taxa previously considered to have a widespread distribution may in reality comprise species complexes. Recent molecular analyses on what were previously considered to be widespread species have revealed extensive cryptic species. For example, the velvet worm *Peripatopsis balfouri* has six evolutionary distinct lineages (Daniels *et al.*, 2009), one of which was present in three forest sites and one pine plantation site in this study. Cryptic species are likely to occur in other taxa with limited dispersal capability and desiccation sensitivity (such as molluscs and earthworms), that are forest specialists and that occur ecotypically with Onychophora (Daniels *et al.*, 2009).

Of the 111 Cape Peninsula endemic species reported by Picker & Samways (1996), only a fraction would be found in the habitats sampled, since many are aquatic, cave-dwelling, or not ground-dwelling. Some of the species recorded in the literature (Picker & Samways, 1996) may be extinct, since many of these records date back many decades. For example, the velvet worm, *Peripatopsis leonina*, has not been collected from its former habitat on Signal Hill since it

was described in 1900, despite numerous search attempts, and is now considered extinct (Hamer *et al.*, 1997; Daniels *et al.*, 2009). Other species sharing this litter habitat might have suffered the same fate.

Two Cape Peninsula endemic cockroach species were found to be widespread and abundant in fynbos, but were not recorded in pine plantation. Afforestation may have had a negative impact on these cockroaches by reducing suitable available habitat. Neither cockroach was collected at Site 3, a small patch of recovering Sandstone Fynbos that was previously under pine. The scorpion *Uroplectes insignis* was the only Cape Peninsula endemic species collected in all three habitats. Although widespread in forest and fynbos, it was only collected in pine plantations in Newlands Forest. This implies that plantations may not offer suitable surrogate habitat for most Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates, in spite of forest and pine plantation sharing a fairly high number of species. Until recently, *U. insignis* was known only from forest on Table Mountain (Prendini, 2005). Rahinjanahary (2007) collected *U. insignis* in both Afrotropical forest and pine plantation in Newlands Forest, at the same sites sampled in this study. Pryke & Samways (2010) also report *U. insignis* as widespread in fynbos and forest across Table Mountain. This species may be expanding its range, possibly in the absence of frequent fires on the mountain, but more plausibly has been inadequately surveyed in the past.

Alien invertebrate species

The 19 alien species identified is also likely an underestimate, since most taxa in this study were identified only to morphospecies, and several species are not yet described, so their origin and distribution are unknown. No previous study has focused on alien invertebrates on the Cape Peninsula, although the Argentine ant (*Linepithema humile*) has received some attention (Picker & Samways, 1996; Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002; Rahinjanahary, 2007; Pryke & Samways, 2010), and 15 other alien invertebrate species were collected in Newlands Forest by Rahinjanahary (2007). Table Mountain is among the most thoroughly sampled areas for invertebrates in southern Africa (Picker & Samways, 1996; Hamer & Slotow, 2002), yet knowledge of its invertebrate fauna remains poor. For example, the world's only known jumping cockroach was recently discovered on Table Mountain (Bohn *et al.*, 2010). The value of, and necessity for, a detailed inventory of alien invertebrates in a national park of World Heritage status and global biodiversity significance seems obvious, and requires urgent attention.

European wasps (*Vespula germanica*), a well known invasive, have received some attention in the Western Cape Province (Tribe & Richardson, 1994), but their distribution and status on the Cape Peninsula require reassessment. Pryke & Samways (2009b) collected only

two individuals of European wasps in an 18 month sampling period (July 2005 – January 2007); both in natural vegetation, suggesting that this species may not inhabit pine plantations and that populations may have declined on the Cape Peninsula. However, 32 individuals of European wasps were collected during the five month sampling period (September 2008 – February 2009) in this study. Although numbers collected were lower in pine plantation, European wasps were present in forest (three sites), fynbos (two sites) and pine plantation (two sites), and in five of the eight areas sampled. European wasps also occur in the Stellenbosch area and in Jonkershoek Nature Reserve (C. Uys pers. obs., March 2010), some 50 km inland, suggesting that they are widespread and well established in a range of vegetation types in the Western Cape Province. A small nest was observed in a decaying pine log in pine plantation (Site 22) in Orange Kloof (C. Uys pers. obs., January 2009), suggesting that they can survive in pine plantation. Most individuals in this study were caught in sugar-baited ant traps, and their presence and abundance are most likely underestimated, because they are not ground-dwelling species, although they hunt for invertebrate prey on the litter surface, and are attracted to a carbohydrate source (Harris & Oliver, 1993; Sackmann *et al.*, 2000; Kasper *et al.*, 2004).

Argentine ants invade new areas by dispersing along roads and water-courses (Human *et al.*, 1998). In fynbos, their spread and successful establishment are closely linked with the road accessibility of an area, such that most of the old records of Argentine ants in fynbos come from residential areas, picnic sites, and refuse dumps (De Kock & Giliomee, 1989). Table Mountain National Park has many mountain streams and a network of roads and well-used paths, especially in the pine plantations, all potentially facilitating the spread of this invasive alien species into native vegetation. It appears as if Argentine ants can establish and maintain colonies in relatively undisturbed fynbos, since in this study at least one confirmed nest was found in fynbos, and the species was present in seven of the eight fynbos sites sampled. Pryke & Samways (2010) also recorded Argentine ants in fynbos at similar elevations (240-400 m a.s.l.) on the western, southern, and eastern slopes of Table Mountain. Rahinjanahary (2007) reports Argentine ants only below 350 m in Newlands Forest. Both of these studies are within the altitudinal range at which Argentine ants were collected in this study, *i.e.* 130-520 m a.s.l. (although they were most abundant below 400 m a.s.l.). It is of concern that the abundance and number of nests was much higher in forest than in pine plantation, where Argentine ants were expected to be most abundant. Argentine ants have probably been well established in Afrotemperate forest on the Cape Peninsula for many years, and have been recognized as a threat to native invertebrate diversity in previous studies (Picker & Samways, 1996; Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002; Rahinjanahary, 2007; Pryke & Samways, 2010).

Species turnover

Species turnover was high both within and between habitats and was, as predicted, somewhat lower between sites in pine plantation than among sites in either forest or fynbos. Individual species generally showed patchy distributions (Hammond, 1994), and high turnover, which for ground-dwelling invertebrates is to be expected (Ferrier *et al.*, 1999; Uys *et al.*, 2009). Based on a survey of arthropods in Gabon, Basset *et al.* (2008) recommended reporting both species richness and turnover, and cautioned against focussing on species richness alone to avoid drawing misleading conclusions about arthropod assemblages in conservation studies. In general, beta diversity should be higher for taxa that are poor dispersers. Arthropods exhibit greater spatial turnover than vertebrates (Ferrier *et al.*, 1999), and within the global distribution of vertebrates, beta diversity of birds and mammals is less than that of amphibians and reptiles (McKnight *et al.*, 2007; Qian, 2009).

Species turnover both within and between habitats did not increase with distance between sites. Distance alone also did not explain species turnover (measured as β_{sim}) for ground-dwelling flightless invertebrates in Afrotropical forest patches in the Drakensberg Mountains, South Africa (Uys *et al.*, 2009). While there is little evidence for distance-dependent community composition of ecosystems over relatively small spatial scales, both environmental variation and geographical distance between sites at larger spatial scales determine patterns of species turnover for ground-dwelling ants, beetles and spiders in north-east New South Wales, Australia (Ferrier *et al.*, 1999), and for macroinvertebrate pond communities in Oxfordshire, UK (Briers & Biggs, 2005). Hughes *et al.* (2000) offer two extremes as explanations for changes in species composition across a landscape: either gradual changes along spatially autocorrelated gradients of environmental variables, or sudden changes between discrete habitat types. More often, turnover is likely to reflect a combination of these two extremes. Afrotropical forest on the Cape Peninsula is naturally fragmented, being restricted to fire-protected rocky ravines (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). Given the low vagility of the largely wingless, moisture-dependent litter fauna, species turnover would be predicted to be high, possibly higher than in more open and contiguous fynbos habitat. This was not supported by the turnover values for forest sites, which were on average slightly lower than those for fynbos sites, but this may reflect the disturbance history and vegetation compositional differences in fynbos. Many of the Cape Peninsula endemic taxa, a fair number of which are litter fauna, are widely distributed across the Peninsula (Picker & Samways, 1996).

Conclusion

Compared to forest and fynbos, pine plantations supported much lower invertebrate abundance, fewer unique species, only one Cape Peninsula endemic species, about the same number of alien invertebrate species, and lower species turnover (beta diversity). The current pine plantation litter community has more in common with Afrotropical forest, and less with the original Granite Fynbos community, which was displaced by the pine plantation. Although not conclusive, pine plantations do appear to have facilitated the spread of a number of alien invertebrates into the surrounding native vegetation on the Cape Peninsula. Pine plantations are a low quality habitat for leaf litter invertebrate fauna, lack their own identity, and consequently have low conservation value in the landscape, even though they support many forest, and some fynbos, invertebrate species.

CHAPTER 5. IMPACTS OF ARGENTINE ANTS ON NATIVE ANTS AND OTHER GROUND-DWELLING INVERTEBRATES ON THE CAPE PENINSULA

Introduction

The ecological impacts of invasive alien species affect all levels of organization (genetic, population, community and ecosystem levels), and differ among herbivores, predators, parasites, parasitoids and pollinators (Kenis *et al.*, 2009). Through collective direct and indirect effects, invasive alien species can displace native species, disassemble the remaining communities (Sanders *et al.*, 2003), and disrupt various ecosystem processes (O'Dowd *et al.*, 2003). In a review of case studies of biological invasion from 1980 to 2006, spanning 892 species from around the world, 36.3% of studies focussed on the biology and ecology of invertebrates, with the Argentine ant (*Linepithema humile*) receiving the most research attention among terrestrial invertebrates (Pyšek *et al.*, 2008). Another review of 403 primary research papers dealing with the impacts of invasive insects (1900-2007 inclusive) revealed that 41% concerned invasive ants, with two species (Red imported fire ant, *Solenopsis invicta*, and Argentine ant, *L. humile*) dominating the literature (Kenis *et al.*, 2009). These two species, together with the Yellow crazy ant (*Anoplolepis gracilipes*), Big-headed ant (*Pheidole megacephala*), and Little fire ant (*Wasmannia auropunctata*) are listed among the *100 of the world's worst invasive species* (Lowe *et al.*, 2000). More recently, other invasive ant species have received more attention (reviewed in Lach & Hooper-Bùi, 2010). Invasive ants are a globally-pervasive ecological problem because of their expanding geographic ranges, high propagule pressure, high local abundances and ability to disrupt ecosystem processes (Holway *et al.*, 2002).

The most widely documented impact of ant invasions is the displacement of native ants, although only a handful of studies use experimental approaches to document such displacements (Holway *et al.*, 2002). Most reports of decreases in native ant species richness with invasion come from studies of Red imported fire ants and Argentine ants (Holway *et al.*, 2002). Argentine ants have reduced native ant diversity in California (e.g. Holway, 1998), Hawaii (Cole *et al.*, 1992), Australia (Rowles & O'Dowd, 2007), Japan (Touyama *et al.*, 2003) and other invaded locations. Argentine ants have also been reported to reduce ant species richness in South African fynbos and to replace dominant native ants, in particular, ground-foraging, seed-dispersing ant guilds (Bond & Slingsby, 1984; Parker-Allie *et al.*, 2008). The presence of Argentine ants in fynbos is therefore of urgent conservation concern, because up to 30% of the

fynbos flora (including 50% of the Proteaceae) depends on seed dispersal by ants (Bond & Slingsby, 1984). Argentine ants include seed in their diet, but do not bury them, unlike many of the native ants (Christian, 2001). This is problematic, because the two abundant native ant species (*Anoplolepis custodiens* and *Pheidole capensis*), that are the most effective dispersers of large-seeded proteas, are displaced or eliminated by Argentine ants (De Kock & Giliomee, 1989; Christian, 2001; Witt *et al.*, 2004). This results in substantially lower post-fire recruitment of large-seeded fynbos species. Ant species such as *Meranoplus peringueyi* and *Tetramorium quadrispinosum*, that are able to coexist with Argentine ants (Luruli, 2007), are not big enough to carry large, heavy seeds (Christian, 2001). This leads to altered plant species composition in invaded fynbos communities, due to the localised decline of large-seeded myrmecochorous plant species. Similar reduced seed dispersal has been reported in California in areas invaded by Argentine ants, compared to control areas dominated by native harvester ants (*Pogonomyrmex subnitidus*) that also disperse seeds (Carney *et al.*, 2003).

Exploitative and interference competition are two of the most important mechanisms contributing to the competitive nature of Argentine ants, and explain this displacement of native ant species (Human & Gordon, 1997). Argentine ants show rapid recruitment, high abundance, high territoriality, and intense interspecific aggression (Rowles & O'Dowd, 2007). Native ant species with similar niche preferences to Argentine ants are most vulnerable to displacement. Epigaeic (above-ground foraging) species are consequently more affected than hypogaeic (below-ground foraging) species (Harris, 2002). Argentine ants, when numerically dominant, also surpass native ant species in exploiting resources, because they show generalist feeding behaviour and are omnivorous, consuming a variety of food resources. Argentine ants display flexible patterns of resource use and a shift in diet after establishment, as a result of resource depletion (Tillberg *et al.*, 2007). Although they are amongst the most carnivorous of ants (Tillberg *et al.*, 2007), they also feed extensively on liquids (Zee & Holway, 2006), showing a preference for hemipteran honeydew (Silverman & Brightwell, 2008). The monopolisation of carbohydrate-rich resources, such as plant and hemipteran exudates, has been reported for all of the most important invasive ant species (Lach, 2003), and is thought to contribute to their invasion success (Holway *et al.*, 2002; O'Dowd *et al.*, 2003; Rowles & Silverman, 2009; Lach *et al.*, 2010). Argentine ants generally choose nest sites in close proximity to a food source, but are able to forage up to 60 m away from their nest (Silverman & Brightwell, 2008).

Argentine ants are unicolonial, forming supercolonies with thousands of workers and multiple queens, distributed among interconnected nests (Tsutsui & Suarez, 2003; Holway & Suarez, 2004; Walters & Mackay, 2005; Heller *et al.*, 2006). In contrast, native ant species

typically live in small colonies with a single nest, with only one queen per nest, and colonies react antagonistically to non-colony members (Hölldobler & Wilson, 1990). Local-scale colony spread of Argentine ants occurs via budding, rather than queens using long-distance dispersal through nuptial flights (Silverman & Brightwell, 2008). This ensures that dispersing queens are accompanied by high numbers of workers, which dominate and suppress native ant species along the colony's expanding border. Accordingly, interference competition, resource exploitation, and highly polygynous (multiple queens per nest) and polydomous (multiple nests per colony) life history traits all contribute to the invasion success of Argentine ants.

Behavioural and life history traits are the basis on which functional groups have been assigned for ant genera. Functional groups are based on niche dimensions, such as diet, nest location and time of foraging, and are indicative of broad-scale, worldwide responses of the component taxa to disturbance and environmental stress (Andersen, 1997a). Argentine ants have been assigned to the Dominant Dolichoderinae functional group, members of which are characteristically abundant, highly active and aggressive ants, with a strong competitive influence on other ant species (Andersen, 1997a). Not all dolichoderines show behavioural dominance, and the Dominant Dolichoderinae functional group is not represented in the native southern African ant fauna, where behavioural dominance has instead evolved in the formicines (*Anoplolepis custodiens* group) (Majer *et al.*, 2004). Dominant Dolichoderinae are similarly absent in cool-temperate regions elsewhere (except for parts of Australia), and formicines (*e.g. Formica*) also dominate throughout the Holarctic. Subordinate Camponotini (*e.g. Camponotus*) co-occur with Dominant Dolichoderinae, because they are behaviourally submissive, have a large body size, and often forage nocturnally (Andersen, 1997a). Opportunists (*e.g. Tetramorium*) can also coexist with Argentine ants, because they generally occur in disturbed habitats that support low ant diversity (Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003). Conversely, Tropical Climate Specialists (*e.g. Tetraponera*) and Hot or Cold Climate Specialists (*e.g. Meranoplus* and certain *Monomorium* species) favour habitats where Dominant Dolichoderinae are not abundant (Andersen, 1997a). Generalized Myrmicinae show a range of responses to Argentine ants and other Dominant Dolichoderinae, from co-occurrence through little or no direct interaction (*e.g. Crematogaster*: Addison & Samways, 2000; Brown, 2000), co-occurrence through the use of chemical secretions that repel Argentine ants (*e.g. Monomorium*: Holway, 1999; Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003), to displacement by Argentine ants due to similar resource requirements (*e.g. Pheidole*: Bond & Slingsby, 1984; Witt & Giliomee, 1999).

The loss of native ants following invasion by Argentine ants leads to the homogenisation of local faunas, and resultant lowered beta diversity, compared to equivalent uninvaded habitats

(Holway & Suarez, 2006). Biotic homogenisation is the process by which the genetic, taxonomic or functional similarities of regional biotas increase over time, as a result of the replacement of local biotas with non-native species (Elton, 1958; McKinney & Lockwood, 1999). Biotic homogenisation is of concern for conservation, since Argentine ants are well established in natural environments on the north-eastern Iberian Peninsula (Roura-Pascual *et al.*, 2010), in coastal California (Holway & Suarez, 2006) and in North Carolina (Rowles & Silverman, 2010). They are equally well-established in protected areas in the Western Cape Province (Luruli, 2007), including Jonkershoek Nature Reserve near Stellenbosch (Witt, 1993), Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve near Hermanus (Bond & Slingsby, 1984; Christian, 2001), Helderberg Nature Reserve outside Somerset West (Boonzaaier, 2006), and Table Mountain National Park in Cape Town (Picker & Samways, 1996; Pryke & Samways, 2009b; 2010). The extent of biotic homogenisation caused by Argentine ant invasion in the Western Cape is not yet fully described or understood.

Invasive ants directly and indirectly alter assemblages of other invertebrates, through resource competition and predation (Human & Gordon, 1997; Hoffmann *et al.*, 1999). However, these impacts are not always simply detrimental. Some studies show no, or only weak, community-level effects (Holway, 1998; Walters, 2006; Rowles & Silverman, 2010). Ground-dwelling taxa that prey on ants may benefit from ant invasions; for example, ant-lions in California (Glenn & Holway, 2008) and myrmecophagic spiders in Japan (Touyama *et al.*, 2008). The magnitude of the impacts of Argentine ants on native, non-ant invertebrates, especially ground-dwelling arthropods, is often proportional to the degree of evolutionary coexistence of the native invertebrate community with aggressive native ant species (Hoffmann & Parr, 2008 and references therein). Island faunas that lack native ants demonstrate the most devastating effects from invasive ants. In Hawaii, spiders and predatory beetles (especially native carabids) are especially negatively affected by invasive ants (Cole *et al.*, 1992; Holway *et al.*, 2002; Liebherr & Krushelnycky, 2007), and compositional changes occur most often among endemic arthropods (Krushelnycky & Gillespie, 2008). Impacts may also be greater on the edge of habitat fragments. For example, the abundance and species richness of Acari, Hemiptera, Coleoptera, Diptera and non-ant Hymenoptera are negatively correlated with Argentine ant abundance in urban habitat fragments in coastal southern California (Bolger *et al.*, 2000).

Soft-bodied taxa, such as Collembola and larval Lepidoptera, appear to be exceptionally vulnerable to invasive ants (Cole *et al.*, 1992; Human & Gordon, 1997; Rowles & O'Dowd, 2009). Woodlice and cockroaches are able to persist in the presence of invasive ants, probably because they are protected by their hard, often armoured exoskeletons (Hoffmann & Parr,

2008), and may even show greater abundance at invaded sites (Human & Gordon, 1997; Bolger *et al.*, 2000; Walters & Mackay, 2003). Amphipods are either more abundant in invaded areas (Walters & Mackay, 2003), or show no change in numbers with invasion (Walters, 2006) in South Australia. Psocoptera and other scavengers may increase in abundance with invasion, because the versatility of their diets helps reduce direct resource competition with invasive ants, and an increased ant biomass means that more dead ants and prey remains are available for scavengers to feed on (Bolger *et al.*, 2000; Walters & Mackay, 2003; Rowles & O'Dowd, 2009). Many honeydew-producing Homoptera, such as scale insects, mealybugs, aphids and membracids, readily establish symbiotic relationships with alien ants (Holway *et al.*, 2002).

This ability to establish mutualisms with native membracids enables Argentine ants to interfere with natural pollination mechanisms. In fynbos, Argentine ants are attracted to native honeydew-producing membracids (*Beaufortiana* sp.) in *Protea* inflorescences, and this mutualism facilitates pollinator deterrence by Argentine ants (Lach, 2007). *Protea nitida* and probably many other fynbos *Protea* species suffer a decline in insect pollinator visitation, decreased pollinator activity in areas where pollen transfer occurs, and a resultant decline in seed set in the presence of Argentine ants (Lach, 2007). Argentine ants also consume floral nectar, which further negatively affects arthropod pollinators (Visser *et al.*, 1996). Pollen-limited, arthropod-pollinated plants are the most susceptible to invasive ants; as evidenced in other parts of the world. In Hawaii, Argentine ants threaten insect-pollinated plants, such as *Metrosideros polymorpha*, by depleting floral nectar and displacing native bee pollinators (Cole *et al.*, 1992; Lach, 2005; 2008). In Spain, Argentine ants threaten *Euphorbia characias* by decreasing visitation times by fly pollinators and overall numbers of arthropod visitors (Blancafort & Gomez, 2005), and displacing native ant pollinators (Blancafort & Gomez, 2006).

By displacing native ants, Argentine ants also have the potential to disrupt the obligatory associations between larvae of myrmecophilous lycaenid butterflies and their native ant hosts (Heath & Claassens, 2003). Myrmecophiles spend at least part of their life cycle in ant colonies, as commensals, mutualists, or parasites (Hölldobler & Wilson, 1990). Lycaenid larvae and pupae use complex chemical and acoustic signals to manipulate ant behaviour in several ways (reviewed by Pierce *et al.*, 2002). Caterpillars suppress ant aggression by mimicking the pheromones of ant brood, maintain a “standing guard” of persistent ant attendants, and mimic the ants’ alarm pheromones to employ ant-mediated defensive measures. Ants are attracted to lycaenid caterpillars for the nutritious, honeydew-like secretions they produce from specialised exocrine glands called dorsal nectar organs (Pierce *et al.*, 2002; Heath & Claassens, 2003). Caterpillars are then transported into underground ant nests by their native ant hosts, where

they are protected from fire, surface predators and pathogens (Pierce *et al.*, 2002). The Western Cape *Aloeides pallida grandis* can survive in the underground nests of *Lepisiota* for up to four months, without emerging to feed on host plants, because they feed on their host ants' eggs (Pierce *et al.*, 2002). In southern Africa, lycaenids are mostly associated with two ant subfamilies: Myrmicinae and Formicinae (Pierce *et al.*, 2002). For example, *Chrysoritis dicksoni* is associated with *Crematogaster* (Myrmicinae), and *Thestor* is associated with *Anoplolepis custodiens* (Formicinae). Native host ants, such as *A. custodiens*, are often displaced by Argentine ants (Christian, 2001). On Table Mountain (Cape Peninsula, South Africa), at least 12 of the 27 Lycaenidae are myrmecophiles, several of which are regional endemics (*e.g.* *Thestor*) and on the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Hence, potential disruptions to these ant-butterfly mutualisms by invasive ants could further threaten these already sensitive species. The Brenton blue, *Orachrysops niobe*, is one of the most endangered butterflies in South Africa, and breeds at only one site in the Western Cape (Edge *et al.*, 2008). Argentine ants occur in disturbed areas surrounding the Brenton Blue Butterfly Reserve, and if they spread into the last remaining breeding site, could disrupt the mutualism between the Brenton blue and its host ant, *Camponotus baynei* (Edge *et al.*, 2008). Similarly, in Australia, 39 of the 56 obligate lycaenid myrmecophiles have distributions that overlap with Argentine ants, or other invasive ants, and it is not yet known whether these invasive ants tend to, or prey on, the lycaenid larvae (Lach & Thomas, 2008). Argentine ants more likely indirectly affect lycaenid larvae by suppressing numbers of native host ant species.

Argentine ants even displace vertebrates (Kenis *et al.*, 2009). Anecdotal, correlative and, more recently, experimental evidence show adverse effects of various invasive ants on birds, mammals and herpetofauna (summarised in Lach & Hooper-Bùi, 2010). In southern California, Argentine ants have been implicated in the decline of the Coastal horned lizard, *Phrynosoma coronatum*, (an ant specialist) throughout its range (Suarez & Case, 2002), and the decreased abundance and distribution of the Grey shrew, *Notiosorex crawfordi* (Laakkonen *et al.*, 2001). Based on experimental evidence using artificial nests, Argentine ants are thought to contribute to nest failure in birds, such as the Dark-eyed junco (*Junco hyemalis*), both directly, through chick predation and indirectly, by depleting arthropod prey resources (Suarez *et al.*, 2005). Argentine ants also compromise the reproductive success of foliage-gleaning birds on the northeastern Iberian Peninsula, by reducing arboreal foliage arthropods (Estany-Tigerström *et al.*, 2010). The impacts of Argentine ants on vertebrates in southern Africa have not yet been investigated, and although beyond the scope of this study, may be important in cases of rodent pollinated flowers (Wiens & Rourke, 1978). Several proteas have ground-hugging flowers that

are adapted for pollination by ground-dwelling rodents that also feed on nectar and insects visiting the inflorescences. Many other proteas are brightly coloured and carry their blooms high in the tree to attract avian pollinators, such as sugarbirds. High numbers of Argentine ants may reduce the visitation rates of these pollinators.

The aim of this study is to investigate the impacts of invasive alien Argentine ants on (a) native ants and (b) other invertebrates in Table Mountain National Park. The literature suggests that native ant species richness and abundance will be reduced at sites where Argentine ants are highly abundant, compared to uninvaded sites. Community composition of native ants is also expected to differ between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants, with greater similarity between invaded sites across habitats, as a result of biotic homogenisation. Co-occurrence patterns of native ant species are predicted to be nonrandomly segregated at uninvaded sites, but to show community disassembly and a tendency towards random associations at sites invaded by Argentine ants. Community disassembly is a change from nonrandom to random co-occurrence of species that alters community organisation, and has been documented in native ant communities as a result of invasion by Argentine ants (Sanders *et al.*, 2003). The impact of Argentine ants on native ants is also expected to differ according to functional group, but is predicted to be negative for most native ant species.

Invasion by Argentine ants could potentially lead to biotic homogenisation of non-ant native invertebrate communities, and facilitation of other alien invertebrates. The species richness and abundance of non-ant invertebrates and Cape Peninsula endemics are predicted to be lower at sites invaded by Argentine ants than at uninvaded sites. Conversely, the species richness and abundance of alien invertebrates is predicted to be higher at sites invaded by Argentine ants. Community composition of non-ant invertebrates, Cape Peninsula endemics and non-ant aliens are expected to differ between uninvaded and invaded sites, with greater similarity between sites invaded by Argentine ants across habitats. The impacts of invasion by Argentine ants are predicted to differ between taxa, but generally to be negative, lowering abundance at invaded sites, compared to uninvaded sites.

Methods

Study sites and collecting methods

This study compared sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants (*L. humile*) in three habitats over one spring-summer season. Refer to Chapter 2 for location of sites sampled and collecting methods used in Western Cape Afrotemperate Forest (n = 8 sites), Peninsula

Sandstone and Granite Fynbos (n = 8 sites) and pine plantation (n = 7 sites; Site 11 omitted) in Table Mountain National Park. For each of the 23 sites, data from the replicates (10 leaf litter, 10 soil, 10 pitfall trap, 10 sugar-baited ant trap and two decayed log samples) were pooled to obtain a single abundance or species richness value per site. Refer to Appendix A for a list of the 670 species collected in forest, fynbos and pine plantation.

Analyses for impacts of Argentine ants on native ants

Species-accumulation curves for the observed ant species richness in all habitats combined, and in each habitat, were calculated using S_{obs} Mao Tau sample-based rarefaction curves, randomised 50 times in EstimateS version 8 (Colwell, 2006). Species-accumulation curves were plotted to ensure that ant assemblages were adequately sampled, so that inferences on the impacts of Argentine ants on the native ant community could be made with confidence.

Mean (\pm SD) species richness and abundance of native ants were calculated at sites under Argentine ant occupancy and invasion, in STATISTICA version 9 (StatSoft, Inc., 2009). Argentine ant occupancy was scored as the presence or absence of Argentine ants at a site. Invasion was scored as “uninvaded” if Argentine ants were absent, or present in very low numbers, and “invaded” if Argentine ants were present in high numbers (over 100 individuals collected at a site). Species richness and abundance of native ants in all habitats combined, and in each habitat, were also compared using Mann-Whitney U tests for Argentine ant occupancy and invasion in STATISTICA. Native ant species richness was regressed against Argentine ant abundance at sites in each habitat, to test the prediction that native ant species richness is reduced when Argentine ants are highly abundant.

A triangular matrix of Bray-Curtis similarity of fourth-root transformed ant community composition between sites (with and without Argentine ants) was used to map the interrelationships of ant communities in cluster analysis, using complete linkage clustering, and in ordination by non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), in PRIMER version 6 (Clarke & Gorley, 2006). In an MDS plot, the x-axis represents the direction of maximum variation, with the position of samples (or sites in this case) reflecting compositional similarity. The stress value acts as a measure of reliability, since the risk of drawing false inferences from an ordination increases with greater stress. Stress values less than 0.2 are deemed reliable. Ant community composition (with and without Argentine ants) was related to normalised environmental variables using BEST, BIOENV (Clarke & Ainsworth, 1993) in PRIMER. Three nominal (area, vegetation type and Argentine ant invasion) and five continuous (latitude, longitude, elevation, soil pH and soil moisture) variables were tested. BIOENV calculates the Spearman rank

correlation (ρ) between the similarity matrix and corresponding environmental variables, to identify which environmental variables best explain the community pattern.

The same Bray-Curtis similarity matrices of fourth-root transformed ant data (with and without Argentine ants) were used for pairwise analysis of similarity (ANOSIM), to test the null hypothesis of no difference in ant community composition between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants in forest, fynbos and pine plantation. ANOSIM is the non-parametric, multivariate equivalent of ANOVA, applied to the rank similarity matrix using a permutation procedure (999 permutations) (Clarke & Green, 1988). It calculates the R statistic, which provides a relative measure of separation of predefined groups, and ranges from zero (no difference among groups) to one (all samples within groups are more similar to one another than to any samples from another group). ANOSIM was used here to confirm whether the cluster patterns identified in the ordinations were statistically significant.

Co-occurrence patterns of native ant species were compared between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants in each habitat, using Stone & Roberts' (1990) C -score index, calculated with EcoSim 7.72 simulation software (Gotelli & Entsminger, 2010). Co-occurrence analyses use a presence-absence data matrix to test for nonrandom patterns of species co-occurrence, based on a null model algorithm (Sanders *et al.*, 2003). In each matrix, rows represent species, columns represent sites, and the entries are the presence (1) or absence (0) of a species at a site. The C -score index quantifies the average number of "checkerboard units" found between all species pairs, where a checkerboard unit is a 2 x 2 submatrix of the form 0 1, 1 0 or 1 0, 0 1 (Sanders *et al.*, 2003). For each pair of species, the C -score was calculated as $(R_i - S)(R_j - S)$, where R_i and R_j are the matrix row totals for species i and j , and S is the number of sites where both species occur (Stone & Roberts, 1990). Each observed data matrix was randomised 5000 times using a null model, with fixed sums of rows and equiprobable columns, to calculate the expected C -score. If a community is structured by competitive species interactions, then its C -score should be significantly larger than expected by chance (Gotelli, 2000; Gotelli & McCabe, 2002). The standardised effect size (SES) was also calculated for each matrix, by measuring the number of standard deviations that the observed index is above or below the mean simulated (*i.e.* expected) index (Gotelli & McCabe, 2002). SES values in the range of 2.0 to -2.0 approximate the 5% significance level, and may be interpreted as random community associations. SES values greater than 2.0 suggest nonrandom segregation, while values less than -2.0 suggest nonrandom aggregation in the community.

Impacts of invasion by Argentine ants on native ant species were investigated by comparing the mean abundance of each native ant species between uninvaded sites (where

Argentine ants were absent, or present in low numbers) and invaded sites (where Argentine ants were present in high numbers). Impacts were scored by calculating the percentage change in abundance with invasion. Impacts were scored as “positive” if there was an increase in mean abundance with invasion, “negative” if there was a decrease in mean abundance with invasion, and “0” if a species was not collected at any site in that habitat.

Ant functional groups for the genera collected, and their responses to Argentine ants, were extracted from the literature. Functional groups were also expressed as a proportion of the total number of native ant species and individuals collected in uninvaded and invaded sites in each habitat, to establish whether invasion by Argentine ants impacted native ant assemblages, based on their niche dimensions.

Analyses for impacts of Argentine ants on other invertebrates

Mean (\pm SD) species richness and abundance of all non-ant invertebrates, Cape Peninsula endemics and non-ant alien invertebrates were compared between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants. Mann-Whitney *U* tests were used to compare the abundance of all non-ant invertebrates, Cape Peninsula endemics and non-ant alien invertebrates between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants in each habitat, and for all habitats combined.

A Bray-Curtis similarity matrix of fourth-root transformed community composition between sites for all non-ant invertebrates, Cape Peninsula endemics and non-ant aliens was used to map the interrelationships of invertebrate communities in cluster analysis, using complete linkage clustering, and in ordination by non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), in PRIMER. Invertebrate diversity was related to normalised environmental variables using BEST, BIOENV. Three nominal (area, vegetation type and Argentine ant invasion status) and five continuous (latitude, longitude, elevation, soil pH and soil moisture) variables were tested to identify which environmental variables best explain the community patterns observed. Pairwise ANOSIM was used to test the null hypothesis of no difference in the community composition of non-ant invertebrates, Cape Peninsula endemic species and non-ant alien species between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants in each habitat. For Cape Peninsula endemics, pine plantation sites were omitted from the MDS ordination, BIOENV and ANOSIM, because only one endemic species (*Uroplectes insignis*) was collected at Sites 2 and 4, and no endemic species was collected at the other five pine plantation sites.

Impacts of invasion by Argentine ants on non-ant invertebrates, Cape Peninsula endemics and non-ant aliens were investigated by comparing the mean abundance of each taxon (for all non-ant invertebrates) or species (for endemics and aliens) between uninvaded

and invaded sites. Impacts were scored by calculating the percentage change in abundance with invasion. Impacts were scored as “positive” if there was an increase in mean abundance with invasion, “negative” if there was a decrease in mean abundance with invasion, “neutral” if there was no difference in mean abundance with invasion, and “0” if a species was not collected at any site in that habitat.

Results

Argentine ants and native ants

Seventeen species of ants, including the invasive alien Argentine ant (*L. humile*), were collected in forest (11 species), fynbos (17 species) and pine plantation (12 species). Sampling achieved saturation for all habitats combined (Fig. 5.1a) and in fynbos (Fig. 5.1b), and closely approached saturation in forest and pine plantation (Fig. 5.1b). Therefore, ant assemblages were considered adequately sampled, allowing for inferences on the impacts of Argentine ants on the native ant community to be made with confidence.

Figure 5.1. Sample-based species accumulation curves of observed ant species richness for (a) all habitats combined and (b) each habitat. Curves were calculated using S_{obs} Mao Tau and randomized 50 times.

Argentine ants were present at 16 of the 23 sites sampled and in all habitats, but were the most abundant ant species at only eight sites. When less than 100 individual Argentine ants were collected from a site, Argentine ants were never the most abundant ant species at that site. This suggests that these sites should not be considered “invaded” by Argentine ants, may not support active Argentine ant nests, and may instead reflect foraging areas of Argentine ants. Of the eight “invaded” sites, twice as many were in forest (four) as in fynbos or pine plantation (two each).

Mean native ant species richness was not different under Argentine ant occupancy (Fig. 5.2a) or invasion (Fig. 5.2b), except in fynbos, where more ant species were collected at uninvaded than at invaded sites (Fig. 5.2b). Mean native ant abundance was also higher in fynbos sites where Argentine ants were absent (Fig. 5.2c) and/or only present in low numbers (Fig. 5.2d). Mean native ant abundance in all habitats combined was significantly different (Mann-Whitney $U = 25$, $Z = -2.227$, $p = 0.026$) between invaded and uninvaded sites. None of the other habitats differed significantly (Mann-Whitney U tests, $p > 0.05$) in native ant species richness or abundance for either Argentine ant occupancy (absence vs. presence) or invasion (none/low vs. high abundance).

Figure 5.2. Mean species richness of native ants under Argentine ant (a) occupancy and (b) invasion, and mean abundance of native ants under Argentine ant (c) occupancy and (d) invasion. The number in each bar (a and b) is the number of sites used in calculations for species richness and abundance.

No linear relationship was found between Argentine ant abundance and native ant species richness in forest ($F_{1,6} = 0.015$, $R^2 = 0.002$, $p = 0.908$), whereas weak negative linear relationships were found in both fynbos ($F_{1,6} = 3.912$, $R^2 = 0.395$, $p = 0.953$) and pine plantation ($F_{1,5} = 0.991$, $R^2 = 0.165$, $p = 0.365$) (Fig. 5.3). The relationship between Argentine ant abundance and native ant species richness may be better described as unimodal (quadratic) in forest ($F_{2,5} = 0.176$, $R^2 = 0.066$, $p = 0.844$), fynbos ($F_{2,5} = 2.604$, $R^2 = 0.510$, $p = 0.168$) and pine plantation ($F_{2,4} = 0.134$, $R^2 = 0.720$, $p = 0.079$). For all habitats combined, a weak negative linear relationship ($F_{1,21} = 3.032$, $R^2 = 0.126$, $p = 0.096$) and unimodal (quadratic) relationship ($F_{2,20} = 1.536$, $R^2 = 0.133$, $p = 0.240$) were found between Argentine ant abundance and the number of native ant species. Although native ant species richness appears to show a linearly decreasing or unimodal relationship with increasing Argentine ant abundance, none of these

relationships was significant ($p > 0.05$), possibly due to the uneven spread in Argentine ant abundance and low number of sites sampled in each habitat.

Figure 5.3. Relationship between Argentine ant abundance and native ant species richness.

Ant community composition varied between habitats and with Argentine ant invasion. In an MDS ordination of all 17 ant species (including Argentine ants), sites clustered in three groups: uninvaded fynbos sites, uninvaded forest and pine plantation sites, and all invaded sites (Fig. 5.4a). These three groups clustered close to each other, but with low (24%) similarity between them. The two sites invaded by Argentine ants in fynbos (Sites 3 and 30) were classified as recovering Sandstone Fynbos, as they were previously under pine plantation. Although Site 7 (forest in Kirstenbosch) appears to be an outlier (spatially separated from other uninvaded forest sites on the MDS plot), it was retained in the analyses, because there was no reason to believe that collector bias, adverse weather conditions or other confounding variables were responsible for the very low ant abundance and low number of ant species collected there. BIOENV identified a combination of vegetation type and Argentine ants as the strongest drivers of ant community composition ($\rho = 0.398$). All top ten BEST, BIOENV results included Argentine ants as an explanatory variable for the community composition of all 17 ant species.

When only native ant species were considered, similar community patterns emerged, but with less distinct separation of uninvaded forest and pine plantation sites from all invaded sites (Fig. 5.4b). BIOENV identified vegetation type as the strongest driver of invertebrate community composition ($\rho = 0.364$), followed by a combination of vegetation type and Argentine ants ($\rho =$

0.341). Six of the top ten BEST, BIOENV results included Argentine ant invasion as an explanatory variable for native ant community composition.

Figure 5.4. Ordination from non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), applied to a Bray-Curtis similarity matrix of fourth-root transformed community composition amongst sites for (a) all 17 ant species (including Argentine ants) and (b) native ant species only.

ANOSIM confirmed that ant community composition differed significantly between sites uninvasion and invasion by Argentine ants in fynbos (with Argentine ants: $R = 0.958$, $p = 0.036$ and without Argentine ants: $R = 0.927$, $p = 0.036$) (Table 5.1). The same was true in pine plantation (with Argentine ants: $R = 0.927$, $p = 0.048$ and without Argentine ants: $R = 0.818$, $p = 0.048$). In forest, there was little difference between sites uninvasion and invasion by Argentine ants when Argentine ants were included in the analyses ($R = 0.510$, $p = 0.029$), and no difference in community composition for native ants only ($R = -0.010$, $p = 0.371$) (Table 5.1). Ant communities of invasion sites were similar in forest, fynbos and pine plantation, with and without Argentine ants included in the analyses (Table 5.1), confirming the pattern observed in the ordination (Figure 5.4a).

Table 5.1. ANOSIM results for ant community composition at sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants in each habitat, for all 17 ant species (*i.e.* with Argentine ants) and for native ant species only (*i.e.* without Argentine ants). Values in bold are significant ($p < 0.05$).

Habitat pairs	With Argentine ants		Without Argentine ants	
	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>
Forest invaded, Forest uninvaded	0.510	0.029	-0.010	0.371
Fynbos invaded, Fynbos uninvaded	0.958	0.036	0.927	0.036
Pine invaded, Pine uninvaded	0.927	0.048	0.818	0.048
Forest invaded, Fynbos invaded	0.000	0.467	-0.036	0.600
Forest invaded, Pine invaded	-0.143	0.733	-0.143	0.667
Fynbos invaded, Pine invaded	-0.750	1.000	-0.750	1.000
Forest uninvaded, Fynbos uninvaded	0.528	0.005	0.504	0.010
Forest uninvaded, Pine uninvaded	0.200	0.079	0.275	0.040
Fynbos uninvaded, Pine uninvaded	0.835	0.002	0.819	0.002
Forest invaded, Fynbos uninvaded	0.865	0.005	0.738	0.005
Forest invaded, Pine uninvaded	0.750	0.008	0.200	0.127
Forest uninvaded, Fynbos invaded	0.893	0.067	0.714	0.067
Forest uninvaded, Pine invaded	0.571	0.133	0.214	0.267
Fynbos invaded, Pine uninvaded	0.945	0.048	0.909	0.048
Fynbos uninvaded, Pine invaded	0.885	0.036	0.823	0.036

At sites uninvaded by Argentine ants across habitats ($n = 15$ sites), there was evidence for nonrandom co-occurrence patterns (*i.e.* aggregation) of native ant species, with a low *C*-score (5.083) compared to the null distribution (8.632), and a standardised effect size (-6.651) well below -2.0, assuming a normal distribution of standard deviations (Table 5.2). At sites invaded by Argentine ants ($n = 8$ sites), co-occurrence patterns of native ant species were random, with little difference between observed (1.291) and null (1.794) *C*-scores, and a standardised effect size (-1.937) falling within the 95% confidence interval, which lies between 2.0 and -2.0 (Table 5.2). Uninvaded fynbos sites also showed significantly more species co-occurrence (aggregation) than expected by chance, whereas invaded fynbos sites and both uninvaded and invaded sites in forest and pine plantation showed random co-occurrence of

native ant species (Table 5.2). This suggests that, at least in fynbos, invasive alien Argentine ants may be responsible for the community disassembly of native ants.

Table 5.2. Co-occurrence of native ant species at sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants. Observed = observed C-score index, Expected = mean of the simulated C-score indices, and SES = standardised effect size. Values in bold are significant ($p < 0.05$).

C-score	Observed	Expected	p (observed \leq expected)	p (observed \geq expected)	SES
All habitats					
Uninvaded	5.083	8.632	< 0.001	1.000	-6.651
Invaded	1.291	1.794	0.045	0.961	-1.937
Forest					
Uninvaded	0.583	0.573	0.502	0.546	0.082
Invaded	0.472	0.618	0.158	0.872	-1.062
Fynbos					
Uninvaded	0.683	1.057	0.003	0.998	-3.569
Invaded	0.267	0.201	1.000	0.380	0.811
Pine plantation					
Uninvaded	0.806	0.850	0.366	0.672	-0.253
Invaded	0.000	0.178	0.067	1.000	-3.098

Across habitats, numbers of all native ant species, except *Tetramorium* sp. and *Tetraoponera* sp., were negatively impacted by Argentine ants, with lower mean abundance at invaded sites compared to sites where Argentine ants were absent, or only present in low numbers (less than 100 individuals) (Table 5.3). Fynbos dictated the impacts for habitats combined for all ant species, except for *Tetramorium* sp., but the impact of Argentine ants differed between habitats for at least five ant species (Table 5.3). Although *Tetraoponera* sp. was collected in very low numbers in each habitat, it appears to be the only species positively associated with Argentine ant invasion across habitats (Table 5.3). Six ant species were absent from invaded sites: *Camponotus* sp. 1 (*maculatus* group), *Lepisiota capensis*, *Meranoplus* sp., *Myrmecaria nigra*, *Pheidole capensis* and *Hagensia peringueyi*. These six species appear to be displaced by Argentine ants. *Monomorium* sp. and *Tetramorium grassii* were present at all eight invaded sites, and at most or all uninvaded sites, respectively. These two species appear to be negatively associated with Argentine ants in fynbos and pine plantation, but *T. grassii* increased in mean abundance at invaded sites in forest. Several ant species were collected from only a

few sites, and as a result, the impacts observed may be incidental (reflecting naturally patchy distributions), rather than a consequence of Argentine ant invasion. Alternatively, these species may have already been displaced by Argentine ants from otherwise suitable sites.

Table 5.3. Impacts of invasion by Argentine ants on the mean abundance of native ant species collected. Impacts were scored as “positive” if there was an increase in mean abundance with invasion, “negative” if there was a decrease in mean abundance with invasion, and “0” if a species was not collected at any site in that habitat. Percentage change in abundance with invasion is expressed in parentheses. * = absent in uninvaded.

Native ant species	All habitats	Forest	Fynbos	Pine
<i>Tapinoma</i> sp.	negative (-34.36%)	0	negative (-100.00%)	positive (*)
<i>Technomyrmex pallipes</i>	negative (-95.11%)	0	negative (-95.17%)	positive (*)
<i>Camponotus bertolinii</i>	negative (-80.93%)	positive (571.43%)	negative (-99.19%)	negative (-91.32%)
<i>Camponotus niveosetosus</i>	negative (-97.60%)	negative (-61.54%)	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)
<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 1 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	negative (-100.00%)	0	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 2 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	negative (-98.74%)	negative (-94.13%)	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-97.50%)
<i>Lepisiota capensis</i>	negative (-99.98%)	negative (-75.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)
<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	negative (-99.32%)	negative (-85.19%)	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Meranoplus</i> sp.	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Monomorium</i> sp.	negative (-67.66%)	negative (-43.52%)	negative (-79.88%)	negative (-90.61%)
<i>Myrmicaria nigra</i>	negative (-100.00%)	0	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Pheidole capensis</i>	negative (-100.00%)	0	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Tetramorium grassii</i>	negative (-5.94%)	positive (5.88%)	negative (-89.84%)	negative (-71.06%)
<i>Tetramorium</i> sp.	positive (820.61%)	positive (*)	negative (-87.25%)	negative (-92.13%)
<i>Hagensia peringueyi</i>	negative (-100.00%)	0	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Tetraponera</i> sp.	positive (261.11%)	positive (100.00%)	positive (987.50%)	positive (87.50%)

The 17 ant species (in 13 genera) collected were divided among six functional groups and vary in their known responses to Argentine ants (Table 5.4). Fewer Tropical Climate Specialist species were present at invaded sites than at uninvaded sites, in both forest and pine plantation (Fig. 5.5a). Opportunist species decreased with invasion in forest, but increased with invasion in pine plantation. Generalized Myrmicinae and Subordinate Camponotini showed no change in numbers of species with invasion across habitats. In fynbos, the proportion of species in each functional group did not differ between invaded and uninvaded sites (Fig. 5.5a). Fynbos was notably the only habitat to support the Specialist Predators functional group, represented by *Hagensia*. All functional groups (except for Opportunists in forest) decreased in abundance with

invasion in all habitats (Figure 5.5b). These declines were by at least 50%, and often by an order of magnitude or more. For example, Opportunists in fynbos decreased from 12 470 individuals at uninvaded sites to only 70 at invaded sites. Opportunists were the only functional group to differ from the general trend of declines with invasion in species richness and abundance, showing a decrease in the number of species (from three to two), but an increase in the number of individuals (from 1944 to 4164), with invasion in forest, and an increase in the number of species (from three to five) with invasion in pine plantation.

Table 5.4. Ant functional groups and their response to the Argentine ant (*L. humile*), based on supporting literature. Functional groups (Andersen, 1997a): DD = Dominant Dolichoderinae, GM = Generalized Myrmicinae, OPP = Opportunists, SC = Subordinate Camponotini, SP = Specialist Predators and TCS = Tropical Climate Specialists.

Genus	Foraging habits	Functional group	Competitive response (at the generic level)	References
Dolichoderinae				
<i>Linepithema</i>	mostly epigaeic	DD	Abundant, active and aggressive. Strong competitive influence over other ants.	Andersen, 1997a
<i>Tapinoma</i>	arboreal	OPP	Subordinate behaviour.	Majer <i>et al.</i> , 2004
<i>Technomyrmex</i>	epigaeic	OPP	Subordinate behaviour.	Majer <i>et al.</i> , 2004
Formicinae				
<i>Camponotus</i>	epigaeic	SC	Behaviourally submissive to <i>L. humile</i> .	Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003
<i>Lepisiota</i>	hypogaeic	OPP	Appears to resist invasions by <i>L. humile</i> .	Matilya, 2003; Edge <i>et al.</i> , 2008
Myrmicinae				
<i>Crematogaster</i>	arboreal	GM	Forage on tree trunks, so little direct interaction with <i>L. humile</i> .	Brown, 2000
<i>Meranoplus</i>	epigaeic	TCS	Occurs where <i>L. humile</i> is not dominant.	Andersen, 2000
<i>Monomorium</i>	epigaeic	GM	Chemical secretions used to repel attacks by <i>L. humile</i> .	Holway, 1999
<i>Myrmecaria</i>	epigaeic	TCS	In habitats with low abundance of <i>L. humile</i> .	Majer <i>et al.</i> , 2004
<i>Pheidole</i>	epigaeic	GM	Similar resource requirements to <i>L. humile</i> .	Christian, 2001
<i>Tetramorium</i>	epigaeic	OPP	Coexist with <i>L. humile</i> . Opportunist and defend nest entrances against attack.	Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003
Ponerinae				
<i>Hagensia</i>	epigaeic	SP	Specialist diet, large body size and small colony. Little interaction with other ants.	Andersen, 1997a
Pseudomyrmicinae				
<i>Tetraponera</i>	arboreal	TCS	Occurs where DD generally not abundant.	Andersen, 1997a

Figure 5.5. Functional groups expressed (a) as a proportion of the total number of native ant species and (b) as a proportion of the total number of native ant individuals collected at sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants in each habitat. Functional groups: GM = Generalized Myrmicinae, OPP = Opportunists, SC = Subordinate Camponotini, SP = Specialist Predators and TCS = Tropical Climate Specialists.

Argentine ants and other invertebrates

In total, 21 866 individuals from 653 non-ant invertebrate species were collected at the 23 sites sampled. Of these, 15 014 individuals (1000.9 ± 653.4 SD individuals per site) and 557 species were collected at uninvaded sites, compared to 6852 individuals (856.5 ± 376.3 individuals per site) and 403 species were collected from sites invaded by Argentine ants. Mean species richness of all non-ant invertebrates was slightly higher at sites uninvaded by Argentine ants than at invaded sites, although no clear differences were evident in fynbos or all habitats combined (Fig. 5.6a). Mean abundance of all non-ant invertebrates, contrary to prediction, was higher at invaded sites in all habitats combined, forest and fynbos, although the opposite was observed in pine plantation (Fig. 5.6b). Mean species richness (Fig. 5.6c) and abundance (Fig. 5.6d) of Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates was higher at uninvaded sites than at sites invaded by Argentine ants. Conversely, mean species richness (Fig. 5.6e) and abundance (Fig. 5.6f) of non-ant alien invertebrates was lower at uninvaded sites in forest and fynbos, but not so in pine plantation. Despite these general trends, the species richness and abundance of all non-ant invertebrates, Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates and non-ant alien invertebrates did not differ significantly (Mann-Whitney U tests, $p > 0.05$) between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants.

Figure 5.6. Mean (+ SD) species richness and abundance of (a and b) all non-ant invertebrates, (c and d) Cape Peninsula endemics and (e and f) non-ant alien invertebrates at sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants.

The community composition of non-ant invertebrates differed between habitats, with sites clustering according to habitat, irrespective of whether sites were invaded by Argentine ants or not (Fig. 5.7a). Similarity among habitat clusters of non-ant invertebrates was low (<30%). Fynbos sites were the least similar to one another, with Granite Fynbos (Sites 6 and 8) separated from both Sandstone Fynbos (Sites 10, 14, 17 and 26) and recovering Sandstone Fynbos (Sites 3 and 30). Sandstone Fynbos sites were more similar to each other than to Granite Fynbos sites, regardless of their disturbance history, or invasion by Argentine ants. BIOENV identified vegetation type as the strongest driver of non-ant invertebrate community composition ($\rho = 0.665$), followed by a combination of vegetation type and soil moisture ($\rho = 0.547$). All top ten BEST BIOENV results for non-ant invertebrates included vegetation type as an explanatory variable for non-ant invertebrate community composition. However, only the tenth BEST result ($\rho = 0.425$) included Argentine ant invasion, together with vegetation type and soil moisture, as an explanatory variable.

The community composition of Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates differed between forest and fynbos, and between fynbos vegetation types, but was not determined by Argentine ant invasion (Fig. 5.7b). BIOENV identified vegetation type as the strongest driver of endemic invertebrate community composition ($\rho = 0.665$), and as an explanatory variable for all top ten BEST BIOENV results for the community composition of Cape Peninsula endemics. Argentine ant invasion was not an important explanatory variable for endemic community composition, featuring in only two of the top ten BEST BIOENV results, and in combination with several other environmental variables.

The community composition of non-ant alien invertebrates was not clearly determined by either habitat or Argentine ant invasion (Fig. 5.7c). At 40% similarity between clusters (grouping shown in Fig. 5.7c), there was some evidence for separation of sites based on invasion by Argentine ants, with five of the eight invaded sites clustering together. None of the variables tested in BIOENV proved to be a strong driver of non-ant alien invertebrate community composition. The BEST BIOENV result for non-ant alien invertebrates ($\rho = 0.339$) included altitude, vegetation type and Argentine ant invasion. Seven of the top ten BEST BIOENV results for non-ant aliens included Argentine ant invasion as one of the explanatory variables.

Figure 5.7. MDS ordination applied to Bray-Curtis similarity matrices of fourth-root transformed data of community composition amongst sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants for (a) all non-ant invertebrates, (b) Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates and (c) non-ant alien invertebrates. For Cape Peninsula endemics, pine plantation sites were excluded, because endemics were mostly absent in pine plantation.

ANOSIM for all non-ant invertebrates confirmed that habitat (vegetation type) had a stronger influence on the community composition than Argentine ant invasion (Table 5.5). No significant difference in the community composition of non-ant invertebrates between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants was found within forest ($R = -0.031$, $p = 0.571$), fynbos ($R = 0.052$, $p = 0.429$), or pine plantation ($R = 0.291$, $p = 0.190$). There were also no significant differences between invaded sites in each pairwise combination of habitats. However, the community composition of non-ant invertebrates was significantly different between uninvaded sites in different habitats, with uninvaded sites in forest and pine plantation the most different ($R = 0.975$, $p = 0.008$).

ANOSIM for Cape Peninsula endemics showed that the community composition of uninvaded sites was significantly different ($R = 0.746$, $p = 0.005$) in forest and fynbos (Table

5.5). Invasion by Argentine ants did not significantly alter the community composition of endemics, both within and between habitats.

ANOSIM for non-ant alien invertebrates showed no difference in community composition between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants in forest or pine plantation, and little significant difference in fynbos ($R = 0.552$, $p = 0.036$) (Table 5.5). Although significant differences were found between uninvaded habitats, these differences were weak ($R \leq 0.525$, $p < 0.05$). This explained the pattern observed in the MDS ordination (Fig. 5.7c), in which clusters overlapped and were not clearly defined by either habitat or Argentine ant invasion, and despite five of the eight invaded sites clustering together.

Table 5.5. ANOSIM results for the community composition of all non-ant invertebrates, Cape Peninsula endemics, and non-ant alien invertebrates, at sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants. Values in bold are significant ($p < 0.05$).

Habitat pairs	All non-ants		Endemics		Aliens	
	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>
Forest invaded, Forest uninvaded	-0.031	0.571	-0.073	0.714	0.198	0.114
Fynbos invaded, Fynbos uninvaded	0.052	0.429	0.333	0.143	0.552	0.036
Pine invaded, Pine uninvaded	0.291	0.190	*		-0.018	0.524
Forest invaded, Fynbos invaded	0.893	0.067	0.804	0.067	-0.179	0.800
Forest invaded, Pine invaded	1.000	0.067	*		-0.179	0.600
Fynbos invaded, Pine invaded	0.500	0.333	*		-0.250	1.000
Forest uninvaded, Fynbos uninvaded	0.631	0.010	0.746	0.005	0.460	0.010
Forest uninvaded, Pine uninvaded	0.975	0.008	*		0.344	0.024
Fynbos uninvaded, Pine uninvaded	0.544	0.006	*		0.525	0.006
Forest invaded, Fynbos uninvaded	0.671	0.010	0.821	0.005	0.540	0.010
Forest invaded, Pine uninvaded	0.856	0.008	*		0.244	0.103
Forest uninvaded, Fynbos invaded	0.964	0.067	0.446	0.133	0.929	0.067
Forest uninvaded, Pine invaded	1.000	0.067	*		0.714	0.067
Fynbos invaded, Pine uninvaded	0.891	0.048	*		0.527	0.095
Fynbos uninvaded, Pine invaded	0.250	0.143	*		0.427	0.107

* Comparisons with pine omitted, because endemics were mostly absent in pine plantation.

The association of Argentine ants with non-ant invertebrates differed among taxa and across habitats, with a few more positive ($n = 16$) than negative ($n = 12$) impacts in fynbos, whereas more than half ($n = 17$) of the taxa showed negative impacts in pine plantation (Table 5.6). Soft-bodied taxa had lower mean abundance at invaded sites across habitats (velvet worms, flatworms and slugs), or at least in the habitat where they were most abundant (earthworms). Snails and springtails, which could also be considered “soft-bodied”, had higher abundance at invaded sites. Centipedes and millipedes both mostly showed positive impacts across habitats, but negative impacts in pine plantation. The two crustacean taxa had different responses to invasion by Argentine ants, with landhoppers showing no change in mean abundance, and woodlice higher mean abundance at invaded sites in all habitats. In most cases, arachnids were negatively impacted by Argentine ant invasion, although impacts varied among taxa and habitats. For insects, impacts also varied among orders and across habitats, with slightly more positive than negative impacts of Argentine ants. Beetles, crickets, earwigs and psocids showed higher mean abundance at invaded sites, whereas bugs, cockroaches, flies and wasps showed lower or no change in mean abundance at invaded sites. The remaining insect orders were collected in low numbers, and represented by only one or two species, often reflecting incidental catches.

Table 5.6. Impacts of invasion by Argentine ants on the mean abundance of non-ant invertebrate taxa. Impacts were scored as “positive” if there was an increase in mean abundance with invasion, “negative” if there was a decrease in mean abundance with invasion, “neutral” if there was no difference in mean abundance with invasion, and “0” if a species was not collected at any site in that habitat. Percentage change in abundance with invasion is expressed in parentheses. * = absent in uninvaded.

Common name	All habitats	Forest	Fynbos	Pine
Bees	positive (181.25%)	0	positive (350.00%)	0
Beetles	positive (72.70%)	positive (7.25%)	positive (909.29%)	positive (*)
Bristletails	positive (608.84%)	positive (442.31%)	positive (333.33%)	negative (-58.33%)
Bugs	negative (-20.98%)	negative (-18.40%)	positive (19.32%)	negative (-31.16%)
Centipedes	positive (8.68%)	positive (3.03%)	positive (80.00%)	negative (-69.70%)
Cockroaches	negative (-60.75%)	negative (-49.38%)	negative (-64.51%)	positive (111.54%)
Crickets	positive (104.36%)	positive (61.02%)	positive (279.15%)	positive (69.08%)
Earthworms	positive (53.86%)	negative (-34.87%)	positive (148.78%)	positive (451.83%)
Earwigs	positive (73.35%)	positive (75.51%)	positive (350.00%)	negative (-59.09%)
Flatworms	negative (-71.70%)	negative (-100.00%)	positive (100.00%)	negative (-6.25%)
Flies	negative (-37.42%)	positive (4.00%)	negative (-69.00%)	negative (-66.38%)
Harvestmen	positive (608.84%)	negative (-12.27%)	negative (-25.00%)	negative (-86.98%)
Lacewings	negative (-100.00%)	0	0	negative (-100.00%)
Landhoppers	negative (-3.30%)	negative (-36.30%)	negative (-47.55%)	negative (-59.16%)
Millipedes	positive (23.45%)	positive (9.85%)	positive (169.66%)	negative (-33.11%)
Mites	negative (-12.28%)	negative (-39.73%)	positive (50.00%)	negative (-14.87%)
Moths	positive (203.98%)	positive (108.16%)	negative (-50.00%)	positive (50.00%)
Praying mantids	negative (-6.25%)	positive (*)	negative (-100.00%)	positive (*)
Pseudoscorpions	negative (-3.41%)	neutral (0%)	negative (-18.18%)	negative (-100.00%)
Psocids/barklice	positive (12.50%)	positive (13.64%)	negative (-40.00%)	positive (11.84%)
Scorpions	negative (-13.46%)	negative (-71.43%)	positive (71.43%)	neutral (0%)
Silverfish	negative (-100.00%)	0	negative (-100.00%)	0
Slugs	negative (-27.88%)	negative (-19.57%)	positive (62.50%)	negative (-77.43%)
Snails	positive (113.77%)	positive (36.32%)	negative (-14.29%)	positive (114.29%)
Spiders	positive (17.61%)	negative (-98.15%)	negative (-100.00%)	0
Springtails	positive (183.61%)	positive (242.90%)	positive (7.87%)	negative (-71.80%)
Stick insects	negative (-53.13%)	0	neutral (0%)	negative (-100.00%)
Sun-spiders	negative (-68.75%)	0	negative (-50.00%)	0
Thrips	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	0	0
Velvet worms	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	0	negative (-100.00%)
Wasps	negative (-6.63%)	positive (9.94%)	positive (4.76%)	negative (-76.63%)
Woodlice	positive (479.21%)	positive (17.86%)	positive (3221.43%)	positive (4733.33%)

The impacts of Argentine ant invasion on Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates differed among species and across habitats (Table 5.7). The worst negative impacts were recorded for habitat specialists: specifically, the two cockroach species (*Dipteretreum brinckae* and *Hoplophoropyga unicolor*) restricted to fynbos, and the dung beetle species (*Bohepilissus nitidus*) restricted to forest. *D. brinckae* was not collected at sites invaded by Argentine ants, despite being abundant at most uninvaded fynbos sites. None of the four endemic spider species was collected at fynbos sites invaded by Argentine ants.

Table 5.7. Impacts of invasion by Argentine ants on the mean abundance of Cape Peninsula endemic species. Impacts were scored as “positive” if there was an increase in mean abundance with invasion, “negative” if there was a decrease in mean abundance with invasion, “neutral” if there was no difference in mean abundance with invasion, and “0” if a species was not collected at any site in that habitat. Percentage change in abundance with invasion is expressed in parentheses.

Endemic Impacts	All habitats [#]	Forest	Fynbos	Pine
<i>Trachycystis perplicata</i>	positive (837.50%)	positive (400.00%)	0	0
<i>Spermophora gordimerae</i>	positive (134.38%)	positive (400.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Spermophora peninsulae</i>	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	0	0
<i>Malaika longipes</i>	positive (12.50%)	negative (-25.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Moggridgea teresae</i>	positive (50.00%)	neutral (0%)	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Uroplectes insignis</i>	positive (4.17%)	negative (-71.43%)	positive (157.14%)	positive (25.00%)
<i>Dipteretreum brinckae</i>	negative (-100.00%)	0	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Hoplophoropyga unicolor</i>	negative (-73.21%)	0	negative (-57.14%)	0
<i>Bohepilissus nitidus</i>	negative (-55.65%)	negative (-76.34%)	0	0

[#] Pine plantation sites were excluded from calculations of impacts for all habitats combined, because only one endemic species was collected in pine plantation.

The impacts of invasion by Argentine ants on non-ant alien invertebrates differed among species and across habitats, but more positive than negative associations were recorded in both forest and fynbos (Table 5.8). The three widespread and abundant alien slug species (*Arion hortensis* aggregate, *Deroceras panormitanum* and *Lehmannia valentiana*) were negatively associated with Argentine ant invasion across habitats. Alien snails, on the other hand, were mostly positively associated with Argentine ants, with six of the eight alien snail species collected in greater numbers at invaded sites across habitats. Both *Oxychilus* species, the only alien snails found in all three habitats, were among those snail species with higher mean

abundance at sites invaded by Argentine ants. Portuguese millipedes (*Ommatoiulus moreleti*) had lower mean abundance, whereas Rough woodlice (*Porcellio scaber*) had higher mean abundance at sites invaded by Argentine ants. Two alien springtails (*Entomobrya nivalis* and *Tomocerus minor*) had lower mean abundance at invaded sites, whereas the third alien springtail (*Neanura muscorum*) had higher mean abundance in all invaded habitats. European wasps (*Vespula germanica*) had higher mean abundance at invaded forest sites, but lower mean abundance in fynbos and pine plantation, where they were absent at invaded sites.

Table 5.8. Impacts of invasion by Argentine ants on the mean abundance of other alien invertebrate species. Impacts were scored as “positive” if there was an increase in mean abundance with invasion, “negative” if there was a decrease in mean abundance with invasion, and “0” if a species was not collected at any site in that habitat. Percentage change in abundance with invasion is expressed in parentheses. * = absent in uninvaded.

Alien impacts	All	Forest	Fynbos	Pine
<i>Arion hortensis</i> complex	negative (-20.79%)	positive (16.33%)	positive (35.00%)	negative (-72.46%)
<i>Deroceras panormitanum</i>	negative (-63.71%)	negative (-75.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)
<i>Lehmannia valentiana</i>	negative (-41.96%)	negative (-52.63%)	positive (*)	negative (-100.00%)
<i>Limax maximus</i>	positive (*)	positive (*)	0	0
<i>Cochlicopa</i> sp.	positive (*)	positive (*)	0	0
<i>Cochlicopa</i> cf. <i>lubricella</i>	positive (5243.75%)	positive (*)	0	positive (25.00%)
<i>Vitrea contracta</i>	positive (212.50%)	negative (-37.50%)	0	positive (837.50%)
<i>Cornu aspersum</i>	negative (-62.50%)	negative (-80.00%)	0	0
cf. <i>Punctum</i> sp.	positive (115.07%)	positive (*)	0	negative (-70.59%)
<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	negative (-100.00%)	0	0	negative (-100.00%)
<i>Oxychilus draparnaudi</i>	positive (*)	positive (*)	positive (*)	positive (*)
<i>Oxychilus</i> sp.	positive (5150.00%)	positive (*)	positive (*)	positive (2150.00%)
<i>Ommatoiulus moreleti</i>	negative (-0.54%)	negative (-22.38%)	positive (170.00%)	negative (-26.54%)
<i>Porcellio scaber</i>	positive (1337.50%)	positive (500.00%)	positive (3312.50%)	positive (316.67%)
<i>Entomobrya nivalis</i>	negative (-100.00%)	0	0	negative (-100.00%)
<i>Neanura muscorum</i>	positive (1025.00%)	positive (*)	positive (*)	positive (150.00%)
<i>Tomocerus minor</i>	negative (-100.00%)	0	negative (-100.00%)	0
<i>Vespula germanica</i>	negative (-1.79%)	positive (175.00%)	negative (-100.00%)	negative (-100.00%)

Discussion

Associations of Argentine ants and native ants

Changes in native ant assemblages with Argentine ant invasion are assumed to be the result of Argentine ant impacts, and not simply habitat heterogeneity. Argentine ants were considered to have invaded sites only when present in high numbers (over 100 individuals per site); such that eight of the 23 sites sampled were considered invaded. Even though Argentine ants have several behavioural and life history traits that contribute to their invasion success (Moller, 1996; Human & Gordon, 1997; Holway, 1999), invasion success is often dependent on sheer numbers (Walters, 2006; Rowles & O'Dowd, 2007). Argentine ants adopt what game theory terms the “bourgeois strategy” during antagonistic interactions with other species, whereby lone workers tend to be submissive, but workers in the presence of fellow colony members are always aggressive (Carpintero & Reyez-López, 2008).

Argentine ants appear to have impacted the species richness, abundance and community composition of native ants in forest, fynbos and pine plantation on the Cape Peninsula, to varying degrees. Mean species richness and abundance of native ants was either unchanged, or lower, under Argentine ant occupancy and invasion (Fig. 5.2), although these impacts were not significantly different. Luruli (2007) found that in fynbos, native ant species richness may be eight times lower at Argentine ant invaded, compared to uninvaded, bait stations. Reduced native ant species richness and abundance in the presence of Argentine ants has also been reported in California (DiGirolamo & Fox, 2006; Glenn & Holway, 2008; Heller *et al.*, 2008), Spain (Oliveras *et al.*, 2005), Australia (Walters & Mackay, 2003; Walters, 2006), and Japan (Touyama *et al.*, 2003).

The most pronounced impact of Argentine ants on native ants was observed in fynbos, where the mean species richness and abundance of native ants were both higher in the absence of Argentine ants (Fig. 5.2). In accordance, native ant species richness decreased linearly with increasing Argentine ant abundance in fynbos (Fig. 5.3). Likewise, the ant community at uninvaded fynbos sites clustered separately (Fig. 5.4) and differed significantly (Table 5.1) from the ant communities at all invaded sites, and from ant communities at uninvaded sites in forest and pine plantation. When species were considered individually, fynbos was the worst affected habitat, with mean abundance of all native ant species (except for *Tetraponera* sp.) negatively affected by Argentine ant invasion (Table 5.3). The two sites in fynbos that were invaded (Sites 3 and 30), were also the only two recovering Sandstone Fynbos sites sampled, confounding the interpretation. These sites were previously under pine plantation

and this historic disturbance may have facilitated Argentine ant invasion. Although it appears unlikely, it remains unclear whether Argentine ants are able to establish permanent colonies in undisturbed fynbos on the Cape Peninsula, as has been reported in other protected areas (e.g. Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve: Christian, 2001).

By comparison, native ant assemblages in Afrotropical forest appear to be similarly impacted to those in the adjacent pine plantation. This was expected, since the majority of ant species in pine plantation most likely originated from native forest (since these habitats are quite similar) and/or represent widespread, habitat-generalist species. Of the six ant species not collected in pine plantations, several are seed-harvesting species, such as *Crematogaster*, *Myrmecaria nigra* and *Pheidole capensis* (Table 5.3). These species may not naturally survive under pine plantations, or may have already been displaced by Argentine ants, if they had previously colonised these pine plantations. Pine plantations on the Cape Peninsula support few flowering plants and hardly ever any Proteaceae (C. Uys pers. obs.), so offer few opportunities for seed-harvesting ants.

Tetraponera sp. was collected in low numbers (only two sites had more than 10 individuals) across all habitats and sites, suggesting that the positive impacts calculated (Table 5.3) may not be meaningful. *Tetraponera* usually occur in areas where the Dominant Dolichoderinae functional group is absent (Andersen, 1997a, Table 5.4). Locally, *Tetraponera* is usually found in small colonies, nesting in dry flower-stalks of *Watsonia*, *Aristea* and other long-stemmed flowering plants (Skaife, 1961), and as such may avoid nest-raids by Argentine ants. Nest-raiding of native ant species is an aggressive behavioural trait of invasive ants, and has been reported in Argentine ants by Rowles & O'Dowd (2007), Carpintero & Reyes-López (2008) and others. Epigaeic ant species are often worse affected by Argentine ant invasion than their arboreal counterparts (Harris, 2002).

Anoplolepis custodiens was not collected in this study, and was most notably missing from fynbos sites. *A. custodiens* is considered the most important species in myrmecochorous seed-dispersal of large-seeded proteas and other fynbos plants (De Kock & Giliomee, 1989; Christian, 2001; Witt *et al.*, 2004). It is never present in areas where Argentine ants have invaded (Christian, 2001; Luruli, 2007), despite its dominant, aggressive behaviour towards other ants (Majer *et al.*, 2004). This suggests that *A. custodiens* may have been entirely displaced by Argentine ants from the moist eastern slopes of Table Mountain National Park. Although recorded in 1995 and 1998 (H. Robertson unpublished museum records) in close proximity to fynbos Site 26 at Tokai (where Argentine ants were present only in low numbers), *A. custodiens* may never have occurred in high numbers on the moist eastern slopes of the

Cape Peninsula, as it typically occupies more arid habitats (Prins, 1982). It is not clear why *A. custodiens* appears to be absent at fynbos sites uninvaded by Argentine ants. This possible local extinction is of grave concern for the conservation of Proteaceae, especially in Peninsula Granite Fynbos, which is listed as 'Endangered' (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). Up to 30% of the fynbos flora (including 50% of the Proteaceae) depends on seed dispersal by ants, and invasion by Argentine ants leads to substantially lower post-fire recruitment of large-seeded fynbos species (Bond & Slingsby, 1984). However, it may simply avoid moist habitats on the eastern slopes of Table Mountain.

Pheidole capensis, the only other abundant native ant species that effectively disperses large-seeded proteas in the Fynbos Biome, is also known to be displaced, or eliminated, by Argentine ants (De Kock & Giliomee, 1989; Christian, 2001; Witt & Giliomee, 2004). In this study, 1545 individuals of *P. capensis* (a mean of 258 individuals per site) were collected in uninvaded fynbos, but not a single individual was collected at sites invaded by Argentine ants, an extremely negative impact of invasion (Table 5.3). *P. capensis* appears to have been displaced by Argentine ants at invaded sites, again raising concern for the conservation of large-seeded proteas in fynbos habitats that are already threatened by fire-exclusion policies and woody invasive species (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). However, *P. capensis* was not collected in pine plantation, so its absence at invaded fynbos sites could reflect historical displacement through afforestation (both invaded fynbos sites were previously under pine plantation), and perhaps not by Argentine ants alone. Ant species, such as *Meranoplus peringueyi* and *Tetramorium quadrispinosum*, which have previously been shown to coexist with Argentine ants (Luruli, 2007) are not big enough to carry large sized seeds (Christian, 2001). This could lead to altered plant species composition in fynbos communities, and the localised decline of large-seeded myrmecochorous species of proteas (such as *Leucospermum* and *Mimetes*) in Argentine ant invaded habitats. Similar reduced seed dispersal occurs in areas invaded by Argentine ants in California, compared to areas dominated by the native seed-dispersing ant *Pogonomyrmex subnitidus* (Carney *et al.*, 2003).

Although *Monomorium* sp. and *Tetramorium grassii* numbers were generally depressed in areas of Argentine ant invasion (Table 5.2), these species appear to coexist with Argentine ants elsewhere in the Western Cape (Christian, 2001; Luruli, 2007). Coexistence with invasive ants has been reported among ant species that are able to exploit different resources, use the same resources at different times, or have strong chemical defences (reviewed in Lach & Hooper-Bùi, 2010).

This study, like that of Gotelli & Arnett (2000) and many others, is only a snapshot comparison of invaded and uninvaded sites, and as such suffers from two potential shortcomings (Sanders *et al.*, 2003). Firstly, invaded and uninvaded sites may vary in some way that promotes invasive species and disadvantages native species. Differing disturbance levels could be one such case, and may apply to the uninvaded and invaded fynbos sites in this study, since both invaded sites were recovering Sandstone Fynbos, previously under pine plantation. Secondly, snapshot studies cannot determine whether invaded sites differed from uninvaded sites in native species richness and co-occurrence patterns prior to invasion. These two problems could lead to potential misinterpretation of the impacts of invasive alien species on community organisation. As a snapshot comparative study, it is not known how many of the “uninvaded” sites were previously invaded by Argentine ants. There is some evidence for a dynamic invasion front, since Argentine ants were collected from Site 9 (forest) during a pilot study in May 2008, but were absent from the samples taken there less than one year later. Argentine ants were also previously collected at Site 2 (pine plantation) by Rahinjanahary (2007), but were not found there two years later. The impacts of Argentine ant invasion may have a long-lasting effect on the native ant community, even after Argentine ants have abandoned a site.

The weak evidence for a unimodal dominance-richness relationship between Argentine ant abundance and native ant species richness (Fig. 5.3) may relate to the sampling design. Most studies describing this dominance-richness relationship use baits, which produce a heightened “momentary” dominance pattern that is not necessarily evident in the sampling methods employed in this study, since pitfall traps reflect broader assemblage level patterns (Parr, 2008). Nevertheless, the dominance-impoverishment rule (Hölldobler & Wilson, 1990) is a widely accepted theory in ant ecology, used to explain whether competition is the main structuring force in a local assemblage (Parr & Gibb, 2010). Unimodal (quadratic) dominance-richness relationships between dominant ant abundance and ant species richness at baits have previously been reported from studies in tropical savannas in Australia and Africa (Andersen, 1992; Parr *et al.*, 2005; Parr, 2008), and are thought to hold across a range of environments. In such unimodal relationships, species richness is low at low abundances of the dominant ant, and increases with increasing numbers of the dominant ant; until a point is reached beyond which species richness drops as dominance increases (Andersen, 1992). The ascending part of the curve reflects the shape of the abundance frequency distribution and increasing habitat favourability (Parr *et al.*, 2005). The descending part of the curve reflects interspecific competition, whereby species richness is decreased through competitive exclusion (Andersen,

1992; Parr *et al.*, 2005). The importance of competition in structuring ant assemblages varies with habitat (Parr, 2008). The reduced importance of competition in structuring ant assemblages, suggested by the non-significant relationships between native ant species richness and Argentine ant abundance (Fig. 5.3), may also be seen through random species co-occurrence patterns (Parr, 2008).

Ground-foraging native ant communities in the absence of invasive ants may be segregated or aggregated, depending on local conditions and the species involved. At uninvaded sites in this study, there was evidence for nonrandom co-occurrence patterns of native ants, suggesting an aggregated community (Table 5.2). This is plausible, since behaviourally dominant native ant species (such as *Anoplolepis custodiens*), which could competitively segregate the native ant community, were not collected from any uninvaded sites. Furthermore, both forest and fynbos are naturally heterogeneous habitats, so nonrandom, aggregated spatial distributions are to be expected (Hui *et al.*, 2010). The dataset of bird distributions in the Vanuata Archipelago, that was originally used to develop C-score, was also more aggregated than expected by chance (Stone & Roberts, 1992). Invasive ant species reduce native species richness, rapidly disassemble native ant communities, and alter community organisation amongst the species that persist (Sanders *et al.*, 2003). In fynbos, community association patterns were random at sites invaded by Argentine ants (Table 5.2), and this invasive alien species may be responsible for the observed community disassembly of native ants. Luruli (2007) also found altered ant community patterns with invasion: native ants were negatively associated (suggesting segregation) at uninvaded bait stations, but were significantly positively associated (suggesting aggregation) at bait stations invaded by Argentine ants in fynbos. In the eastern United States, ground-foraging native ant species co-occur less often than expected by chance (segregation), but at sites invaded by the Red imported fire ant, *Solenopsis invicta*, community structure is also random (Gotelli & Arnett, 2000). This disrupted ant community pattern in the presence of invasive ants is evident at both local and biogeographic scales.

Stone and Roberts' (1990) C-score index is considered the most appropriate null model for analysing species co-occurrence patterns, because it maintains fixed row sums, and is therefore not prone to Type I errors (false positives) (Gotelli, 2000). As such, C-score can confidently detect species pairs that do not frequently co-occur (Gotelli, 2000). C-score is also the least sensitive index to Type II errors (false negatives) and noise in the data (Gotelli, 2000). However, in assuming that all sites are equiprobable (because they are of similar size and quality), negative co-occurrence patterns may be hidden by heterogeneity among sites (Gotelli

& McCabe, 2002). C-score may also be overly conservative, because it does not take differences in abundance into account.

The functional group approach to describing ant communities was originally designed in Australia (Andersen, 1997a; Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003; Majer *et al.*, 2004). It has useful applications in other parts of the world (Andersen, 1997a), and is relevant in South Africa, because many of the common Australian ant genera also occur here (Andersen & Majer, 2004). Nevertheless, the functional group scheme has limitations for studies of community dynamics at local scales, when a detailed understanding of the impacts on individual species is needed (Andersen, 2010). Functional groups based on niche dimensions tend to be purely descriptive, even though they are based on global-scale responses of ants to environmental stress and disturbance at the genus or species-group level (Andersen, 2010). Functional group comparisons are also limited because they were designed for continental and intercontinental analyses of biogeographic patterns of ant community structure, and their responses to disturbance (Andersen, 1997a; Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003). Therefore, functional group comparisons may not always offer reliable interpretation at local scales.

Despite these various limitations, the functional group approach has exciting potential for explaining the impacts of invasive ants. In South Australia, sites invaded by Argentine ants supported greater proportions of Generalized Myrmicinae, Cold Climate Specialists and Specialised Predators (Walters, 2006). In this study, the native ant community was represented by five functional groups (Table 5.4), which in most instances decreased in mean abundance with invasion (Fig. 5.5b). Generalized Myrmicinae and Subordinate Camponotini species richness was unaffected by Argentine ant invasion, suggesting that they can co-occur, even though their numbers were depressed. Within the Generalized Myrmicinae, *Monomorium* use chemical secretions to repel attacks by Argentine ants (Holway, 1999), and *Crematogaster* have little direct interaction with Argentine ants, because they forage in different habitats (Addison & Samways, 2000; Brown, 2000). Within the Subordinate Camponotini, *Camponotus* have large body sizes, and are behaviourally submissive to Argentine ants (Andersen, 1997a; Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003). Luruli (2007) reports positive associations with Argentine ants for *Monomorium* and *Crematogaster*, and neutral associations for *Camponotus*. Walters (2006), on the other hand, reports a negative association of *Camponotus* with Argentine ants in Australia, so impacts may differ at the species level, and in different habitats.

Tropical Climate Specialists and Specialist Predators had fewer species at invaded sites, suggesting both are unable to coexist with Argentine ants. Tropical Climate Specialists, such as *Meranoplus*, *Myrmicaria* and *Tetraoponera*, all generally occur in habitats where native Dominant

Dolichoderinae are not dominant or abundant (Andersen, 1997a; Holway, 1999; Andersen, 2000). This might explain why *Meranoplus* sp. and *Myrmicaria nigra* were absent at invaded sites, but not why *Tetraponera* sp. appears to be positively affected by Argentine ant invasion in all habitats. Perhaps this is simply a limitation of the genus level based functional group approach. Luruli (2007) did not collect *Tetraponera*, so comparisons in other fynbos regions are not yet possible.

Opportunists varied in response to invasion in different habitats. This functional group was the most diverse taxonomically (three subfamilies, four genera and five species), and in foraging habits (arboreal, epigeaic and hypogaeic) represented (Table 5.4). Opportunists also ranged in their known behavioural response to Argentine ants from subordinate behaviour (*Tapinoma* and *Technomyrmex*), to coexistence through nest entrance defence (*Tetramorium*), and the potential to resist invasion (*Lepisiota*) (Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003; Matilya, 2003; Majer *et al.*, 2004; Edge *et al.*, 2008). *Tetramorium* sp. was one of only two species (together with *Tetraponera* sp.) to show a positive association with Argentine ants for all habitats combined, and *Tetramorium* sp. and *T. grassii* both showed positive associations in forest (Table 5.3). Similarly, Luruli (2007) reports a positive association of *Tetramorium* with Argentine ants, confirming that this Opportunist does coexist with Argentine ants in fynbos. *Lepisiota capensis* was one of the six species absent at invaded sites, yet was collected in appreciable numbers at five of the six uninvaded fynbos sites. *L. capensis* was collected in very low numbers (less than five individuals per site) at uninvaded forest and pine plantation sites, so is likely a fynbos specialist species. If *L. capensis* is capable of resisting invasion (Matilya, 2003; Edge *et al.*, 2008), this helps explain the absence of Argentine ant invasion in undisturbed fynbos sites.

Associations of Argentine ants and other invertebrates

Other invertebrates are affected by both the direct impacts of invasive alien ants and the resultant indirect impacts of the displacement of native ants (Holway *et al.*, 2002). Displacement of other invertebrates often leads to cascading effects on ecosystems, and disrupts ecosystem processes (Human & Gordon, 1997). However, clear impacts of invasive ants on entire invertebrate communities have seldom been reported, and were not found in this study. Neither non-ant invertebrate species richness (Fig. 5.6a), nor community composition (Fig. 5.7a) showed an impact of Argentine ant invasion. Argentine ants also have little impact on ground-dwelling invertebrate diversity in fynbos on the Cape Peninsula (Pryke & Samways, 2010). Weak community-level effects of Argentine ants on ground-dwelling arthropods have been

reported in riparian woodlands in northern California (Holway, 1998), and urban parklands in Adelaide, Australia (Walters, 2006). In all these habitats, the impacts of invasive ants may be difficult to detect, because communities were most likely shaped by native ant predation prior to invasion (Cole *et al.*, 1992). The worst impacts of invasive ants on invertebrate communities are often seen soon after invasion (Heller *et al.*, 2008). Argentine ants have been established on the Cape Peninsula for about a century (Skaife, 1961; 1962; Richardson *et al.*, 1992).

Community-level impacts of Argentine ant invasion were not clear in this study, because the impacts on the mean abundance of individual non-ant invertebrate taxa (mostly orders) differed among taxa (Table 5.6). Invertebrates that move slowly, or cannot fly, may be the most vulnerable to predation by Argentine ants (Human & Gordon, 1997).

Soft-bodied taxa are also especially vulnerable to attack by invasive ants. Several soft-bodied taxa (velvet worms, earthworms, flatworms and slugs) had lower mean abundance at invaded sites in this study. Velvet worms, however, may avoid attack by Argentine ants, because they are cryptic, spend most of their lives deep inside logs, and have slime glands for defence. The negative association of velvet worms with Argentine ants reported here may therefore be the indirect consequence of competition for food resources, since velvet worms are also predators. Collembola, despite being soft-bodied, increased in mean abundance at invaded sites – the opposite result to studies elsewhere (Human & Gordon, 1997; Rowles & O’Dowd, 2009). Cole *et al.* (1992) report higher abundance with Argentine ants, and suggest that springtails may escape ant predation by using their ability to spring, although not all species possess a springing organ. If this is the case, one might expect landhoppers (Amphipoda) to similarly escape predation by jumping clear of ant attackers. Amphipods were more abundant at sites invaded by Argentine ants in Australia (Walters & Mackay, 2003), but less abundant in this study. The eggs and larvae of most taxa (even those that are highly mobile and have hard exoskeletons as adults) are also highly vulnerable to ant predation (Bolger *et al.*, 2000).

Taxa with chemical defences and/or hard exoskeletons for protection should be less vulnerable to attack by Argentine ants (Cole *et al.*, 1992). Woodlice and millipedes have odoriferous glands, and many adopt a conglobate position, to defend themselves against attack from predators (Lawrence, 1953). Both woodlice and millipedes were positively associated with Argentine ant invasion in this study. Previous studies suggest that woodlice persist (Hoffmann & Parr, 2008), or are over-represented, at sites with invasive ants (Human & Gordon, 1997; Bolger *et al.*, 2000; Walters & Mackay, 2003). Spiders and scorpions have poison glands, scorpions and pseudoscorpions have pincers, and harvestmen employ autotomy (the ability to dispense with limbs), to defend themselves against attack from would-be predators (Lawrence, 1953).

However, these weapons may be useless against ant attackers. Even if ground-dwelling spiders are not often preyed upon, Argentine ants may interfere with spider foraging activity and compete for prey (Cole *et al.*, 1992; Human & Gordon, 1997). Therefore, ground-dwelling spiders are more liable to be negatively affected by Argentine ants than web-building species (Holway *et al.*, 2002). In most cases, arachnids were negatively associated with Argentine ant invasion, although impacts varied among taxa and habitats (Table 5.6). Spiders are also negatively affected by Argentine ant invasion in Hawaii (Cole *et al.*, 1992).

Psocoptera appear to be positively affected by Argentine ant invasion on the Cape Peninsula (Table 5.6) and elsewhere (Human & Gordon, 1997; Bolger *et al.*, 2000; Walters & Mackay, 2003; Rowles & O'Dowd, 2009). Scavengers (such as Psocoptera) may increase in abundance at invaded sites, because invasive ants are often hyper-abundant, so that there are more dead ants available for scavengers to forage on (Human & Gordon, 1997). Scavengers may also avoid direct resource competition with Argentine ants by having versatile diets (Bolger *et al.*, 2000; Walters & Mackay, 2003; Rowles & O'Dowd, 2009).

Investigations of impacts at the ordinal level may be too coarse, since behavioural and life history traits vary widely within several orders. Beetles are a prime example. Predatory beetles, such as Carabidae, may be severely negatively affected by Argentine ant invasion (Cole *et al.*, 1992), either because they compete with Argentine ants for arthropod prey, or have vulnerable soil-inhabiting larvae. Boring beetles, such as Scolytidae, should be less vulnerable to attack. Argentine ants do not appear to have an obvious negative impact on xylophagous or xylomycophagous communities in Afrotropical forest or pine plantation on the Cape Peninsula (Rahinjanahary, 2007). Body size may also influence the impacts of invasive ants on invertebrate taxa, with effects intuitively expected to be more pronounced in small species. Although not tested in this study, Rahinjanahary (2007) found that small native snails (such as *Trachycystis* sp. and *Nata* sp.) were absent at invaded forest sites on the Cape Peninsula.

Impacts on the mean abundance of individual non-ant invertebrate taxa (mostly orders) also differed among habitats for different taxa (Table 5.6). Although a few more positive (16 taxa) than negative (12) impacts were recorded in fynbos, these may largely be by chance, or reflect differences in habitat (vegetation type), rather than a consequence of ant invasion. Interestingly, more negative (17 taxa) than positive (9) impacts were recorded in pine plantation (Table 5.6), reflecting the lower mean abundance of non-ant invertebrates at invaded pine plantation sites (Fig. 5.6b). The data collected here do not provide any evidence for a synergistic impact of pine plantations acting in concert with Argentine ants (Fig. 5.7a). It is not yet clear whether, or how, Argentine ants interact with plantations or invasive stands of alien

woody plants to impact native invertebrate species richness, abundance or community composition.

Mean species richness (Fig. 5.6c) and abundance (Fig. 5.6d) of Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates was lower at sites invaded by Argentine ants. Community composition of endemic species was, however, not determined by Argentine ant invasion, either within or between forest and fynbos (Fig. 5.7b and Table 5.5). The most extreme negative impacts on endemics (Table 5.7) were recorded for habitat specialists, such as the two cockroach species restricted to fynbos, one of which (*Dipteretrum brinckae*) was absent at all invaded sites. Cockroaches as a group were also negatively affected by Argentine ant invasion (Table 5.6). Since populations of endemic invertebrates often occur naturally in low densities, the impacts of Argentine ants are usually difficult to demonstrate statistically, as was the case for endemic arthropods on Hawaii (Cole *et al.*, 1992). This may also apply to several endemic species collected in low numbers in this study. However, Cole *et al.* (1992) did show negative impacts of Argentine ants on ground-dwelling, endemic, flightless beetles. Likewise, *Bohepilissus nitidus*, a tiny Cape Peninsula endemic dung beetle, was negatively impacted by Argentine ant invasion in Afrotropical forest (Table 5.7).

Mean species richness (Fig. 5.6e) and abundance (Fig. 5.6f) of non-ant alien invertebrates was higher at sites invaded by Argentine ants in forest and fynbos, but not in pine plantation. However, these differences were not statistically significant due to high variance between sites. The community composition of non-ant alien invertebrates (Fig. 5.7c) was also not primarily determined by Argentine ant invasion, although Argentine ants do seem to have a strong influence, particularly in fynbos (Table 5.5). Most non-ant alien invertebrate species showed positive associations with invasion by Argentine ants across habitats (Table 5.8), but these impacts varied among taxa. This may suggest a common invasion susceptibility of certain sites, for various reasons, rather than an effect of Argentine ants on other alien invertebrates.

Alien slug species (except for *Limax maximus*, which was collected from one forest site only) were negatively associated with Argentine ant invasion. Similarly, Rahinjanahary (2007) recorded five alien slug species (*Arion* sp., *Deroceras* sp., *D. reticulatum*, *Limax maximus* and *Lehmanna* sp.) in higher numbers in uninvaded Afrotropical forest and pine plantation on the Cape Peninsula. Thus, Argentine ants do appear to have a negative impact on the abundance of alien slugs. Conversely, most alien snail species, including both *Oxychilus* species, appear to be positively associated with Argentine ant invaded sites. Rahinjanahary (2007) collected *Oxychilus draparnaudi* only in uninvaded forest, suggesting the opposite to the impact observed

in this study. However, since Rahinjanahary (2007) focussed collection on saproxylic communities, many litter-dwelling snails may have been under represented in his study.

Alien woodlice (*Porcellio scaber*) were positively associated with Argentine ants across habitats. Rahinjanahary (2007) also did not collect *P. scaber* in uninvaded Afrotropical forest in Newlands Forest. Cole *et al.* (1992) and Human & Gordon (1997) both report a positive association of alien woodlice with Argentine ants in invaded areas. Invasive woodlice, such as *P. scaber* and *P. laevis*, are often heavily sclerotised, affording them protection from attack. As scavengers, alien woodlice may also benefit from abundant dead ants and the remains of prey items brought to nests by foraging Argentine ants (Cole *et al.*, 1992). High abundance of alien woodlice at sites invaded by Argentine ants does not automatically imply a relationship with these invasive ants, because they are known to track disturbance (Human & Gordon, 1997).

Only one of the three alien springtail species collected in this study had higher mean abundance at sites invaded by Argentine ants. Cole *et al.* (1992) found that *Entomobrya* (probably alien) were more abundant with Argentine ants, and suggest that springtails may escape ant predation by using their ability to spring. This hypothesis does not appear to hold on the Cape Peninsula, where *Entomobrya nivalis* had lower mean abundance at invaded sites. Furthermore, *Neanura muscorum*, the only alien springtail with higher mean abundance at invaded sites, lacks a furculum, so cannot jump to escape attack.

European wasps (*Vespula germanica*) had higher mean abundance at invaded forest sites, but lower mean abundance in fynbos and pine plantation, where they were absent from invaded sites. *V. germanica* adults forage for carbohydrates in the form of nectar and honeydew (Tribe & Richardson, 1994; Kasper *et al.*, 2004), and may compete with Argentine ants for honeydew resources. Argentine ants also attack colonies of Yellowjackets (*Vespula* spp.) in California (Gambino, 1990). Their habit of constructing subterranean nests (Sackmann *et al.*, 2000; Kasper *et al.*, 2004) could therefore make them vulnerable to Argentine ant predation.

Conclusion

The comparative approach adopted here provides evidence for the displacement and impoverishment of native ground-dwelling ant communities consistent with the findings of Argentine ant invasions reported elsewhere. Clear impacts of invasive ants on entire invertebrate communities have seldom been reported, and were not found in this study. As a cautionary note, several of the impacts of Argentine ants observed in this study may be influenced by habitat heterogeneity, especially in fynbos. Individual studies may produce different results due to different durations and levels of ant invasion, the disturbance history of

sites, habitat variability, compositional differences in the original invertebrate communities, or simply due to the bias inherent in various sampling methods. Nevertheless, Argentine ant invasion on the Cape Peninsula appears to have negatively impacted native ant communities, and likely many other native invertebrates, with devastating (but often under-appreciated and overlooked) consequences for biodiversity conservation.

CHAPTER 6. IMPACTS OF ALIEN INVERTEBRATES ON NATIVE GROUND-DWELLING INVERTEBRATES ON THE CAPE PENINSULA

Introduction

The British ecologist, Charles Elton, prophetically warned of the dangers arising from invasive alien species: “The real thing is that we are living in a period of the world’s history when the mingling of thousands of kinds of organisms from different parts of the world is setting up terrific dislocations in nature. We are seeing huge changes in the natural population balance of the world.” (Elton, 1958). Invasive alien species are now widely recognised as the second greatest threat to global biodiversity, after habitat destruction (Wilcove *et al.*, 1998; Simberloff, 2001). Yet, the impacts and consequences of invasion by most invasive alien species, particularly invertebrates, remain poorly understood. In a review of the ecological affects of invasive alien insects, Kenis *et al.* (2009) report that only 72 invasive insect species had been studied worldwide, of which 54 showed evidence for ecological impacts in the field. Although the number of invasive insect species known to have an effect on biodiversity appears to be disproportionately low, this most likely reflects a lack of investigations, rather than a lack of effect, since the vast majority (over 80%) of studies conducted on invasive insects do report significant effects (Kenis *et al.*, 2009).

Social insects, such as ants and wasps, are amongst the most successful invasive organisms, because of their excellent dispersal abilities, high fecundity, long-lived colonies, large body size (in wasps), broad habitat range, social foraging behaviour, broad and flexible diets, effective predator defences and competitive abilities (Moller, 1996). These traits enable invasive social insects to overcome biotic resistance and become permanent additions to the ecological communities that they invade (Moller, 1996; D’Adamo *et al.*, 2002).

The European wasp (also known as German wasp or Yellowjacket), *Vespula germanica*, is native to Eurasia and North Africa, and has successfully invaded and established populations in the United States, Canada, Ascension Island, New Zealand, Australia, Tasmania, Chile, Argentina, and South Africa (Archer, 1998). *V. germanica* was unintentionally introduced to the Western Cape Province, South Africa, probably prior to 1970, and was first recorded on the Cape Peninsula in 1974 (Whitehead & Prins, 1975). It has established populations in relatively undisturbed natural vegetation on the Cape Peninsula (Richardson *et al.*, 1992), although these are mostly in moist localities associated with mountains, such as in dense forest on Table Mountain (Whitehead & Prins, 1975). Fynbos is considered a marginal habitat for the

establishment of colonies, as a result of low arthropod prey abundance (Tribe & Richardson, 1994). Compared to New Zealand and Tasmania (Davidson, 1987), expansion in South Africa has been very slow, despite the entire eastern coastal region being seemingly climatically suitable (Tribe & Richardson, 1994). The harsher, drier conditions on the Cape Flats (Fynbos Biome) may have prohibited range expansion beyond the Cape Peninsula (Tribe & Richardson, 1994), although in recent years this species has spread inland to Stellenbosch and as far as the Hottentots Holland mountains. Population numbers also appear to show large annual fluctuations in the Western Cape, although this trend is yet to be quantified (T. Wossler pers. comm., 2010).

European wasps have injurious effects on both native wasp species and other native arthropods. Evidence for such detrimental impacts comes from semi-urban scrubland-pastures (Harris & Oliver, 1993) and beech forests (Beggs, 2001) in New Zealand. Adult European wasps catch invertebrate prey to meet the requirements of their larvae for fresh protein (Caron & Schaefer, 1986). Diptera, Hymenoptera, Lepidoptera larvae and Araneae are the most common invertebrate prey items taken by European wasps in New Zealand (Harris & Olivier, 1993), Australia (Kasper *et al.*, 2004) and Argentina (Sackmann *et al.*, 2000). Although no equivalent dietary study has been undertaken in South Africa, the most common invertebrate prey items taken are likely to include the same taxa, since these are amongst the most commonly found in nature. This suggests that European wasps are generalist, rather than selective, predators (Sackmann *et al.*, 2000). They also compete with birds for insect food resources, effecting entire insectivorous bird communities in New Zealand (Harris, 1991; Beggs, 2001). In addition to protein prey items, European wasps also forage for water, pulp and carbohydrates (Kasper *et al.*, 2004). Adults collect wood pulp for building nests, and require carbohydrates as an energy source (Caron & Schaefer, 1986). Adults mostly feed on nectar, but also pierce soft fruits, such as grapes, pears and plums, compromising soft-fruit and wine industries. By removing large quantities of honeydew (a carbohydrate source), European wasps may alter nutrient cycling by decreasing the flow of carbon to soil microorganisms (Beggs, 2001). Removal of honeydew may have additional indirect effects on the ecosystem, and on other invertebrate taxa, such as ants, that also utilize this resource.

Molluscs have received more attention than most other non-insect invertebrate taxa, most often for their notorious economic impacts. Six molluscs, including the terrestrial Giant African snail (*Achatina fulica*) and Rosy wolf snail (*Euglandina rosea*), are among the *100 of the world's worst invasive alien species* (Lowe *et al.*, 2000). Despite severe impacts for agriculture, a long history of invasion (over 150 years for several species), and establishment in relatively

undisturbed natural areas (Herbert, 2010), alien terrestrial molluscs have received inadequate attention in the South African literature, even in reviews discussing alien invertebrates (Lach *et al.*, 2002). Recently, Herbert (2010) inventoried the South African alien terrestrial mollusc fauna, listing 34 introduced species, of which 28 have established. Most terrestrial mollusc introductions have taken place in Cape Town, because it is a major port of entry, has a long European colonial history (dating back to the 1600s), and a temperate, Mediterranean climate. Twenty alien mollusc species have been collected in Cape Town – more than all other localities combined. Of the 34 introduced terrestrial mollusc species in South Africa, 25 have also invaded southern Australia, which shares a similar Mediterranean climate, and 19 have invaded New Zealand (Smith, 1992; Barker, 1999; Herbert, 2010). This resemblance is not surprising, as both Australia and New Zealand share a comparable colonial history with South Africa.

Since most millipedes are phytophages, saprophages or detritivores, alien millipedes are unlikely to pose a serious threat to native biodiversity and ecosystems (Baker, 1985; Stoev *et al.*, 2010). Some millipedes have, however, attained pest status in their invaded habitats. The Portuguese millipede (*Ommatoiulus moreleti*), native to the Iberian Peninsula, was introduced to Australia in 1953, where it quickly reached “plague proportions” and invaded houses in spring and autumn (McKillup *et al.*, 1988; Stoev *et al.*, 2010). *O. moreleti* numbers typically explode in newly-invaded areas in Australia, then decrease over time, possibly due to food shortages (Baker, 1985), or control by a native rhabditid nematode (McKillup *et al.*, 1988). These “boom and bust” dynamics of invasive alien species have also been reported for terrestrial mammals, aquatic plants and marine invertebrates (reviewed in Parker *et al.*, 1999). *O. moreleti* is also considered a nuisance in South Africa (Lawrence, 1984).

Alien woodlice are largely confined to urban environments, where they often become dominant detritus feeders (Cochard *et al.*, 2010). This ability to rapidly build up large numbers, and exploit resources more successfully than native species (Sutton, 1972), means that successful invasions of relatively natural habitats potentially lead to disturbance and biotic homogenisation (Cochard *et al.*, 2010). *Armadillidium vulgare*, *Porcellionides pruinosus*, and *Porcellio scaber* are considered “synanthropically cosmopolitan” woodlice species (Cochard *et al.*, 2010). The Rough woodlouse (*P. scaber*), which originates from southwestern Europe, has colonised the rest of Europe and many other parts of the world, including Africa (Slabber & Chown, 2002). It has been recognised as an invasive alien species in South Africa for many decades (Lawrence, 1953), and spread from here to Marion Island, probably arriving in building supplies from Cape Town in April 2001 (Slabber & Chown, 2002).

Impacts of the vast majority of alien species have not yet been quantified (Parker *et al.*, 1999). Nevertheless, it is generally assumed that most invasions do have ecological impacts on the invaded ecosystem (Ricciardi & Kipp, 2008), and that these impacts span a skewed continuum in which the most adverse impacts are comparatively rare, *i.e.* the upper tail of a log-normal distribution (Williamson & Fitter, 1996). The aim of this study is to profile and investigate the impacts of non-ant alien invertebrate species on native ground-dwelling invertebrate species richness, abundance, and community composition in Table Mountain National Park. Invasion by alien invertebrates could potentially lead to the biotic homogenisation of native invertebrate assemblages. Therefore, the identification of potentially high-impact (*sensu* Ricciardi & Kipp, 2008) alien invaders that may be implicated in substantial declines of native invertebrate populations and homogenisation of assemblages is of scientific interest and urgent conservation concern. Habitat alteration, such as afforestation, may also facilitate such invasions, and this is investigated by contrasting alien invertebrate communities in natural and transformed vegetation on the Cape Peninsula.

Methods

Study sites and collecting methods

Most studies attempting to quantify the impacts of alien species are correlative, either comparing one site before and after invasion, or different sites where the alien species is present or absent (Parker *et al.*, 1999). This study compared sites differing in their degree of invasion by non-ant alien invertebrates, in three habitats across one spring-summer season. Refer to Chapter 2 for the location of the sites sampled and the collecting methods used in Western Cape Afrotemperate Forest (n = 8 sites), Peninsula Sandstone and Granite Fynbos (n = 8 sites) and pine plantation (n = 7 sites; Site 11 omitted) in Table Mountain National Park. For each of the 23 sites, data from the replicates (10 leaf litter, 10 soil, 10 pitfall trap, 10 sugar-baited ant trap and two decayed log samples) were pooled to obtain a single abundance or species richness value per site. Refer to Appendix A for a full list of species collected in forest, fynbos and pine plantation.

Analyses

The region of origin, South African distribution, habitats invaded locally, and date of first record of introduction in South Africa was summarised for alien invertebrates other than ants. Each alien species was compared to its corresponding native taxon only (*e.g.* Portuguese millipede

compared to native millipede species), because impacts due to competition or predation (cannibalism in the case of some molluscs) were expected to be most evident among taxonomically related species. Non-parametric analyses were used for all alien species collected, because residuals of data were not normally distributed for most alien species, and abundance and incidence were generally quite low. Spearman rank correlations were calculated for all habitats combined, and for each habitat, to establish whether the abundance of each alien species was significantly associated with the species richness and abundance of native species from the alien's associated taxon. Mean (\pm SD) native species richness and abundance were calculated between sites across habitats where each alien was present and absent, and then compared using Mann-Whitney *U* tests, to establish whether observed impacts were statistically significant. Several alien species were collected at one site only, so comparisons of mean native species richness and abundance were not made for these species. All species richness and abundance comparisons were performed in STATISTICA version 9 (StatSoft, Inc., 2009).

A triangular matrix of Bray-Curtis similarity of fourth-root transformed community composition between sites was used to map the interrelationships of invertebrate communities for each alien invertebrate species' corresponding taxon in cluster analysis, using group average clustering, and in ordination by non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), in PRIMER version 6 (Clarke & Gorley, 2006). Data were fourth-root transformed to down-weight highly abundant species. Sites with no corresponding native species collected in that taxon were omitted. The community composition of each taxon was related to normalised environmental variables using BEST, BIOENV (Clarke & Ainsworth, 1993) in PRIMER. Three nominal (area, vegetation type and alien presence-absence) and five continuous (latitude, longitude, elevation, soil pH and soil moisture) variables were tested. The same Bray-Curtis similarity matrices for each alien's taxon equivalent were used for pairwise analysis of similarity (ANOSIM), to test the null hypothesis of no difference in community composition between sites where each alien species was present or absent. ANOSIM was applied to the rank similarity matrix using a permutation procedure (999 permutations) (Clarke & Green, 1988), to test for statistical significance of the cluster patterns identified in the ordinations.

Results

Eighteen alien species (excluding Argentine ants, the impacts of which are addressed in Chapter 5) were collected in forest, fynbos and pine plantation. The invasion history and currently known South African distribution of alien invertebrate species was summarised from

the literature (Table 6.1). All alien molluscs identified were European in origin, with most species from the Mediterranean region. Most alien mollusc species have been established in South Africa for many decades, and several have distributions beyond the Western Cape Province. The Portuguese millipede, Rough woodlouse, springtails and European wasp all have a Palearctic (mostly European) native range, and most have a synanthropically cosmopolitan distribution. The South African distribution and habitats invaded by alien invertebrates (other than ants and molluscs) have not yet been adequately studied.

The native invertebrate assemblage, against which the impacts of these alien taxa were compared, consisted of eight mollusc, nine millipede, six woodlice, 16 springtail and 107 wasp species. Across habitats, there was no correlation between the abundance of most alien invertebrate species and either the species richness (Table 6.2) or abundance (Table 6.3) of native species in each alien's corresponding taxon. Significant, positive Spearman rank correlations between alien abundance and equivalent native species richness in all habitats combined were found for *Deroceras panormitanum*, *Ommatoiulus moreleti*, and *Neanura muscorum* (Table 6.2). Significant, positive correlations between alien and equivalent native taxa abundances in all habitats combined were found for *D. panormitanum*, *Cornu aspersum*, *O. moreleti*, and *Vespula germanica* (Table 6.3). In Afrotropical forest, wasp species richness was significantly positively correlated with *V. germanica* abundance (Table 6.2), and snail abundance was significantly positively correlated with *Vitrea contracta* abundance (Table 6.3). In fynbos, snail species richness was significantly positively correlated with *D. panormitanum* abundance (Table 6.2). In pine plantation, millipede species richness and abundance were significantly positively correlated with *O. moreleti* abundance, and wasp abundance was significantly correlated with *V. germanica* abundance. Both native snail species richness (Table 6.2) and abundance (Table 6.3) were negatively (although not significantly) correlated with the abundance of the carnivorous alien snail *Oxychilus draparnaudi*.

Table 6.1. Invasion history of alien invertebrates collected, excluding those lacking positive species-level determinations.

Species	Common names	Native range	South African distribution	South African habitats invaded	Date introduced	References
<i>Arion hortensis</i> aggregate [#]	Garden arion, Férussac's orange-soled slug, Yellow-soled slug	Western Europe	Cape Town and Stellenbosch	Exotic pine plantations	Prior to 1939	Herbert, 2010
<i>Deroceras panormitanum</i> *	Brown field slug, Long-necked field slug	Probably Mediterranean	Western Cape, Eastern Cape and Gauteng	Suburban and rural gardens, forest on Table Mountain and near Somerset East	Prior to 1963	Herbert, 2010
<i>Lehmannia valentiana</i>	Three-banded garden slug, Valencia slug	Iberian Peninsula	Western Cape, Eastern Cape, Northern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal and Kruger National Park	Suburban and rural gardens, and natural habitats in Cape Town	Prior to 1961	Herbert, 2010
<i>Limax maximus</i>	Giant garden slug, Great grey slug, Tiger slug, Leopard slug, Spotted garden slug	Western and Central Europe, and perhaps North Africa	Western Cape	Cape Town: forest near suburbia and on Table Mountain	Prior to 1898	Herbert, 2010
<i>Cochlicopa cf. lubricella</i>	Slender moss snail	Holarctic	Western Cape, Eastern Cape, Gauteng and North West Province	Primarily in gardens, Kirstenbosch and Knysna forest	Prior to 1965	Herbert, 2010
<i>Vitrea contracta</i>	Milky crystal snail, Contracted glass snail	Much of Europe, Ukraine, Turkey, Caucasia, Middle East and North Africa	East facing slopes of Table Mountain and Cape Peninsula	East-facing slopes on Cape Peninsula, and probably more widely distributed in Cape Town and surrounds	Prior to 2004, probably not recent	Herbert, 2010
<i>Comu aspersum</i>	Brown garden snail, Common garden snail	Western Europe and the Mediterranean	All nine provinces, synanthropic and not widespread in natural habitats	Most widespread alien terrestrial snail in South Africa	Prior to 1878, probably much earlier	Herbert, 2010

C. Uys, PhD (Jan 2011). Chapter 6. Other alien invertebrate impacts

Species	Common names	Native range	South African distribution	South African habitats invaded	Date introduced	References
<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	Common chrysalis snail	Western Europe and the Mediterranean	Cape Town, Cape Peninsula and Worcester	Gardens, vineyards and exotic conifer plantations	Prior to 1879	Herbert, 2010
<i>Oxychilus draparnaudi</i> *	Draparnaud's glass snail, Dark-bodied glass snail	Western Europe and the Mediterranean	Western Cape, Eastern Cape, Northern Cape and Gauteng	Spread into native habitats and abundant on Table Mountain above Newlands and Kirstenbosch	Circa 1908, or earlier	Herbert, 2010
<i>Ommatoiulus moreleti</i>	Portuguese millipede	Iberian Peninsula	Cape Town and the South Western Cape	Gardens, pine plantations and Afrotropical forest	Prior to 1984, probably much earlier	Lawrence, 1984; Hamer, 1998
<i>Porcellio scaber</i>	Rough woodlouse	South Western Europe	Cape Town, and probably widespread across the country	Gardens and Afrotropical forest	Prior to 1885	Barnard, 1932; Lawrence, 1953; Slabber & Chown, 2002
<i>Entomobrya nivalis</i>	springtail	Palaearctic	Not adequately studied	Not known	Prior to 1934	Womersley, 1934; Paclt, 1956.
<i>Neanura muscorum</i>	springtail	Palaearctic	Not adequately studied	Not known	Prior to 1968	Coates, 1968
<i>Tomocerus minor</i>	springtail	Palaearctic	Not previously recorded	Not previously recorded	Post 1956	Womersley, 1934; Paclt, 1956; E. Bernard pers. comm., 2010
<i>Vespula germanica</i> *	European wasp, German wasp, Yellowjacket	Eurasia and North Africa	Cape Peninsula, Stellenbosch, Somerset West, to Hottentots-Holland Mountains	Afrotropical forest, Fynbos, orchards and vineyards	Prior to 1970	Whitehead & Prins, 1975; Richardson <i>et al.</i> , 1992; Tribe & Richardson, 1994; T. Wossler pers. comm., 2010

Arion hortensis aggregate is a member of an unresolved species complex

* Cannibal or carnivorous species

Table 6.2. Spearman rank correlations between the abundance of each alien invertebrate species collected and the species richness of native species from the corresponding taxon to which the alien belongs. Values in bold are significant ($p < 0.05$).

Alien	Corresponding taxon	All habitats		Forest		Fynbos		Pine	
		<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Arion hortensis</i> aggregate	Snails	0.319	0.137	-0.236	0.573	0.619	0.102	0.316	0.446
<i>Deroceras panormitanum</i>	Snails	0.866	<0.001	0.326	0.431	0.761	0.028	0.667	0.071
<i>Lehmannia valentiana</i>	Snails	0.159	0.470	-0.481	0.227	-0.354	0.390	-0.016	0.970
<i>Limax maximus</i>	Snails	0.050	0.822	-0.514	0.193	*	*	*	*
<i>Cochlicopa</i> sp.	Snails	0.348	0.104	0.514	0.193	*	*	*	*
<i>Cochlicopa</i> cf. <i>lubricella</i>	Snails	0.051	0.816	0.514	0.193	*	*	0.135	0.750
<i>Vitrea contracta</i>	Snails	0.156	0.476	0.776	0.023	*	*	0.206	0.624
<i>Cornu aspersum</i>	Snails	0.332	0.122	-0.221	0.599	*	*	*	*
cf. <i>Punctum</i> sp.	Snails	-0.239	0.271	-0.514	0.193	*	*	0.498	0.209
<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	Snails	-0.066	0.764	*	*	*	*	0.381	0.352
<i>Oxychilus draparnaudi</i>	Snails	0.023	0.916	-0.226	0.590	-0.354	0.390	-0.432	0.285
<i>Oxychilus</i> sp.	Snails	-0.264	0.224	-0.421	0.299	-0.535	0.172	-0.571	0.139
<i>Ommatoiulus moreleti</i>	Millipedes	0.536	0.008	0.159	0.708	0.201	0.632	0.712	0.048
<i>Porcellio scaber</i>	Woodlice	0.261	0.230	0.085	0.841	0.276	0.508	0.201	0.633
<i>Entomobrya nivalis</i>	Springtails	0.365	0.087	*	*	*	*	0.607	0.111
<i>Neanura muscorum</i>	Springtails	0.545	0.007	0.514	0.193	1	0.105	0.475	0.234
<i>Tomocerus minor</i>	Springtails	0.083	0.707	*	*	0.176	0.677	*	*
<i>Vespula germanica</i>	Wasps	0.388	0.068	0.607	0.110	0.383	0.349	0.201	0.634

* Alien species not collected in that habitat

Table 6.3. Spearman rank correlations between the abundance of each alien invertebrate species collected and the abundance of native species from the corresponding taxon to which the alien belongs. Values in bold are significant ($p < 0.05$).

Alien	Corresponding taxon	All habitats		Forest		Fynbos		Pine	
		<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Arion hortensis</i> aggregate	Snails	0.317	0.141	-0.467	0.243	0.484	0.224	0.454	0.259
<i>Deroceras panormitanum</i>	Snails	0.768	<0.001	0.218	0.604	0.697	0.054	0.286	0.493
<i>Lehmannia valentiana</i>	Snails	0.232	0.286	-0.217	0.606	-0.351	0.393	0.142	0.738
<i>Limax maximus</i>	Snails	0.115	0.601	-0.412	0.310	*	*	*	*
<i>Cochlicopa</i> sp.	Snails	0.214	0.327	-0.082	0.846	*	*	*	*
<i>Cochlicopa</i> cf. <i>lubricella</i>	Snails	-0.016	0.944	-0.082	0.846	*	*	0.297	0.475
<i>Vitrea contracta</i>	Snails	0.022	0.919	-0.265	0.526	*	*	0.429	0.289
<i>Cornu aspersum</i>	Snails	0.475	0.022	0.385	0.346	*	*	*	*
cf. <i>Punctum</i> sp.	Snails	-0.302	0.162	-0.412	0.310	*	*	0.498	0.209
<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	Snails	-0.033	0.882	*	*	*	*	0.571	0.139
<i>Oxychilus draparnaudi</i>	Snails	0.072	0.744	-0.109	0.797	-0.351	0.393	-0.432	0.285
<i>Oxychilus</i> sp.	Snails	-0.156	0.478	0.069	0.872	-0.531	0.175	-0.571	0.139
<i>Ommatoiulus moreleti</i>	Millipedes	0.655	<0.001	0.371	0.365	0.043	0.919	0.826	0.011
<i>Porcellio scaber</i>	Woodlice	0.328	0.127	0.530	0.176	0.416	0.306	0.291	0.485
<i>Entomobrya nivalis</i>	Springtails	0.289	0.180	*	*	*	*	0.577	0.134
<i>Neanura muscorum</i>	Springtails	0.239	0.272	0.577	0.134	0	0.615	0.312	0.452
<i>Tomocerus minor</i>	Springtails	-0.225	0.302	*	*	-0.249	0.552	*	*
<i>Vespula germanica</i>	Wasps	0.554	0.006	0.768	0.026	0.659	0.076	0.764	0.027

* Alien species not collected in that habitat

Mean species richness of native invertebrates in the taxon to which each alien belongs was generally higher at sites where the alien species occurred (Table 6.4). However, this positive association of native species with an alien species was only statistically significant for *D. panormitanum* (Mann-Whitney *U* test: $Z = 3.939$, $p < 0.001$) and *N. muscorum* ($Z = -2.433$, $p = 0.009$) (Table 6.4).

Table 6.4. Mean native taxon species richness compared between sites where each alien species was present and absent. Values in bold are significant ($p < 0.05$).

Alien	Mean \pm SD		Mann-Whitney <i>U</i>	
	present	absent	<i>Z</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Arion hortensis</i> aggregate	1.9 \pm 1.6	0	1.582	0.126
<i>Derocheras panormitanum</i>	3.2 \pm 1.1	0.4 \pm 0.7	3.939	<0.001
<i>Lehmannia valentiana</i>	2.2 \pm 1.7	1.4 \pm 1.6	1.071	0.277
<i>Limax maximus</i>	*	*	*	*
<i>Cochlicopa</i> sp.	*	*	*	*
<i>Cochlicopa</i> cf. <i>lubricella</i>	2.0 \pm 2.6	1.7 \pm 1.6	-0.046	0.966
<i>Vitrea contracta</i>	2.4 \pm 2.4	1.6 \pm 1.4	-0.671	0.491
<i>Cornu aspersum</i>	3.0 \pm 1.0	1.6 \pm 1.7	1.461	0.139
cf. <i>Punctum</i> sp.	1.0 \pm 1.2	2.1 \pm 1.8	-1.236	0.222
<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	*	*	*	*
<i>Oxychilus draparnaudi</i>	2.0 \pm 2.1	1.7 \pm 1.6	0.186	0.857
<i>Oxychilus</i> sp.	1.1 \pm 1.5	2.0 \pm 1.7	-1.069	0.278
<i>Ommatoiulus moreleti</i>	**	**	**	**
<i>Porcellio scaber</i>	1.3 \pm 1.6	0.6 \pm 1.1	1.033	0.302
<i>Entomobrya nivalis</i>	*	*	*	*
<i>Neanura muscorum</i>	5.8 \pm 2.2	3.2 \pm 1.1	-2.433	0.009
<i>Tomocerus minor</i>	*	*	*	*
<i>Vespula germanica</i>	15.9 \pm 10.4	8.6 \pm 5.7	-1.928	0.055

* Present at one site only

** Present at all sites sampled

Mean abundance of taxonomic equivalent native invertebrates was also generally higher at sites where the alien species was present (Table 6.5). However, this positive association of native abundance with the presence of an alien species was only statistically significant for *D.*

panormitanum (Mann-Whitney U test: $Z = 3.631$, $p < 0.001$), *C. aspersum* ($Z = 2.100$, $p = 0.026$) and *V. germanica* ($Z = -2.741$, $p = 0.004$) (Table 6.5).

Table 6.5. Mean native taxon abundance compared between sites where alien species were present and absent. Values in bold are significant ($p < 0.05$).

Alien	Mean \pm SD		Mann Whitney U	
	present	absent	Z	p
<i>Arion hortensis</i> aggr.	18.1 \pm 34.4	0	1.582	0.126
<i>Deroceras panormitanum</i>	32.9 \pm 43.0	1.6 \pm 3.0	3.631	<0.001
<i>Lehmannia valentiana</i>	28.0 \pm 48.3	9.2 \pm 16.7	1.354	0.179
<i>Limax maximus</i>	*	*	*	*
<i>Cochlicopa</i> sp.	*	*	*	*
<i>Cochlicopa</i> cf. <i>lubricella</i>	8.7 \pm 12.5	17.8 \pm 35.3	0.137	0.898
<i>Vitrea contracta</i>	9.8 \pm 10.8	18.4 \pm 37.2	-0.112	0.914
<i>Cornu aspersum</i>	64.7 \pm 77.2	9.4 \pm 15.1	2.100	0.026
cf. <i>Punctum</i> sp.	2.4 \pm 3.6	22.8 \pm 38.4	-1.570	0.118
<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	*	*	*	*
<i>Oxychilus draparnaudi</i>	18.6 \pm 25.0	16.0 \pm 35.8	0.335	0.745
<i>Oxychilus</i> sp.	14.1 \pm 22.9	17.6 \pm 37.5	-0.535	0.579
<i>Ommatoiulus moreleti</i>	20.2 \pm 32.2	0	**	**
<i>Porcellio scaber</i>	13.1 \pm 21.0	7.5 \pm 18.5	1.001	0.317
<i>Entomobrya nivalis</i>	*	*	*	*
<i>Neanura muscorum</i>	286.3 \pm 443.0	48.6 \pm 60.8	-1.217	0.218
<i>Tomocerus minor</i>	*	*	*	*
<i>Vesputula germanica</i>	60.4 \pm 38.4	17.4 \pm 15.2	-2.741	0.004

* Present at one site only

** Present at all sites sampled

The community composition of native snails, millipedes, woodlice, springtails and wasps was not structured according to the presence or absence of alien species. In all cluster analyses and MDS ordinations, sites did not cluster according to alien presence-absence, or a combination of alien presence-absence with habitat, so were not presented. BIOENV confirmed that alien presence-absence was not an important explanatory variable for community composition for any of the taxa to which these alien species belong. Of the alien mollusc species collected in sufficient abundance and present at more than one, but not at all, sites (to

enable presence-absence comparisons), *D. panormitanum* was the only species that showed some association with native snail community composition. *D. panormitanum*, in combination with four other environmental variables, was identified as the strongest driver of snail community composition ($p = 0.584$). Eight of the top ten BEST, BIOENV results also included *D. panormitanum* presence-absence as an explanatory variable for native snail community composition. *O. moreleti* was present at all sites sampled, so the approach of comparing the native millipede community composition of sites based on alien presence-absence was not possible. Seven of the top ten BEST, BIOENV results included *N. muscorum* presence-absence as an explanatory variable for native springtail community composition, although in all cases the correlations were weak ($p \leq 0.261$). *E. nivalis* and *T. minor* were each collected at a single site, so the approach of comparing native springtail community composition of sites based on alien presence-absence was not considered meaningful. Not one of the top ten BEST, BIOENV results included *P. scaber* or *V. germanica* as a driver of woodlice and wasp community composition respectively.

Despite BIOENV results identifying *D. panormitanum* as a potential explanatory variable for snail community composition, ANOSIM showed that native snail community composition was not significantly different between sites where *D. panormitanum* was present and absent in each habitat. There was also no significant difference in snail community composition based on the presence-absence of the other alien molluscs. Springtail community composition compared between the presence and absence of *N. muscorum* was significantly different ($R = 0.727$, $p = 0.048$) in pine plantation, but not in forest or fynbos. *P. scaber* and *V. germanica* showed no significant influence on woodlice and wasp community composition respectively.

Discussion

The potential ecological impacts of most alien invertebrates have not been studied locally. This applies to alien molluscs, despite several species showing negative economic impacts as crop pests (Herbert, 2010). Among the alien molluscs recorded in this study, *Oxychilus draparnaudi*, *Arion hortensis*, *Deroceras panormitanum* and *Limax maximus* have also invaded native forest in New Zealand (Mahlfeld, 2000), where their ecological impacts have been studied. In the Waipipi Scenic Reserve in New Zealand, native snail species richness and abundance have decreased substantially since *A. hortensis* and *Cochlicopa lubrica* were first reported in 1981 (Mahlfeld, 2000 and references therein). Both have invaded South Africa and were collected in this study. Comparisons of impacts based on presence-absence were not made for *A.*

hortensis, because it was collected at 21 of the 23 sites sampled; being absent at only one fynbos and one pine plantation site. No mollusc species (either alien or native) was collected at Site 26 (Sandstone Fynbos), where *A. hortensis* was not collected. This site was quite dry, exposed and had sparse, dry leaf litter, so may not be suitable for molluscs. Only one individual each of two other alien molluscs (*Oxychilus* sp. and cf. *Punctum* sp.) were collected at Site 31 (pine plantation), where *A. hortensis* was not collected. For some unknown reason, this pine plantation site also appears to be unsuitable for molluscs. Other native forest litter taxa, including millipedes and woodlice, were likewise poorly represented at this site.

Although the slug *D. panormitanum* feeds primarily on living and dead plant material, it is aggressive towards other individuals, bites readily and is cannibalistic, even when food is abundant (Herbert, 2010). Other species of *Deroceras* are also known to eat small, soft-bodied invertebrates (Herbert, 2010). It is pertinent to note that no native slug species were collected. In this study, *D. panormitanum* abundance was significantly positively correlated with both native snail species richness and abundance across habitats. Mean native snail species richness and abundance were also significantly higher at sites where *D. panormitanum* was present. While this suggests that *D. panormitanum* does not negatively impact the native mollusc fauna, it more likely implies that certain sites and habitats (namely Afrotropical forest) are more attractive to molluscs, whether native or alien. *D. panormitanum* was collected at all eight Afrotropical forest sites, both Granite Fynbos sites in Kirstenbosch, and one pine plantation site in Newlands. A significant correlation of *D. panormitanum* abundance with native snail species richness in fynbos may be related to site-specific or vegetation compositional differences between Granite and Sandstone Fynbos. Alien molluscs may further impact the native fauna by outcompeting them for moisture-retaining spaces under rocks, logs and in ground surface depressions; especially during the summer dry season (Mahlfeld, 2000).

Oxychilus draparnaudi readily eats other land snails in captivity, and appears to have reduced the numbers and diversity of large native terrestrial snail species in Iowa, more likely as a consequence of carnivory than competition for food (Frest & Rhodes, 1982). *O. draparnaudi* has also been identified as the most serious introduced predator of native terrestrial snails in New Zealand, threatening at least two rare species with extinction (Mahlfeld, 2000). In South Africa, the native dwarf cannibal snails, *Nata tarachodes* and *N. vernicosa*, prey on smaller native snails (such as *Trachycystis* spp.) and on earthworms (Herbert & Kilburn, 2004). This suggests that the native snail fauna of the Cape Peninsula is not entirely naïve to, and may be able to tolerate or avoid, alien cannibal snails such as *O. draparnaudi*. No significant correlation of native snail species with alien abundance, or difference in mean native snail species richness

or abundance, was found for *O. draparnaudi*. The observed reductions in native snail species richness and abundance where this species occurred in each habitat may well prove statistically significant with a larger sample size and parametric statistics. *O. draparnaudi* is relatively abundant in natural habitats around Cape Town (Herbert, 2010), so numbers and potential impact should be monitored carefully over time. There are enough examples around the world of the devastating impacts of successfully introduced molluscs to take this threat seriously (Mahlfeld, 2000).

If the Portuguese millipede, *Ommatoiulus moreleti*, does have an impact on the Cape Peninsula, juliform (worm-like) native millipede species are probably worst affected, because they are morphologically and behaviourally most similar to Portuguese millipedes. However, in light of the significant positive correlations, millipedes may simply congregate in suitable microhabitats, with little or no interaction between species. Positive correlations were found between the abundance of the Portuguese millipede and both native millipede species richness and abundance across habitats. Similarly, native millipede species richness and abundance were significantly correlated with *O. moreleti* abundance in pine plantation. *O. moreleti* was collected at all 23 sites sampled, and therefore, comparisons of potential impacts between sites based on presence-absence cannot be made. Portuguese millipedes were also far more abundant than any native millipede, and 2.6 times more abundant than all native millipedes combined across sites. Portuguese millipedes typically quickly reach high abundance at invaded sites (Baker, 1985; McKillup *et al.*, 1988; Stoev *et al.*, 2010). It is unknown whether native rhabditid nematodes or other parasites are able to keep Portuguese millipede numbers in check locally, as is the case in Australia (McKillup *et al.*, 1988).

Collembola are often the most abundant terrestrial arthropods, many species have cosmopolitan distributions, and several have become invasive (Zettel, 2010). *Entomobrya nivalis* and *Tomocerus minor* were collected at a single site each, so the impacts of these springtails on the native fauna could not be calculated. *T. minor* had not previously been recorded in South Africa, so it may either have only recently invaded the Cape Peninsula, or have simply never been collected. It is known from a single pine plantation (Site 15, Cecilia). *Neanura muscorum* was collected at four sites, and showed a significant correlation with native springtail richness ($R = 0.545$, $p = 0.007$), and higher mean native species richness occurred at sites where it was present ($Z = -2.433$, $p = 0.009$). These springtails are not known or expected to have serious detrimental impacts on native springtails, or on other invertebrates (Coates, 1968). They feed mainly on decaying organic matter and associated microorganisms, and are therefore not considered pests (Zettel, 2010). However, as detritivores, alien springtails may

have significant effects on decomposition processes (Greenslade, 2002), and thereby indirectly impact other detritivores. Reports of springtails becoming invasive and displacing native species do come from isolated microhabitats on sub-Antarctic inlands (e.g. Greenslade, 2002), but not as yet from mainland Europe (Zettel, 2010), or other continents.

The abundance of European wasps (*Vespa germanica*) was significantly positively correlated with the abundance of native wasps across habitats. Similarly, *V. germanica* abundance was significantly correlated with native wasp abundance in pine plantation. Mean abundance of native wasps was also significantly higher at sites where European wasps were present across habitats. These positive correlations between European wasps and native wasps could reflect selection for Lepidoptera larvae-rich areas, since many wasps are predators or parasites of Lepidoptera. Sackmann *et al.* (2008) experimentally showed that *V. germanica* did not affect arthropod assemblages in north-west Patagonia, Argentina. Although their finding contradicts previous studies elsewhere, Sackmann *et al.* (2008) suggest that the low population levels of European wasp relative to other invaded regions might explain these findings. European wasp numbers collected in this study were also very low. The reported impacts on arthropods are more severe when European wasps switch from small annual colonies to large perennial colonies, as has been demonstrated in Hawaii (Wilson *et al.*, 2009). The climatically marginal conditions of fynbos (Tribe & Richardson, 1994) may have prevented European wasps from switching to large perennial colonies on the Cape Peninsula. However, this colony switch cannot be ruled out in the future, should European wasps undergo range expansion during wetter periods to invade the moister east coast of South Africa.

Hymenoptera was not the most frequent order taken as prey items by European wasps near Hamilton in New Zealand (Harris & Oliver, 1993), and this may also be the case on the Cape Peninsula. If European wasps indiscriminately catch any wasps as prey, then significantly lower species richness and abundance might be expected where European wasps are present. However, many of the wasp species collected in this study were tiny, cryptic, litter parasitoids, reducing the value of this comparison. Kasper *et al.* (2004) found that Honeybees (*Apis mellifera*) comprise 95% of Hymenoptera prey taken by European wasps in Australia. Only one Honeybee individual was collected by the sampling methods employed in this study. In addition to preying upon Honeybee adults, European wasps also forage for nectar from flowers and honey from the hives of Honeybees (Sackmann *et al.*, 2000), thereby exacerbating their pernicious impacts. Kasper *et al.* (2004) also report that Diptera (mostly Calliphoridae and Muscidae) comprised the largest proportion of identifiable prey items taken by European wasps. Fewer than ten calliphorid fly individuals and no muscids were collected here, but this likely

reflects inherent bias in the collecting methods used, which were chosen to target ground-dwelling taxa.

The community composition of native snails, millipedes, woodlice, springtails and wasps does not appear to have been influenced by the presence-absence of an alien species in each respective invertebrate taxon. This is not surprising, in light of finding no statistically significant negative impacts on the species richness and abundance of native taxa. In Europe, no ecological impacts have been documented for alien spiders (Nentwig & Kobelt, 2010), myriapods (Stoev *et al.*, 2010), terrestrial crustaceans (Cochard *et al.*, 2010), springtails (Zettel, 2010), bugs (Heteroptera) (Rabitsch, 2010), or flies (Skuhrová *et al.*, 2010). Burger *et al.* (2001) found no negative association between native and alien spiders, and concluded that alien spiders do not impact native ground-dwelling spiders in California. The literature supports evidence that some invasions in fact increase species diversity (Hulme, 2003). However, correlation does not imply causation. The most productive habitats may support both the highest proportion of alien species and the highest species richness of native species. This would explain correlated native and alien spider diversity in California (Burger *et al.*, 2001), and may be the most parsimonious interpretation of the observed positive correlations between various alien species and their taxonomic equivalent. For most taxa, vegetation type and other environmental variables, but not the presence of an alien species, explains the cluster patterns observed in the MDS ordinations. The ubiquitous positive correlation between native species decline and invasive species dominance may thus be an indirect consequence of habitat modification, or disturbance driving native species loss (Didham *et al.*, 2005).

It remains a scientific curiosity why some alien species persist for decades in low numbers at a given location without spreading (Nentwig & Josefsson, 2010). In this study, *Limax maximus* appears to be such a curiosity, having persisted in a single patch of Afrotemperate forest for over a century (Herbert, 2010). Most of these alien species were introduced to South Africa many decades ago (Table 6.1). Fifteen of these alien species were first recorded in South Africa prior to 1970, and the three recorded more recently (*O. moreleti*, *V. contracta* and *T. minor*) were probably misidentified, not collected, or not described in the literature until recently. A long naturalised residency time on the Cape Peninsula can also be generally expected, since all 18 alien species have a mostly European origin, promoting their establishment in the temperate, Mediterranean climate of the Western Cape. There are various possible reasons for the low numbers of several of the alien species collected. Some aliens may still be in the lag phase of invasion, showing little or no increase in abundance or spread (Elton, 1958; Crooks,

1995; Aikio *et al.*, 2010). Considerable lag phases, often lasting several decades and sometimes over a century, are commonly reported during invasions (Hulme, 2003).

The 'Ten's Rule' (Williamson, 1993; Williamson & Fitter, 1996) has been widely invoked to explain why most alien species fail to become invasive (Hulme, 2003; Ricciardi & Kipp, 2008). It is based on the probability that on average 10% of introduced species will escape into the wild, 10% of these escapees will become naturalised (*i.e.* established), and 10% of naturalised species will become pests and cause ecological damage or change (Williamson & Fitter, 1996). Thus, there is a very low probability that the alien species collected are all high-impact invaders (Williamson & Fitter, 1996; Ricciardi & Kipp, 2008).

No quantified, systematic survey of terrestrial alien invertebrates has been conducted on the Cape Peninsula, prior to this study. Consequently, no analyses of temporal trends in alien abundance and distribution are possible. Alien species may be under control by native species, as in the case of Portuguese millipede, which is controlled by a native rhabditid nematode in Australia (McKillup *et al.*, 1988). Alien species (*e.g.* European wasp) may show annual variation in population size, with the annual impact on the native fauna fluctuating accordingly. This study was not designed to provide evidence for lag phases, control by native species, or annual fluctuations in alien populations. Nevertheless, logic dictates that the impact of an alien species is proportional to its abundance (Parker *et al.*, 1999). If the ecological impacts of alien species are in fact distributed along a skewed continuum, then the 18 alien invertebrate species discussed here do not fall within the upper tail of a log-normal distribution describing the most severe ecological impacts (Williamson & Fitter, 1996; Ricciardi & Kipp, 2008).

Conclusion

Finding an alien species in a non-invasive state does not of course mean that it cannot become invasive and cause high ecological impact in the future (Nentwig & Josefsson, 2010). Climate change, for example, could enable currently innocuous aliens to become invasive and spread rapidly (Walther *et al.*, 2009; Nentwig & Josefsson, 2010). Thus, a precautionary approach is necessary in light of the apparent lack of impact of these 18 alien species, especially given the high levels of local endemism on the Cape Peninsula (Picker & Samways, 1996). The potential for future invasions by other alien species also cannot be ruled out, and is heightened by increasing globalisation, international trade, and associated human-assisted transportation of species.

CHAPTER 7. ANTS AS BIOINDICATORS OF RESTORATION PROGRESS FOLLOWING CLEAR-FELLING OF PINE PLANTATIONS IN A MEDITERRANEAN-TYPE ECOSYSTEM

Introduction

Inventory and monitoring are two separate tasks with different goals. Inventory, or biodiversity assessment, aims to document, as fully as possible, the taxonomic and ecological diversity of all or part of the biota of an area (Kremen *et al.*, 1993; Basset *et al.*, 2009) and can hence be accomplished with a single set of samples. By comparison, biological monitoring aims to document population changes over time, using repeat sampling (Noss, 1990; Basset *et al.*, 2009). The goal of biological monitoring is to distinguish between human-induced disturbance and natural fluctuations from a baseline state (Andersen, 1997b; 1999). This goal necessitates monitoring control sites in 'pristine' habitats, in addition to sites subject to disturbance (Kremen *et al.*, 1993). Well-designed inventories can thus provide the obligatory baseline data for monitoring (Noss, 1990; Rohr *et al.*, 2007).

The value of, and necessity for, inclusion of invertebrates in biodiversity monitoring programmes has been widely promoted (Kremen *et al.*, 1993; Andersen *et al.*, 2004; Rohr *et al.*, 2007). Invertebrates can respond rapidly to environmental changes, because they have short generation times compared to vertebrates or trees (Kremen *et al.*, 1993). Small body size, low vagility, poor dispersal ability, and specific habitat requirements also mean that ground-dwelling invertebrates show stronger patterns of spatial turnover than vertebrates and flowering plants (Ferrier *et al.*, 1999). Ground-dwelling invertebrates also show greater site fidelity than most vertebrates (Kremen *et al.*, 1993; Oliver & Beattie, 1996). Furthermore, invertebrates generally greatly outnumber vertebrates in abundance, species richness, and higher taxa diversity, often by orders of magnitude (Kitching, 1999; New, 1999b). This high biomass and diversity both reduces the size, and hence environmental impact, of samples and affords statistical rigor in both inventory and monitoring of invertebrates.

Neither inventory nor monitoring of invertebrates can be exhaustive, due to the difficulty of adequately identifying the full range of taxa present (Kremen *et al.*, 1993). The challenges of generating invertebrate species inventories should not be underestimated (Engelbrecht, 2010). Monitoring programmes accordingly rely on indicator taxa that can be identified, given available resources and personnel, and that respond quickly to environmental change, in ways that are easily measured or observed (Kremen *et al.*, 1993). Invertebrates are usually more difficult to

survey than plants, so their use as indicators can only be justified if they perform better than plants, and provide additional (fine-scale) information (Andersen & Sparling, 1997).

For most invertebrate groups, (1) a large proportion of species has not been described or discovered, (2) the distribution patterns of species are poorly or unknown, (3) too few (if any) specialists are available to identify specimens, (4) sampling protocols are not adequately standardised, and (5) knowledge of responses to environmental change is limited, and often hypothetical, or extrapolated from a few case studies (New, 1999b). Terrestrial invertebrates fall into three broad categories of value as tools for monitoring: well-known, catch-up and black hole taxa (New, 1999a; 1999b). Well-known taxa have a long history of interest, most species are described, their biology is broadly understood, and patterns of distribution are reasonably well documented. Examples of well-known taxa include butterflies and dragonflies. Catch-up taxa include many groups of invertebrates for which there is a fair level of knowledge of taxonomy, biology and distribution. With some focussed attention, these catch-up taxa could be elevated to 'well-known' status for conservation value. The distinction between well-known and catch-up taxa differs among regions. Ants, for example, may be considered well-known taxa in mesic Australia, but catch-up taxa in temperate Australia and other parts of the world. By comparison, black hole taxa have very poorly understood taxonomy, biology, and distribution. Consequently, solid ecological interpretation of black hole taxa is difficult or impossible, and these taxa have little proven value as indicators. Black hole taxa, such as nematodes, are best ignored for conservation purposes, especially in light of the limited resources available for invertebrate conservation. Taxa with a high proportion of rare and low abundance species similarly have limited use or relevance for monitoring, due to the low probability of finding them (New, 1999b).

There is often much confusion over what is being indicated (Andersen, 1999), because indicators have been applied in a variety of contexts (*e.g.* Noss, 1990). These contexts include indication of habitat destruction, contamination, modification, and rehabilitation, together with vegetation succession, climate change, and species diversity (McGeoch, 1998). It is therefore essential to state precisely what the indicator taxa selected are intended to indicate, especially when contexts are related to management actions (Engelbrecht, 2010). Terrestrial invertebrates used to assess general ecological change after disturbances have been referred to as 'ecological indicators' for their ability to demonstrate the impacts of environmental change on biota (McGeoch, 1998). Ecological indicators differ from biological indicators (McGeoch, 1998), that are used as surrogates of biodiversity.

Even when there is agreement on what to indicate, it is difficult to know which indicator species to choose (Simberloff, 1998), because there is no single indicator for biodiversity (Duelli

& Obrist, 2003). Choice of indicator based on statements of faith about one's favourite invertebrate group is not enough to validate their use (Andersen, 1999). Demonstration of a chosen indicator's response to disturbance is also not sufficient to validate its reliability as an indicator. Ecological indicators must also genuinely reflect broad ecological change (Andersen, 1999). It is advantageous, although not required, for ecological indicator taxa to have presence-absence patterns that are positively linearly correlated with the species richness of a larger group of organisms (Duelli & Obrist, 2003; Fleishman *et al.*, 2005; Rohr *et al.*, 2007). While correlation or cross-taxon congruency is the goal of biodiversity indicators, it is most effective within taxonomic groups. Cross-taxon congruency should be approached with caution, because the correlation of species richness between pairs of taxa varies taxonomically and geographically (Su *et al.*, 2004; Bilton *et al.*, 2006). Using higher taxa offers better congruency for invertebrates than does cross-taxon comparison (Lovell *et al.*, 2007). However, no single taxon sufficiently indicates the diversity of others, even in well-studied regions (such as tropical forest) and considering a range of taxa (birds, butterflies, flying beetles, canopy beetles, canopy ants, leaf litter ants, termites and soil nematodes) (Lawton *et al.*, 1998). To avoid misinterpretation, true congruency should only be inferred when p -values are greater than 0.75 (Lovell *et al.*, 2007).

Hammond's (1994) 'shopping basket' approach to indicator selection is widely recommended (*e.g.* McGeoch, 1998) and supported with case studies (*e.g.* Kotze & Samways, 1999). The 'shopping basket' approach selects a set of taxa that each represents the response of taxonomically or functionally closely related taxa, and thereby adequately represents the community as a whole. Widening the taxonomic focus to families or orders has the advantage of unintentionally including representative species in a range of guilds (Basset *et al.*, 2004). This facilitates wider interpretation than is possible for single species indicators. Recommending individual species as indicators has limitations, because those species are seldom suitable outside of the system in which they were tested (Gollan *et al.*, 2010). Nevertheless, individual species can have advantages as indicators in specific cases, acting as 'umbrella' or 'flagship' species, when resources and knowledge needed for more comprehensive analyses are limited.

The use of morphospecies (*sensu* Oliver & Beattie, 1996) as indicators has limitations for the interpretation of data (Majer, 2009) and is no longer recommended. Morphospecies may have some use for identifying general trends (Snyder & Hendrix, 2008), but can be misleading, especially when males, females and juveniles of individual species are morphologically different, and can hence be classified as separate morphospecies (Slotow & Hamer, 2000). Furthermore, morphospecies have little value as ecological indicators for monitoring, because they overlook

potentially important information, such as region of origin (Gollan *et al.*, 2010). Failure to identify alien, and especially invasive, species could also misguide management decisions and unknowingly promote non-native species (Gollan *et al.*, 2010). Alien invertebrates can be used as a measure of restoration success or failure, because the proportion of alien invertebrates is likely to differ between restored and undisturbed sites (Longcore, 2003). Therefore, taxa that can only be identified to morphospecies, and for which the alien fauna is not well known, would not make appropriate or responsible indicators.

Ants have been widely used as indicator species, because they are often highly sensitive to disturbance and habitat transformation (Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003). In particular, ants have a long history of use as indicators of restoration success in the mining industry in Australia (e.g. Andersen, 1997b), and more recently in South Africa (Majer & De Kock, 1992; van Hamburg *et al.*, 2004). Ant communities respond to disturbance through loss of diversity, and through changes in species composition, interspecific interactions, trophic interactions with honeydew-producing hemipterans and ant-plants, and ant-provided ecosystem services, such as seed dispersal (Philpott *et al.*, 2010). Ant assemblages can be reliably assessed on both taxonomic (genera are easily identified) and functional levels (New, 2000). Their functional importance and ease of sampling makes ants effective and efficient taxa for assessment and monitoring in land management (Andersen, 2010). The functional group approach (Andersen, 1995; 1997a) offers a predictive understanding of the responses of ant communities to disturbance (Andersen *et al.*, 2004). The relative proportion of ant functional groups is highly dependent on the structural diversity of vegetation, predominant land-use, and disturbance regime (New, 2000). Functional groups have proved especially useful for assessment of habitat disturbance (Andersen, 1997a) and plantation forestry (Pik *et al.*, 1999).

As with any bioindicator, the use of ants as indicators relies on the assumption that changes in ant communities reflect ecosystem changes (Andersen, 1999; 2010). This assumption appears to be valid, at least for most relevant studies on ants (Andersen, 2010). However, ants may have limited predictive indicator value when small scale heterogeneity is high, as in grassland ecosystems in Victoria, Australia (New, 2000). In such cases, ants may not be sufficiently sensitive to floristic change to be used as the only indicators for monitoring environmental change. The choice of indicator taxa depends on the monitoring goals set.

Ants and other invertebrates show potential as ecological indicators of restoration progress. Restoration often relies on the assumption that the native fauna associated with a habitat will return as the natural vegetation is re-established (Longcore, 2003; Gratton & Denno, 2005; Majer, 2009; Babin-Fenske & Anand, 2010). This assumption is seldom verified, despite

the importance of the re-establishment of trophic interactions among organisms in restored habitats (Gratton & Denno, 2006). The presence of organisms is not sufficient to demonstrate that they adequately perform ecosystem functions in restored habitats (Majer, 2009). Trophic interactions should be monitored explicitly, because they are vital to our understanding of how ecosystems recover (Gratton & Denno, 2006). Different taxa colonise disturbed sites at different rates (Dunn, 2004). In tropical rainforest restoration, for example, invertebrate herbivores and detritivores recover much faster than predators (Jansen, 1997). This trend relates to different levels of taxa in the food chain, and is therefore probably widespread across habitats. This trend can also be used as a measure of restoration progress. However, there is a distinct paucity of studies on terrestrial invertebrates in the restoration literature. For example, a review of the first 14 years of *Restoration Ecology* revealed that of the 845 papers published, a meagre 12.4% had vertebrates or invertebrates as the main focus (Majer, 2009). Few generalities have been deduced on the use of invertebrates in the restoration process.

The species identity of fauna that return to sites undergoing restoration is important. On mined dunes in Maputaland, South Africa, the dung beetle fauna is dominated by widespread species, whereas natural dune forest that has not been mined supports a high proportion of localised endemic dung beetle species (Davis *et al.*, 2002). While the absence of endemic species at rehabilitated sites is expected, this has implications for biodiversity conservation, and highlights the danger in using species richness as the sole measure of restoration success. For ants and birds in tropical forests, the recovery of species composition takes much longer than the recovery of species richness (Dunn, 2004). This finding is probably broadly applicable to most terrestrial invertebrate taxa in most habitats.

To measure restoration progress, an assessment of the resultant species assemblage is needed (Brewer & Menzel, 2009). Some knowledge of reference condition and at least one extant reference site are advantageous. Restored sites should ideally be compared against a number of reference sites to encompass historically relevant environmental variation. This may not always be possible, or practical, since appropriate reference sites may be extremely rare or no longer exist. Attention should also be paid to off-site species that expanded their distribution into the areas now being restored, but that were not part of the original reference community. Regionally rare off-site species may be negatively affected by restoration efforts, which is of particular concern in biodiversity hotspots.

The Cape Peninsula is renowned for its exceptional diversity and endemism, with 158 endemic angiosperm (Helme & Trinder-Smith, 2006) and at least 111 endemic invertebrate (Picker & Samways, 1996) species currently recorded. The greatest threat to biodiversity on the

Cape Peninsula comes from increasing alien plant invasions (Richardson *et al.*, 1996), which are predicted to replace at least 30% of the remaining natural vegetation over the next two decades (Rouget *et al.*, 2003). Removal of commercial pine plantations is akin to clearing invasive alien stands, because pines were originally planted into pristine fynbos (Holmes *et al.*, 2000). Pine plantations also act as the source for many of the alien plant invasions threatening biodiversity on the Cape Peninsula (Richardson *et al.*, 1996). The spread of invasive alien trees from commercial plantations into adjacent native vegetation threatens conservation areas (Armstrong *et al.*, 1998), and offers strong motivation for the removal of these old plantations.

Pine plantations on the Cape Peninsula were first established in the 1880s (Cowling *et al.*, 1996; Richardson & Higgins, 1998). Commercial plantations were established in the fynbos surrounding forest patches, but rarely in areas cleared of evergreen native forest (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006). Therefore, restoration after clear-felling pine plantations should be aimed towards fynbos, not forest, communities. Today, plantations on the eastern slopes of the Table Mountain range are in Peninsula Granite Fynbos, because Peninsula Sandstone Fynbos was too unproductive to sustain plantations (T. Rebelo pers. comm., 2010). Very few patches of intact Peninsula Granite Fynbos remain to act as source populations of plants and invertebrates colonising clear-felled patches. Sandstone Fynbos, rather than Granite Fynbos, surrounds most plantations and clear-felled stands on the eastern slopes. Therefore, restoration of the majority of clear-felled pine stands back to the exact original vegetation type is unlikely, and sites may never return to strictly Peninsula Granite Fynbos communities. To add to this dilemma, invertebrate community composition (at least of the litter fauna) appears to differ between Granite and Sandstone Fynbos (refer to previous chapters). Regardless of origin, native fynbos invertebrates should, however, be functionally similar enough to maintain ecosystem processes, such as seed dispersal, litter decomposition and nutrient recycling in these restored areas. The re-establishment of these key ecosystem processes is central to most restoration projects (Holmes & Richardson, 1999).

A structurally and functionally representative fynbos plant community can recover from the soil seed-bank alone, following alien clearance and fire in recently-invaded mountain fynbos (Holmes & Marais, 2000). Serotinous proteoid shrubs and other species lacking soil storage of seeds are generally the only species absent in seed-bank restored communities (Holmes, 2002). Fynbos seed-banks are able to survive for over 25 years under stands of alien *Acacia* on the Cape Peninsula, but are severely reduced in both density and species richness (Holmes & Cowling, 1997; Holmes, 2002). By comparison, fynbos seed-banks under pine plantations on the Cape Peninsula are unlikely to still survive, because these plantations have a much longer

planting history, sometimes exceeding 100 years, than the invasive *Acacia* stands studied. These commercial pine plantations have also undergone several planting rotations, further compromising viable, dormant seeds. Most fynbos species have short seed dispersal distances, so natural recovery of vegetation through colonisation from surrounding fynbos patches may take several fire cycles (Holmes & Richardson, 1999), translating to several decades.

Local extinction of many fynbos plant species has been reported following invasion by pine (Richardson & van Wilgen, 1986; Richardson *et al.*, 1989). Most fynbos species are unable to withstand shading under pine, although some native geophytes, including *Ornithogalum* and *Moraea*, do persist (Adamson, 1927). This is yet another reason to remove pine plantations in fynbos, so as to minimise and eventually eliminate propagule pressure. Pines have a tendency to form dense thickets, and often out-compete fynbos shrubs in areas recovering from fire (Richardson *et al.*, 1994). Most pine seedlings establish in the first two years after fire in fynbos, when native plant cover is low (Richardson & Cowling, 1992). This may also be the case in clear-felled pine, where pine seedlings are among the first plant species to establish (C. Uys pers. obs.). This also implies that the success of restoration depends on follow-up removal of invasive alien plants, especially pine seedlings, within the first few years after clear-felling.

Terrestrial invertebrates have not been identified or tested as bioindicators in fynbos, although they have been used as indicators of restoration success in other Mediterranean-type vegetation, such as coastal sage scrub in southern California (Longcore, 2003). The aim of this study is to address the lack of data on the recovery of ground-dwelling invertebrates after alien pine removal in fynbos. This study also attempts to identify and test suitable potential ground-dwelling invertebrate taxa for use as ecological indicators for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos. Considering the many taxonomic challenges associated with terrestrial invertebrates, monitoring programmes should focus on adult stages of reasonably well-collected species (Basset *et al.*, 2009), preferably well-known taxa (New, 1999a; 1999b). Bioindicator use should follow a basic two-step process: initial identification, followed by testing the potential indicator taxa (McGeoch, 1998; McGeoch *et al.*, 2002). Guidelines for developing effective and efficient monitoring programmes for invertebrates need to be tested with case studies (*e.g.* Rohr *et al.*, 2007). Ideally, case studies should adopt both coarse- and fine-filter approaches. Monitoring invasive alien species is one such fine-filter approach (Noss, 1990).

Methods

Study sites and collecting methods

Ecological indicator taxa were selected from the ground-dwelling invertebrates collected in three habitats over one spring-summer season. Refer to Chapter 2 for location of sites sampled and collecting methods used in Western Cape Afrotemperate Forest (n = 8 sites), Peninsula Sandstone and Granite Fynbos (n = 8 sites) and pine plantation (n = 7 sites; Site 11 omitted) in Table Mountain National Park, on the Cape Peninsula. For each of the 23 sites, data from the replicates (10 leaf litter, 10 soil, 10 pitfall trap, 10 sugar-baited ant trap, and two decayed log samples) were pooled to obtain a single abundance, or species richness, value per site. Refer to Appendix A for a list of the 670 species collected in forest, fynbos and pine plantation.

Eight additional sites in clear-felled pine plantation were sampled at the same time, in the same areas, and following the same collecting procedures adopted in forest, fynbos and pine plantation. Refer to Chapter 2 for clear-felled site locations and to Appendix A for a list of the 309 species collected there. Clear-felled sites spanned a chronosequence from recently felled (less than one year before sampling) to older felled (over five years since felling) sites (Fig. 7.1). These clear-felled sites were used to test the suitability of identified indicator taxa. Verification tests of potential indicators should ideally be conducted on an independent data set, either collected in a different area, or at a different time (McGeoch, 1998; McGeoch *et al.*, 2002). However, this is not always possible, and depends on the nature of the disturbance. The plantations surrounding Table Mountain National Park targeted for clear-felling by 2025 are in Cecilia and Tokai Plantations. Therefore, a case study on these eastern slopes is appropriate for testing the ecological indicators selected for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos.

Analyses

It is impractical to use all invertebrate taxa as ecological indicators for monitoring restoration progress. Therefore, a stepwise approach to indicator selection was adopted. First, taxa were omitted if they were considered incidental catches in this study, because they had extremely low species richness and abundance, or were not ground-dwelling in nature. This step eliminated Hymenoptera (bees only), Thysanura, Neuroptera, Mantodea, Phasmatodea, and Thysanoptera from contention as suitable ecological indicators. The remaining ground-dwelling invertebrate taxa were scored using seven criteria that would render them suitable, or unsuitable, as potential indicator taxa. Each taxon was given a final score, calculated as the sum of scores for each of the seven criteria against which taxa were assessed. Final scores could range from zero (most suitable) to 14 (worst choice or most unsuitable). Taxa were considered unsuitable ecological indicators if they are poorly known regionally, lack taxonomic expertise, are difficult to identify to species level, have either very low or very high species richness, occur in low

abundance, are difficult to sample, and/or have few species unique to fynbos (low habitat fidelity). An additional set of criteria for selecting ecological indicators was compiled from the literature. The most suitable potential taxa were subjected to these new criteria to assess current local taxonomic knowledge on a globally relevant scale for monitoring restoration following disturbance.

Figure 7.1. Chronosequence of fynbos restoration: (a) mature pine plantation, (b) recently clear-felled, (c) over two years since clear-felling, (d) over five years since clear-felling, (e) recovering Sandstone Fynbos and (f) undisturbed Sandstone Fynbos. Photographs taken during sampling.

In addition to the coarse-filter approach of using higher taxa as indicators, a fine-filter approach of monitoring individual species is often recommended, because species may offer more reliable and predictable responses to habitat change (disturbance, restoration, etc.). Species with the highest percentage contributions to the separation of habitats were identified

using SIMPER (similarity percentage of species contributions) analysis (Clarke & Warwick, 2001). SIMPER was calculated from a triangular matrix of Bray-Curtis similarity of $\log_e(x + 1)$ transformed community composition between sites, with a 90% cut-off for low contributions, in PRIMER version 6 (Clarke & Gorley, 2006). The ten species that contributed the most to (a) the percentage similarity of fynbos sites, (b) the dissimilarity between fynbos and forest, and (c) the dissimilarity between fynbos and pine plantation, were considered as potentially suitable indicator species. These species were also used to confirm the choice of higher taxa selected as ecological indicators for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos.

Baseline data on the species richness of all 728 invertebrate species (58 of which were unique to clear-felled pine) were assessed for the eight clear-felled sites, together with the 23 other sites sampled. Species-accumulation curves for the observed species richness of forest, fynbos, pine plantation and clear-felled pine were calculated using S_{obs} Mao Tau sample-based rarefaction curves, randomised 50 times in EstimateS version 8 (Colwell, 2006). Estimated species richness based on abundance (ACE and Chao 1) and incidence (ICE and Chao 2) was also calculated for each habitat in EstimateS. The coverage-based species richness estimators, ACE (abundance-based coverage estimator) and ICE (incidence-based coverage estimator) recognise the contribution of rare (less than 10 individuals) species (Magurran, 2004). Chao's classic species richness estimators, like coverage estimators, are non-parametric and provide a minimum estimate of species richness, with the assumption of homogeneity amongst samples (Magurran, 2004). Mean species richness per site was compared among habitats using a Kruskal-Wallis (ANOVA by ranks) test in STATISTICA version 9 (StatSoft, Inc., 2009), because data were not normally distributed (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test: $p < 0.001$).

Baseline data on the community composition of all 728 invertebrate species were also assessed for the eight clear-felled sites, together with the 23 other sites sampled. A Bray-Curtis similarity matrix of log transformed data was used to map the interrelationships of invertebrate communities in cluster analysis, using group average clustering, and in ordination by non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), in PRIMER.

The indicator taxon selected (ants) was verified by testing community composition and functional group response to clear-felling. Bray-Curtis similarity matrices of log transformed abundance data were used to verify ants as the selected indicator taxon in cluster analysis, using group average clustering, and in ordination by non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), in PRIMER. Functional groups were assigned based on Andersen (1997a) (refer to Chapter 5). The potential ecological indicator species identified were tested using SIMPER analysis, calculated from a Bray-Curtis similarity matrix of log transformed ant community composition

between sites, with a 90% cut-off for low contributions, in PRIMER. For the selected ecological indicator species to prove suitable, they should have the highest percentage contribution to the dissimilarity between clear-felled pine and pine plantation, because they were indicative of fynbos. Suitable indicator species should also be most abundant at the clear-felled sites with the best progress towards restoration (*i.e.* most similar to fynbos reference sites).

Results

Indicator selection

Of the 92 109 individual invertebrates from 670 species collected in forest, fynbos and pine plantation, 27 higher taxa (mostly orders) were collected in sufficient numbers to be considered representative of the ground-dwelling invertebrate community, rather than as incidental catches. Nine additional families from diverse orders (Araneae, Orthoptera, Hemiptera and Coleoptera) were included in this assessment, because they were considered relatively well studied locally. Cockroaches and ants were identified as the most suitable potential ecological indicator taxa for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos (Table 7.1). Assassin bugs (Reduviidae), ground beetles (Carabidae), darkling beetles (Tenebrionidae), springtails, all beetles (Coleoptera), bugs, crickets, snails, millipedes, centipedes, and spiders also showed potential as ecological indicators in fynbos (Table 7.1). Ants performed better than cockroaches when subjected to a list of criteria commonly applied to ecological indicator taxa selection for monitoring (Table 7.2).

Table 7.1. Criteria for selection or exclusion of invertebrate taxa considered suitable ecological indicators in fynbos. For all criteria, a zero score is the most suitable. Taxa with the lowest final scores are considered most suitable as potential ecological indicators for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos.

Taxon	Taxonomic handicap¹	Estimated species richness in fynbos²	General abundance in fynbos³	Ease of sampling⁴	Species richness in the fynbos sites sampled⁵	Total abundance in the fynbos sites sampled⁶	Habitat fidelity in the sites sampled⁷	Final score
Tricladida (flatworms)	3	1 (low)	2 (low)	2 (low)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	2 (very low)	13
Pseudoscorpiones (pseudoscorpions)	3	1 (high)	2 (low)	2 (low)	1 (too low)	0	2 (very low)	11
Isopoda (woodlice)	3	1 (high)	2 (low)	1 (medium)	1 (too low)	0	2 (very low)	10
Archaeognatha (bristletails)	1 (identification)	1 (low)	2 (low)	2 (low)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	0	9
Haplotaxida (earthworms)	2 (specialist, identification)	0 (medium)	1 (medium)	2 (low)	1 (unidentified)	2 (very low)	1 (unknown)	9
Migidae (trapdoor spiders)	0	1 (low)	2 (low)	2 (low)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	1 (low)	9
Onychophora (velvet worms)	1 (identification)	1 (low)	2 (low)	2 (low)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	0	9
Hymenoptera (wasps)	1 (identification)	1 (high)	0 (high)	1 (medium)	2 (too high)	1 (low)	2 (very low)	8
Lepidoptera (moths)	2 (specialist, identification)	1 (high)	0 (high)	2 (low)	1 (unidentified)	1 (low)	1 (unknown)	8
Opiliones (harvestmen)	1 (specialist)	0 (medium)	2 (low)	0 (high)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	2 (very low)	8
Psocoptera (psocids)	2 (poorly known, identification)	0 (medium)	2 (low)	1 (medium)	0	1 (low)	2 (very low)	8
Acari (mites)	3	1 (high)	0 (high)	1 (medium)	0	0	2 (very low)	7

Taxon	Taxonomic handicap¹	Estimated species richness in fynbos²	General abundance in fynbos³	Ease of sampling⁴	Species richness in the fynbos sites sampled⁵	Total abundance in the fynbos sites sampled⁶	Habitat fidelity in the sites sampled⁷	Final score
Amphipoda (landhoppers)	0	1 (low)	1 (medium)	0 (high)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	2 (very low)	7
Anostomatidae (king crickets)	0	0 (medium)	2 (low)	1 (medium)	1 (too low)	1 (low)	2 (very low)	7
Dermaptera (earwigs)	2 (poorly known, identification)	0 (medium)	2 (low)	2 (low)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	1 (low)	7
Diptera (flies)	3	1 (high)	0 (high)	1 (medium)	1 (too high)	0	1 (low)	7
Gastropoda (slugs)	0	1 (low)	2 (low)	0 (high)	1 (too low)	1 (low)	2 (very low)	7
Orthoptera (grasshoppers etc.)	2 (specialist, identification)	1 (low)	1 (medium)	1 (medium)	0	0	2 (very low)	7
Scarabaeidae (dung beetles)	0	1 (low)	2 (low)	0 (high)	1 (too low)	1 (low)	2 (very low)	7
Scorpiones (scorpions)	0	1 (low)	2 (low)	1 (medium)	1 (too low)	0	2 (very low)	7
Solifugae (sun-spiders)	0	0 (medium)	2 (low)	2 (low)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	0	7
Stenopelmatidae (sand crickets)	0	0 (medium)	2 (low)	2 (low)	1 (too low)	2 (very low)	0	7
Araneae (spiders)	1 (identification)	1 (high)	1 (medium)	1 (medium)	2 (far too high)	0	0	6
Chilopoda (centipedes)	0	0 (medium)	2 (low)	1 (medium)	0	1 (low)	2 (very low)	6
Diplopoda (millipedes)	1 (identification)	0 (medium)	2 (low)	0 (high)	0	1 (low)	2 (very low)	6
Gastropoda (snails)	0	0 (medium)	2 (low)	0 (high)	1 (too low)	1 (low)	2 (very low)	6
Gryllidae (crickets)	1 (poorly known)	0 (medium)	1 (medium)	1 (medium)	1 (too low)	0	2 (very low)	6

Taxon	Taxonomic handicap¹	Estimated species richness in fynbos²	General abundance in fynbos³	Ease of sampling⁴	Species richness in the fynbos sites sampled⁵	Total abundance in the fynbos sites sampled⁶	Habitat fidelity in the sites sampled⁷	Final score
Hemiptera (all bugs)	2 (specialist, identification)	1 (high)	0 (high)	1 (medium)	1 (too high)	1 (low)	0	6
Coleoptera (all beetles)	1 (identification)	1 (high)	0 (high)	0 (high)	2 (far too high)	0	2 (very low)	5
Collembola (springtails)	2 (poorly known, identification)	0 (medium)	0 (high)	1 (medium)	0	1 (low)	2 (very low)	5
Tenebrionidae (darkling beetles)	1 (specialist)	0 (medium)	2 (low)	0 (high)	0	0	2 (very low)	5
Carabidae (ground beetles)	0	0 (medium)	2 (low)	0 (high)	0	1 (low)	1 (low)	4
Reduviidae (assassin bugs)	0	0 (medium)	2 (low)	1 (medium)	1 (too low)	0	0	4
Hymenoptera (ants)	0	1 (high)	0 (high)	0 (high)	0	0	2 (very low)	3
Blattodea (cockroaches)	0	1 (high)	0 (high)	0 (high)	0	0	0	1

¹ Calculated as the sum of three criteria: poorly known regionally, lack of specialists identified/available, and species level identification challenging.

² Taxa with either very low or very high species richness in fynbos throughout the region considered unsuitable indicators, based on expert opinion (M. Picker).

³ Taxa with either very low or very high abundance in fynbos throughout the region considered unsuitable indicators, based on expert opinion (M. Picker).

⁴ Refers to practicality of collecting methods required and adequate representation in samples. Rare or difficult to find taxa are considered unsuitable indicators.

⁵ Based on data collected in this study and scored as: 1 (too low) if ≤ 5 species, 1 (too high) if > 25 species, and 2 (far too high) if > 100 species.

⁶ Based on data collected in this study and scored as: low if $< \frac{1}{2}$ total abundance collected in forest, and very low if < 10 individuals collected.

⁷ Based on data collected in this study and scored as: low if most/all species collected in forest and fynbos, and very low if most/all species in all three habitats.

Table 7.2. Criteria for using terrestrial invertebrates as ecological indicators for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos following disturbance (clear-felling pine) on the Cape Peninsula.

Suitability criteria	Cockroaches	Ants
Species level identification possible ^{3,4 *}	Species list in prep.	Unpublished species list available
Distribution, richness and abundance known ^{3,4 *}	Yes	Yes
Well known taxonomy and life history ^{2,4 *}	Yes	Yes
Sampling and processing practicality ^{2,3,5 *}	Fairly high	High
High ecological or habitat fidelity ^{4 *}	Certain species	Certain species
Sampling and monitoring methods published and used frequently in monitoring ⁵	Not used frequently	Pitfall traps and bait cards
Baseline data on biology available ²	Limited	Fairly good
Functional importance in ecosystems ³	Decomposition	Wide range
Sensitivity to environmental change ^{1,3}	Poorly known	Well documented
Distinguish between natural population fluctuations and human induced disturbance ^{1,2,3}	Requires further study	Functional group predictions possible
Sampled individuals expendable (won't hinder restoration progress) ²	Yes – few rare species	Yes – most species in large colonies
Representative of related and unrelated taxa ^{2,3}	Requires further study	Demonstrated elsewhere
Potential for collaboration between researchers and protected area managers ⁵	Limited: taxonomists overseas	High: local expertise and interest
Species of special (conservation) concern: IUCN Red List, endemic or other significance ⁵	Cape Peninsula endemics	Invasive alien species
Cost efficient (time, funds and personnel) ^{1,2}	Maybe	Yes

¹ Noss, 1990

² McGeoch, 1998

³ Andersen, 1999

⁴ Summerville *et al.*, 2004

⁵ McGeoch *et al.*, in press

* Assessed in Table 7.1

Forest, fynbos and pine plantations could be distinguished according to their native invertebrate community composition – a finding necessary to ensure the reliable interpretation of ecological indicators of restoration progress. The average dissimilarity among fynbos sites

was 67.67%, between fynbos and forest 76.79%, and between fynbos and pine plantation 73.44%, based on SIMPER analysis. The cumulative percentage contribution of the top ten invertebrate species to the similarity of fynbos sites was 38.93%, to the separation (dissimilarity) of fynbos and forest 11.34%, and fynbos and pine plantation 13.73% (Table 7.3). Six of the top ten species accounting for the similarity among fynbos sites were ants (Table 7.3). Similarly, six ant species were among the top ten species separating fynbos and forest, and eight ant species were among the top ten species separating fynbos and pine plantation. The most important ant species contributing to the separation of habitats were *Lepisiota capensis*, *Crematogaster* sp., and *Camponotus* sp. 2 (*maculatus* group), all of which were more abundant in fynbos than in forest and pine plantation, and thus good indicators of the fynbos ant community. One cockroach species (*Temnopteryx phalerata*) was among the top ten species in fynbos, but no cockroaches were among the top ten species separating fynbos from forest or pine plantation. Several other species were considered unsuitable indicator species, because they were not identified even to genus level (Mogoplistidae, Aphididae and Opiliones), and/or their higher taxa were considered unsuitable ecological indicators in fynbos (Haplotaxida and Amphipoda: refer to scores assigned in Table 7.1).

Table 7.3. Top ten species contributing to the separation of invertebrate communities in different habitats, identified from SIMPER analysis, and used to identify potentially suitable ecological indicator species for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos. Alien species omitted.

Habitat	Higher taxa	Species	Cum. %
Fynbos	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Tetramorium grassii</i>	5.36
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 2 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	10.10
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Monomorium</i> sp.	14.24
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Lepisiota capensis</i>	18.11
	Oligochaeta, Haplotaxida	sp.	21.76
	Orthoptera, Mogoplistidae	sp.	25.41
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Technomyrmex pallipes</i>	29.01
	Blattodea, Blattellidae	<i>Temnopteryx phalerata</i>	32.56
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	36.03
	Araneae, Theridiidae	<i>Euryopsis</i> sp. 1	38.93
Fynbos and Forest	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Lepisiota capensis</i>	1.38
	Arachnida, Opiliones	sp. 1	2.66
	Collembola, Entomobryidae	<i>Seira barnardi</i>	3.88
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	5.05
	Coleoptera, Staphylinidae	<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 1	6.19
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Technomyrmex pallipes</i>	7.31
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 2 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	8.39
	Amphipoda, Talitridae	<i>Talitriator cylindripes</i>	9.39
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Monomorium</i> sp.	10.37
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Tetramorium</i> sp.	11.34
Fynbos and Pine	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Lepisiota capensis</i>	1.72
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	3.32
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 2 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	4.90
	Hemiptera, Aphididae	sp. 2	6.39
	Hemiptera, Aphididae	sp. 1	7.81
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Monomorium</i> sp.	9.20
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Technomyrmex pallipes</i>	10.54
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Camponotus niveosetosus</i>	11.64
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 1 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	12.71
	Hymenoptera, Formicidae	<i>Tetramorium</i> sp.	13.73

Baseline data for clear-felled sites

In total, 20 295 individual invertebrates representing 309 ground-dwelling invertebrate species were collected at the eight clear-felled sites sampled, 58 of which were unique to clear-felled sites (mostly singletons). This brought the total number of individuals collected in all four habitats to 112 404, representing 728 species. Almost all higher taxa collected at other sites were represented at clear-felled sites. One velvet worm (a single individual of *Peripatopsis stelliporata*), eight spider, one cricket (*Gryllus bimaculatus*), seven bug, 16 beetle, nine fly and 16 wasp species were unique to clear-felled sites.

Sampling approached, but did not achieve, saturation in all four habitats (Fig. 7.2a). Consequently, estimated species richness was higher than observed in all habitats. Estimated species richness based on incidence (ICE and Chao 2) was higher in all habitats than when based on abundance (ACE and Chao 1), reflecting the high percentage of singletons. Both observed (Fig. 7.2a) and estimated (Fig. 7.2b) species richness were highest in forest, with very little difference among fynbos, pine plantation, and clear-felled habitats. Although there was some variation among estimators, the pattern of highest species richness in forest persisted across all estimators. This suggests that the sampling methods used accurately represented the true pattern of ground-dwelling invertebrate species richness. Mean species richness was lower in clear-felled pine (81.5 ± 13.1 SD species), than in fynbos (99.9 ± 16.7), pine plantation (107.9 ± 20.6), and forest (154.6 ± 16.3). Mean species richness per site was significantly different among habitats (Kruskal-Wallis $H_{(3, N=31)} = 20.488$, $p < 0.001$), reflecting the higher species richness in forest. Mean species richness was not significantly different between fynbos and pine plantation ($p = 1.000$), fynbos and clear-felled pine ($p = 0.702$), and pine plantation and clear-felled pine ($p = 0.468$).

Figure 7.2. Baseline data species richness comparison among habitats with (a) sample-based species-accumulation curves of observed species richness, calculated using S_{obs} Mao Tau and randomised 50 times, and (b) mean \pm SD estimated species richness based on abundance (ACE and Chao 1) and incidence (ICE and Chao 2).

The ground-dwelling invertebrate community composition differed among habitats (Fig. 7.3). Forest and pine plantation sites formed two separate, tight clusters. Fynbos sites separated into three clusters, according to vegetation type: Granite Fynbos (Sites 6 and 8), Sandstone Fynbos (Sites 10, 14, 17 and 26), and recovering Sandstone Fynbos (Sites 3 and 30). Clear-felled pine sites also formed various clusters. Clear-felled Sites 12, 16 and 19 clustered together. These were the most recently felled (less than one year prior to sampling), had sparse ground cover and shrubs compared to other clear-felled and fynbos sites, and

appear to have retained their pine signature, clustering closest to pine plantation sites. Clear-felled Sites 24 and 32 had the longest time-since-felling (over five years), densest vegetation of all clear-felled sites, and clustered with the two recovering Sandstone Fynbos sites. Old clear-felled Sites 20 and 23 clustered with the undisturbed Sandstone Fynbos sites. Clear-felled Site 28 appears to be an outlier, possibly because baboons destroyed four sugar-baited ant traps and five pitfall traps at this site.

Figure 7.3. Ordination from non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS), applied to a Bray-Curtis similarity matrix of log transformed community composition amongst sites for all 728 ground-dwelling invertebrate species.

Indicator verification

Ant communities separated into three clusters (Fig. 7.4a). One cluster comprised all undisturbed Granite and Sandstone Fynbos sites and clear-felled Sites 20 and 23. The other two clusters were a mixture of forest, pine plantation and clear-felled pine sites. One cluster included the three most recently felled sites (Sites 12, 16 and 19), and with the exception of Site 21, all sites in this cluster were not invaded by Argentine ants (no or very few individuals of Argentine ants present). The other mixed habitat cluster included older clear-felled sites with dense vegetation, and all sites where Argentine ants were abundant (over 100 individuals collected).

Six ant functional groups were represented: Dominant Dolichoderinae, General Myrmicinae, Opportunists, Subordinate Camponotini, Specialist Predators and Tropical Climate Specialists. Sites separated into four clusters based on ant functional groups, with 62% similarity between clusters (Fig. 7.4b). Functional group clusters followed a similar pattern of

on SIMPER analysis (Table 7.4). These three native ant species were all more abundant in fynbos than in forest and pine plantation. They were also most abundant at clear-felled Sites 20 and 23, the sites that clustered with undisturbed fynbos sites in ordinations from MDS (Fig. 7.4). These species were absent, or present in very low numbers (1-3 individuals), at clear-felled Sites 28 and 32, where Argentine ants were highly abundant (over 2000 individuals per site). *Crematogaster* sp. and *Camponotus* sp. 2 (*maculatus* group) were absent at recently clear-felled Sites 12, 16 and 19, where Argentine ants were not abundant (less than 10 individuals). Argentine ants contributed the most to the dissimilarity of ant communities between clear-felled and other habitats, although their contribution to the separation of fynbos and clear-felled sites was lower than for other habitats.

Table 7.4. Ant species contributing to 50% of the dissimilarity of ant communities in different habitats, identified from SIMPER analysis, and used to verify the previously identified potentially suitable ecological indicator species for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos.

Habitats	Ant species	Cumulative %
Forest and clear-felled (average dissimilarity = 52.07%)	<i>Linepithema humile</i>	17.00
	<i>Lepisiota capensis</i>	29.14
	<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 2 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	39.06
	<i>Tetramorium</i> sp.	48.67
	<i>Monomorium</i> sp.	58.20
Fynbos and clear-felled (average dissimilarity = 58.02%)	<i>Linepithema humile</i>	9.98
	<i>Lepisiota capensis</i>	19.93
	<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 2 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	28.69
	<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	36.84
	<i>Technomyrmex pallipes</i>	44.21
	<i>Monomorium</i> sp.	50.64
Pine plantation and clear-felled (average dissimilarity = 48.71%)	<i>Linepithema humile</i>	17.77
	<i>Lepisiota capensis</i>	30.83
	<i>Monomorium</i> sp.	42.30
	<i>Tetramorium</i> sp.	51.20

Discussion

Indicator selection

The final scores assigned during indicator selection are dependent on the criteria chosen and score category range. Several criteria are subjective, while criteria that depend on collected data are influenced by the choice and vagaries of the sites sampled. The rank order of taxa is thus likely to differ, depending on the opinion and experience of the researchers assigning the scores, and the region in question. Notwithstanding these limitations, this approach, when combined with a case-study to test the selected ecological indicator taxa, is more pragmatic than continuing to ignore or exclude invertebrates in monitoring programmes. Indicator selection criteria can save time and money that might otherwise be wasted studying and monitoring taxa that are not suitable candidates (McGeoch, 1998).

Ants, both as a higher taxon (family) and individual species, appear to be the most suitable native ground-dwelling invertebrates to use as ecological indicators for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos on the Cape Peninsula (Tables 7.1-7.3). Ants were recently identified as the most suitable terrestrial invertebrate taxon for inclusion in protected area monitoring programmes in South Africa (McGeoch *et al.*, in press). Ants are also by far the most commonly used invertebrate taxon in indicator studies throughout Australia, and in parts of North and South America, Europe, Asia and southern Africa (Majer *et al.*, 2007). Compared to most other ground-dwelling invertebrate taxa, ants are easily collected and readily identifiable, making them suitable indicator taxa for monitoring (Andersen & Sparling, 1997; Summerville *et al.*, 2004).

Baseline data for clear-felled sites

Biodiversity inventories are a vital first step in any monitoring programme (Rohr *et al.*, 2007; Engelbrecht, 2010). Although the species and higher taxon richness was high (728 species), most of the species collected in this study have little value for baseline data for future monitoring, because as morphospecies, they were not identified even to family or genus level. Roughly 20% of the 728 species collected at the 31 sites sampled were not checked or identified further by a taxonomic expert. The vast majority of invertebrate taxa are too poorly known and difficult to identify to be useful or practical for monitoring (Kremen *et al.*, 1993; New, 1999b). Despite the taxonomic limitations, these baseline data show that mean, observed and estimated invertebrate species richness of habitats did not offer suitable indications of restoration progress (Fig. 7.2). Mean species richness in clear-felled pine was lower than, but

not significantly different from, that in both fynbos and pine plantation. These baseline data on invertebrate community composition suggest that vegetation type and age (time-since-felling) are insufficient to explain restoration progress in fynbos (Fig. 7.3). The proportions of bare ground, groundcover and shrubs, and presence of invasive alien species, especially Argentine ants, are likely to be equally important drivers of invertebrate community composition.

The time scale necessary to observe full floral recovery of fynbos after clear-felling is of the order of several fire cycles and thus several decades (Holmes & Richardson, 1999), far beyond the scope of this study, or similar previous studies (e.g. Pryke & Samways, 2009b). For this reason, most studies (including this one) adopt the chronosequence approach of comparing sites of different ages at a single point in time in order to infer how succession or colonisation might take place over time. This chronosequence approach has inherent problems, many of which relate to the vagaries of sites (Majer, 2009). As is often the case with biological field studies, uncontrolled factors confounded the interpretation of patterns in these data. Baboons destroyed four sugar-baited ant traps and five pitfall traps (almost half of the traps set) at clear-felled Site 28, and one ant trap and two pitfall traps in the adjacent pine plantation Site 27. These sites are consequently not strictly comparable with other, undisturbed fynbos sites, because data from all sampling replicates were pooled to calculate species richness and abundance at each site.

Restoration practitioners often assume that if plant communities are restored, invertebrate communities will return to the undisturbed condition, but this is not always the case (Longcore, 2003; Babin-Fenske & Anand, 2010). Longcore (2003) found that arthropod communities in restored coastal sage scrub in California did not closely resemble arthropod communities at undisturbed sites, regardless of time elapsed since vegetation was established. Instead, restored sage scrub sites were considered “depauperate imitations” that supported lower arthropod diversity and more alien species. Similarly, Pryke & Samways (2009b) found that undisturbed fynbos on the Cape Peninsula supported higher invertebrate species richness than fynbos restoration sites where pine plantations had been removed within the previous five years. Although no significant differences in litter invertebrate species richness between undisturbed and recovering fynbos were detected in this study, this finding does not imply that restoration is complete, or that invertebrate communities have fully re-established in clear-felled sites. Rather, it emphasises the danger in relying on species richness alone as a measure of restoration progress or success. The sampled guild of invertebrates will also determine rates of recovery. Litter fauna may in fact respond more rapidly to restoration than herbivores, which

would by necessity be linked to the recovery of floral species composition, owing to their often specialised plant association. Leaf litter is a more generic habitat and food source.

Ecological memory is fundamental for restoration success, but is lost over time (see Schaefer, 2009 for discussion). The ecological memory of Peninsula Granite Fynbos under pine plantation and clear-felled pine sites is likely to be poor, considering the long planting history on the Cape Peninsula. The ecological memory of afforested Peninsula Granite Fynbos is also clouded by clearing practices. Following clear-felling, pine stumps (with roots intact), needles, and some logs are left in place, retaining some of the ecological signature of pine plantations. While this practice can avert major soil erosion after clear-felling, and may facilitate the establishment of fynbos vegetation by trapping seeds, it also means that restored sites may never be equivalent to fynbos reference sites. It is unknown what effect this will have on the resultant invertebrate community.

Even if viable soil seed banks have survived under pine plantations, or fynbos species are able to colonise clear-felled sites, a fully functioning fynbos ecosystem may not be achieved unless essential ecosystem processes, such as seed dispersal, are re-established. The presence of a species in a restored habitat does not guarantee that it is performing the same ecological function as in an uninvaded habitat (Gratton & Dunn, 2006). For example, once monitoring has confirmed that native seed dispersing ants have established colonies in clear-felled sites undergoing restoration, ant behavioural studies will be necessary to link the presence of these ant species to the dispersal of myrmecochorous proteas and other fynbos plants. Only then will these ant species be reliable ecological indicators of restoration success in fynbos. Indications are that the ecological memory of the Peninsula Granite Fynbos invertebrate community has largely been lost under pine plantation, as the pine communities were most similar to those in forest, and the clear-felled communities most closely resembled Sandstone Fynbos (Fig. 7.3). More complex species mutualisms, such as the provision of honeydew resources to ants by various bugs, are also affected by plant species composition. This is likely to have cascading ecological impacts, where for example, Argentine ant numbers might be facilitated by weedy pioneer plants that support honeydew-producing bugs.

Indicator verification

This study did not attempt to establish the robustness of the indicator taxa selected by developing and testing appropriate hypotheses under different conditions (different areas or at different times). However, exhaustive hypothesis testing defeats the purpose of selecting indicators in the first place – to save time and money in answering pressing conservation

questions (McGeoch, 1998). This study also did not attempt to show correlation between restoration progress and ant species richness, or between ant species richness and the species richness of other invertebrates. While species richness may be an appropriate measure for some taxa, this does not always hold for ants. Ant species richness can remain relatively stable, even when major compositional changes take place (Kaspari & Majer, 2000). Ant species richness can also respond to habitat changes in unpredictable ways that are often case-specific, and therefore difficult to interpret (Andersen, 2010). Most ant-monitoring programmes therefore focus on community composition changes (Kaspari & Majer, 2000; Andersen, 2010). Because ant communities respond to ecosystem disturbance and reflect ecosystem changes, ants are widely used in monitoring faunal changes associated with mine restoration, agriculture and livestock grazing (Andersen, 1997b; 1999; 2010).

Reliable interpretation of the response of ants to clear-felling and restoration of fynbos is possible using functional groups. Reliable prediction and interpretation using functional groups is advocated, even when predictive power is not possible at the species level, because little is known about specific dynamics within communities (Andersen, 1997a). Changes in the abiotic environment can result in changes in functional group abundance that lead to shifts from aggressive Dominant Dolichoderinae to subdominant and opportunistic Myrmicinae or Climate Specialists (Andersen & Majer, 2004). Ant functional groups follow vegetation succession, with opportunists and generalists the first to colonise after a disturbance, such as clear-felling (Andersen, 1995), a general trend supported by the finding of Opportunists dominating the most recently clear-felled sites sampled in this chronosequence study. The relative proportion of ant functional groups is highly dependent on the structural diversity of vegetation (New, 2000). As restoration proceeds, the community should increase in complexity and diversity, but may be altered by dominant invasive ants.

This test of the selected indicator taxa highlights the importance of including a fine-filter approach to monitoring, using features such as invasive alien species (Noss, 1990). Habitat disturbance has been shown to facilitate community invasion and subsequent competitive dominance by invasive ants in various ecosystems (Christ, 2009). Argentine ants are known to reduce native ant diversity (Cole *et al.*, 1992; Holway, 1998; Touyama *et al.*, 2003; Rowles & O'Dowd, 2007) and to replace dominant native ants (Bond & Slingsby, 1984; Holway *et al.*, 2002; Parker-Allie *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, invasion by Argentine ants at sites undergoing restoration will hamper restoration efforts. Argentine ants displace abundant native ant species, such as *Anoplolepis custodiens* and *Pheidole capensis*, that are vital for the effective dispersal and below-ground storage of large-seeded proteas (De Kock & Giliomee, 1989; Christian, 2001;

Witt *et al.*, 2004). Argentine ants are seed predators and do not bury seeds, unlike many native ant species (Christian, 2001). Therefore, if Argentine ants persist and prevent native ants from establishing colonies as restoration proceeds, an altered plant community composition in fynbos sites undergoing restoration might result. Non-resprouting myrmecochorous fynbos plants might not survive fires unless their seeds are safely stored below ground.

At present, undisturbed Granite and Sandstone Fynbos on the eastern slopes of Table Mountain National Park do not appear to be invaded by Argentine ants. However, both restored fynbos sites and clear-felled sites (apart from the three most recently felled sites), were invaded by Argentine ants, with over 100 individuals collected per site. Pryke & Samways (2009b) also recorded significantly higher abundance of Argentine ants in recovering fynbos than in mature fynbos, forest or pine plantation on the Cape Peninsula. They suggest that this may only be temporary, with Argentine ant abundance likely to decline as recovering fynbos sites undergo succession to mature fynbos. Confirmation of this requires regular monitoring, since the invasion and colony establishment of Argentine ants can lead to biotic homogenisation (Holway & Suarez, 2006) and community disassembly (Sanders *et al.*, 2003). In a study of coastal sage scrub restoration, Longcore (2003) concluded that ants were not suitable ecological indicators, because Argentine ants had invaded all sites and reduced native arthropod diversity. However, for this very reason, ants should be considered as bioindicators, because a goal of restoration should be to eliminate Argentine ants and other alien invertebrates as restoration proceeds, allowing the native ant community to re-establish.

Of the three native ant species tested as ecological indicator species, *Lepisiota capensis* appears to be the most suitable indicator of restoration progress in fynbos, because it was the only species contributing to the cumulative top 50% of dissimilarity between clear-felled sites and pine plantation sites, with higher numbers at the latter (Table 7.4). *L. capensis* may resist Argentine ant invasion (Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003; Matilya, 2003; Edge *et al.*, 2008), a possible explanation for the absence of Argentine ants in high abundance in undisturbed fynbos sites, and offers additional predictive power for assessing restoration progress. *Monomorium* sp. was among the species contributing the most to the dissimilarity between clear-felled sites and other habitats, but was not considered a suitable indicator species, because it was abundant in all habitats and present at 28 of the 31 sites sampled.

Although not identified by SIMPER analysis (Table 7.4) as making a high percentage contribution to the similarity within habitats, or dissimilarity among habitats, four additional ant species show promise as ecological indicators of restoration progress in fynbos. These additional species, *Camponotus* sp. 1 (*maculatus* group), *Myrmecaria nigra*, *Pheidole capensis*

and *Hagensia peringueyi*, were collected in fynbos, but not in forest or pine plantation, and were most abundant at clear-felled Sites 20 and/or 23. Until the taxonomy of the *Camponotus maculatus* species complex is resolved, it may be pragmatic to treat them as a single group, since both morphospecies collected show promise as ecological indicators. The Spotted sugar ant complex (*Camponotus maculatus* group) is easy to identify, comprising the largest ants in fynbos.

Conclusion

Ants, at both the higher taxon (family) and individual species level, appear to be the most suitable native ground-dwelling invertebrates to use as ecological indicators for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos following clear-felling of pine. The functional group approach has universal relevance and is easy to apply, requiring identification to genus level only. Monitoring the relative positions of ant communities in clear-felled sites undergoing restoration in relation to mature pine plantations and undisturbed fynbos control sites on ordination scatterplots over time will provide a measure of restoration progress (Pik *et al.*, 2002). It is important to monitor ants over time, at both fine and coarse scales, because Argentine ants display a dynamic invasion front, with seasonal and annual fluctuations. Their apparent absence in pristine fynbos on Table Mountain needs to be confirmed, and further researched, as this has implications for the spread and control of this species. In this regard, pine plantations may well offer refugia for Argentine ants (especially during the dry summer), effectively extending the front and possibly providing a launch for this species into native forest. The current situation is likely to be an old one, with the possibility of some equilibrium having been achieved. Monitoring could focus on the Argentine ant and *Lepisiota capensis*, to support the suggestion that each is capable of displacing the other. These findings have application to other Mediterranean-type ecosystems where pine has been introduced and become invasive. Monitoring invasive alien species, especially Argentine ants, is also important in other Mediterranean-climate regions.

CHAPTER 8. IMPLICATIONS OF PLANTING AND FELLING PINE FOR GROUND-DWELLING INVERTEBRATES ON THE CAPE PENINSULA

Implications of planting pine for ground-dwelling invertebrates

Appropriate comparisons of biodiversity between plantations and native vegetation

Plantations are popularly perceived to support impoverished faunal diversity, compared to nearby native forests (Hartley, 2002; Lachat *et al.*, 2006). Globally, most studies comparing the biodiversity of single-species exotic plantations to natural forests have reported lower diversity of invertebrates, birds, mammals and plants in plantations (Stephens & Wagner, 2007). In spite of this negative public perception, and the scientific evidence to support it, plantations can offer habitat refuges for many species of birds and invertebrates (Brockhoff *et al.*, 2003; Pawson & Brockhoff, 2005; Berndt *et al.*, 2008). This is most relevant in areas where deforestation has led to large-scale loss and fragmentation of native forest habitat.

In South Africa, however, most plantations were not established on deforested land. Afrotemperate forest (formerly Afromontane forest, *sensu* White (1978)) patches are small (less than 10 ha) and have a naturally fragmented distribution across the eastern and southern mountain ranges (Berliner, 2005; Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006). The extensive network of commercial plantations surrounding this 'forest archipelago' is therefore rooted in the matrix of other temperate biomes, such as grassland and fynbos (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006). Plantations on the eastern slopes of the Table Mountain range were established in sites previously supporting fynbos, rather than in areas cleared of evergreen forest (Mucina & Geldenhuys, 2006). While the Cape Peninsula's Afrotemperate forests were heavily exploited in the early days of colonial settlement in the Cape (SANParks, 2009), there is little evidence to show that forest was more widespread in the recent past. On the contrary, the natural fire patterns and underlying geology (Afrotemperate forest occurs mainly on sandstone, whereas most montane plantations were established on granite) suggest that these plantations did replace fynbos, more specifically Peninsula Granite Fynbos (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006 and references therein). Hence, afforestation likely had detrimental impacts on fynbos-specialist species, rather than on forest-specialists.

While plantations on the Cape Peninsula are known to act as 'surrogate habitat' for the components of the native Southern Afrotemperate Forest fauna (Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002; Rahinjanahary, 2007), they offer only temporary habitat for forest-adapted invertebrates, because plantations are harvested and replanted on a regular basis (roughly every 30-35

years). For the comparison of faunal diversity between exotic plantations and native vegetation to be appropriate (Stephens & Wagner, 2007), invertebrate species richness, abundance and community composition in this study were compared between exotic pine plantation and both native forest and fynbos.

Impacts of afforestation on invertebrate diversity

In total, 92 109 individuals representing 670 ground-dwelling invertebrate species were collected at the 23 sites sampled in forest, fynbos and pine plantation across the eastern slopes of Table Mountain National Park (Chapters 2 and 3). Cumulative observed species richness, estimated species richness based on abundance (using ACE and Chao 1) and incidence (using ICE and Chao 2), as well as mean species richness per site, were all significantly lower in pine plantation than in forest, but not compared to fynbos (Chapter 3). These findings follow the global trend of lower biodiversity in plantations compared to natural forests (94% of studies), but not always (only 57% of studies) when compared to non-forested natural ecosystems (Stephens & Wagner, 2007).

For all litter invertebrates combined, community composition differed among sites within habitats, and among habitats (Chapter 3). In a MDS ordination, sites clustered into distinct groups according to habitat, with pine plantation invertebrate communities being more similar to forest communities than to those of fynbos. This was expected, since pine plantation offers litter and dead wood microhabitats comparable to those in Afrotropical forest, hence extending the range of many forest litter species. Fynbos sites separated out across the y-axis into three clusters according to vegetation type, namely Granite Fynbos, Sandstone Fynbos, and recovering Sandstone Fynbos that is considered rehabilitated. The Granite Fynbos sites clustered separately, far apart from pine plantation sites. This suggests that most Granite Fynbos specialist invertebrate species do not survive under pine plantations, and that, due to afforestation, much of the true Peninsula Granite Fynbos invertebrate community may already be lost from this 'Endangered' vegetation type. This likely includes the loss of some Cape Peninsula endemic species.

Of the nine Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrate species identified (Chapter 4), the scorpion *Uroplectes insignis* was the only endemic species collected in pine plantation, and then only in Newlands Forest. This implies that pine plantations do not provide suitable surrogate habitat for most Cape Peninsula endemic species, many of which are Afrotropical forest litter specialists, or are aquatic or cave-dwelling (Picker & Samways, 1996). Plantations often support

few forest specialist invertebrate species (Magura *et al.*, 2000), even though they may offer habitat reservoirs for some endangered species (Brockerhoff *et al.*, 2005).

Pine plantations supported roughly half the cumulative total number of invertebrate individuals, and half the mean number of invertebrate individuals per site, compared to forest and fynbos (Chapter 4). Pine plantations also supported far fewer unique species (59 species compared to 176 in forest and 120 in fynbos), and most species collected only in pine plantations were represented by singletons (Chapter 4). Approximately 22% of all species collected were common to all three habitats. Mean species turnover within each habitat was significantly lower in pine plantation than in either forest or fynbos (Chapter 4). Pine plantation is a fairly uniform, artificial habitat, and is dominated by widespread, generalist species, so lower turnover compared to native habitats was expected. High species turnover (beta diversity) for epigaeic invertebrates has previously been reported in fynbos on Table Mountain (Pryke & Samways, 2010), and in Afrotropical forest in the Drakensberg mountains, where turnover ranged from complete to 50%, even between forest patches within the same valley (Hamer & Slotow, 2009; Uys *et al.*, 2009). Mean species turnover was also lower between pine plantation and forest, than between other pairs of habitats, confirming that pine plantations share greater affinity with Afrotropical forests than with fynbos.

Afforestation facilitates the establishment and spread of alien invertebrate species

In addition to generating impoverished faunal diversity and excluding locally endemic species, alien plantations may facilitate the establishment and spread of alien species into surrounding native vegetation. The 19 alien invertebrate species identified comprised the Argentine ant (*Linepithema humile*), four slug and eight snail species, the Portuguese millipede (*Ommatoiulus moreleti*), the Rough woodlouse (*Porcellio scaber*), three springtail species, and the European wasp (*Vespula germanica*). All 18 non-ant alien invertebrate species collected are European in origin, with most originating from the Mediterranean region (Chapter 6). Most of these alien species have also been established in South Africa for many decades, and some for centuries. However, some alien species, such as the Leopard slug (*Limax maximus*), have not become invasive and expanded their range, despite their long establishment on Table Mountain. The number of alien species identified has almost certainly been underestimated, because most taxa were only identified to morphospecies level and the South African alien fauna remains poorly known for most invertebrate taxa (other than ants and molluscs).

Fifteen of the 19 alien invertebrate species were collected in pine plantation, compared to 16 in forest and 11 in fynbos, with no significant difference between habitats in mean number

of alien species per site (Chapter 4). Over half of the alien invertebrate species identified were present in all three habitats, and probably represent generalist species. The opportunistic, highly invasive Argentine ant was present in all habitats, with lower total abundance and mean abundance per site in pine plantation than in forest, but similar abundance in pine plantation and fynbos (albeit far more abundant in recovering Sandstone Fynbos than in undisturbed Granit or Sandstone Fynbos sites). Argentine ants were first recognised as a pest in Cape Town in 1908 (Skaife, 1961; 1962; Richardson *et al.*, 1992), so have probably been well-established in Afrotropical forest on the Cape Peninsula for many decades. They have also been recognised as a threat to native invertebrate diversity in a number of previous studies (Picker & Samways, 1996; Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002; Rahinjanahary, 2007; Pryke & Samways, 2010). Most other alien invertebrate species identified have also been established in the Western Cape for several decades (refer to Chapter 6). The Portuguese millipede and one of the slug species (*Arion hortensis* aggregate) were also abundant and widespread (present at all or most sites respectively). The invasive European wasp was present in all habitats, but was collected in low numbers, and was less abundant in pine plantation than in both forest and fynbos.

Impacts of alien invertebrate species on native invertebrate taxa

Alien invertebrate species that have colonised and/or spread through plantations may also impact native invertebrate diversity, either directly through predation and parasitism, or indirectly by disease transmission, by disrupting mutualisms, or through interference competition (Kenis *et al.*, 2009). Through these combined direct and indirect effects, invasive alien species can displace native species (Holway *et al.*, 2002), disassemble the remaining communities (Sanders *et al.*, 2003), and/or disrupt various ecosystem processes (O'Dowd *et al.*, 2003). In particular, social insects (ants and wasps) are among the most successful invasive organisms (Moller, 1996) and several of them, including Argentine ants, feature among the *100 of the world's worst invasive species* (Lowe *et al.*, 2000).

Argentine ants were present at 16 of the 23 sites sampled, but only eight sites were considered invaded in that Argentine ants were collected in appreciable numbers (over 100 individuals) and represented the most abundant ant species at these sites (Chapter 5). Argentine ants had the most pronounced negative impacts on the species richness, abundance and community composition of native ants in fynbos. Argentine ants have previously been reported to reduce ant species richness and replace dominant native ants, especially ground-foraging seed-dispersers, in fynbos (Bond & Slingsby, 1984; De Kock & Giliomee, 1989; Parker-Allie *et al.*, 2008). Reduced native ant species richness and abundance following invasion has

similarly been reported in Australia (Walters & Mackay, 2005; Walters, 2006), California (DiGirolamo & Fox, 2006; Glenn & Holway, 2008; Heller *et al.*, 2008), Spain (Oliveras *et al.*, 2005), and Japan (Touyama *et al.*, 2003).

Invasion by Argentine ants also altered ant community composition. In a MDS ordination of all 17 ant species, sites clustered in three groups: uninvaded fynbos sites, uninvaded forest and pine plantation sites, and all invaded sites. It is not surprising that uninvaded forest and pine plantation sites clustered together, since most ant species in pine plantations probably originated from Afrotropical forest, and/or are widespread, generalist species.

The 16 native ant species recorded were divided among five functional groups (Andersen, 1995; 1997a) that vary in their known responses to Argentine ant invasion (reviewed in Chapter 5). Argentine ants belong to the Dominant Dolichoderinae functional group, which is not represented in the native South African ant fauna (Majer *et al.*, 2004). Abundances in all functional groups decreased with invasion, with the magnitude of these declines ranging from at least 50% to several orders of magnitude. Although the functional group approach was designed in Australia (Andersen, 1997a; Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003; Majer *et al.*, 2004), it is considered applicable in South Africa, because many Australian ant genera also occur here (Andersen & Majer, 2004).

Species co-occurrence patterns of native ants were investigated using Stone & Roberts' (1990) C-score index. At uninvaded sites there was evidence for nonrandom co-occurrence patterns of native ants, suggesting an aggregated community. This is plausible, since behaviourally-dominant native ants, such as *Anoplolepis custodiens*, which could competitively segregate the native ant community, were not collected. The natural heterogeneity of forest and fynbos may also explain these nonrandom, aggregated spatial distributions (Hui *et al.*, 2010). At sites invaded by Argentine ants, random community association patterns were observed. This suggests that Argentine ants may be responsible for the community disassembly of native ants, especially in fynbos. The comparative approach adopted here provides evidence for the displacement and impoverishment of native ground-dwelling ant communities, consistent with the findings of impacts of Argentine ants reported for the eastern United States (Gotelli & Arnett, 2000) and in fynbos (Luruli, 2007). Invasive ant species are known to reduce native ant species richness, rapidly disassemble native ant communities, and alter community organisation amongst the species that persist (O'Dowd *et al.*, 2003; Sanders *et al.*, 2003).

Non-ant invertebrates may be affected by both the direct impacts of invasive ants and by the resultant indirect impacts following from the displacement of native ants (Holway *et al.*, 2002). However, the impacts of invasive ants may be difficult to detect in mainland faunas,

where communities were most likely shaped by native ant predation prior to invasion (Cole *et al.*, 1992). Clear impacts of invasive ants on entire invertebrate communities have seldom been reported in the literature, and were not found in this study (Chapter 5). The species richness and abundance of the 653 non-ant invertebrate species, the nine Cape Peninsula endemic species and 18 other alien species did not differ significantly between sites uninvaded and invaded by Argentine ants. Community composition was also not clearly defined by Argentine ant invasion, with vegetation type identified as the strongest driver in all cases (Chapter 5). This lack of community-level impact results from the different responses of individual invertebrate orders to Argentine ant invasion. Invertebrates that move slowly, or cannot fly, and those that have soft-bodies, are especially vulnerable to attack by invasive ants (Human & Gordon, 1997). Velvet worms, earthworms, flatworms and slugs all had lower mean abundance at sites invaded by Argentine ants in this study. Taxa with hard exoskeletons and chemical defences should be less vulnerable to attack from would-be predators (Cole *et al.*, 1992). Yet, even spiders, which may not be preyed upon by Argentine ants, were negatively affected by invasion in this study, probably through competition for prey (Cole *et al.*, 1992; Human & Gordon, 1997), or through interference competition, especially for spiders that build webs at ground level (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997). Seventeen of the 32 taxa examined showed reduced mean native abundance associated with Argentine ant invasion in pine plantations. It is not yet clear whether, or how, Argentine ants interact with alien trees to impact native invertebrate diversity.

The impacts of most alien species have not been quantified (Parker *et al.*, 1999). Alien species are generally assumed to have some ecological impact on their invaded ecosystem (Ricciardi & Kipp, 2008), although most species are not likely to become invasive, or to have highly adverse impacts (Williamson & Fitter, 1996; Hulme, 2003). The abundances of most of the 18 non-ant alien species identified here were not significantly correlated with either the species richness or abundance of their corresponding native taxa (Chapter 6). A few taxa showed significant positive correlations with their equivalent alien species, but this was probably related to microhabitat suitability for that taxon in general. The community composition of corresponding native taxa also does not appear to be driven by the presence-absence of these alien species (Chapter 6).

Finding an alien species in a non-invasive state does not, of course, mean that it cannot become invasive in the future (Nentwig & Josefsson, 2010). Therefore, a precautionary approach is necessary in light of the apparent lack of evidence for impact of these 18 alien invertebrate species, especially considering the exceptional local invertebrate endemism found on the Cape Peninsula (Picker & Samways, 1996). Climate change could enable currently

innocuous alien species to become invasive and spread rapidly in the future (Walther *et al.*, 2009; Nentwig & Josefsson, 2010). For example, the Leopard Slug (*Limax maximus*) was first recorded in Newlands Forest on Table Mountain in 1900, where it is still present today, but it has not spread to other forest patches (Herbert, 2010). Much of the distribution and spread data for these alien species in South Africa are anecdotal, and the only published model of potential spread of an alien invertebrate in the Western Cape Province (European wasp: Tribe & Richardson, 1994) is outdated. Particular attention should be paid to carnivorous alien species, including the Brown field slug (*Deroceras panormitanum*), Draparnaud's glass snail (*Oxychilus draparnaudi*) and the European wasp (*Vespula germanica*), each of which could, as they have done elsewhere, potentially negatively impact native invertebrate diversity.

Implications of felling pine for ground-dwelling invertebrates

After original vegetation clearing, clear-fell harvesting causes the most extreme disturbance event in plantation forestry (Pawson *et al.*, 2005), especially under intensified forestry and effective fire suppression (Niemelä *et al.*, 1993). Clear-felling changes the microclimate conditions of an area in terms of temperature, wind speed, relative humidity, evaporation and solar radiation (Chen *et al.*, 1995). As a consequence, recently (two-year-old) clear-felled sites often temporarily support equal or higher invertebrate species richness than surrounding mature plantations, or native forest (Niemelä *et al.*, 1993; Pawson *et al.*, 2009). This initial elevated species richness is a result of colonisation by open-habitat specialist species, which often dominate clear-fell sites, in addition to the short-term survival of species that colonised the plantation prior to felling (Pawson *et al.*, 2005). While species richness may not be negatively affected by harvesting, mature forest specialists and especially the litter fauna, often do not persist and fail to recolonise (Niemelä *et al.*, 1993).

Commercial pine plantations in South Africa are mostly planted in 'same age' compartments and clear-fell harvested when mature, with roughly 30-35 years between planting cycles. However, in the case of Tokai and Cecilia Plantations, the current management plan is to harvest the majority of plantations over a 20-year period up to 2025, and then not to replant them. Management of this land was transferred from Mountain to Ocean (MTO) Forestry Pty (Ltd) to South African National Parks (SANParks) in April 2005, and the land (roughly 1000 ha, of which 600 ha are covered by plantations) has been incorporated into Table Mountain National Park, since this land is of high conservation value (SANParks, 2009).

The ecosystem restoration that is taking place through land acquisition and alien clearing in Table Mountain National Park requires careful monitoring to ensure natural patterns and processes are restored. The time scale necessary to observe full recovery of fynbos after clear-felling of pine plantations spans several fire cycles and hence several decades (Holmes & Richardson, 1999), far beyond the scope of this study, or similar previous studies (e.g. Pryke & Samways, 2009b). Therefore, the chronosequence approach (*i.e.* space for time substitution) was adopted, by comparing eight different aged clear-felled sites sampled at the same time, in order to infer how succession or colonisation might take place over time (Chapter 7).

Pine plantations replaced Peninsula Granite Fynbos across the eastern slopes of the Table Mountain range, and the management aim is to restore this 'Endangered' vegetation type. If plantations in areas such as Tokai are not harvested and restored to fynbos, South Peninsula Granite Fynbos may become 'Critically Endangered' (SANParks, 2009). The problem is that very little Peninsula Granite Fynbos remains, especially in the southern portion of its distribution, to act as reference sites and a source for the recolonisation of fynbos plants and animals in clear-felled sites at Tokai and Cecilia. Pine plantations have already transformed 13% of Peninsula Granite Fynbos (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). The target for conservation of 30% is also not met, despite most of this vegetation type falling within Table Mountain National Park and Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, because fire-exclusion policies have led to the transformation of much of the conserved fynbos into Afrotemperate forest (Rebelo *et al.*, 2006). Furthermore, the invertebrate community composition differs between Granite and Sandstone Fynbos (refer to Chapter 3). These faunal differences should be considered in measurements of fynbos restoration progress. This study is one of the first to compare the invertebrate community between fynbos vegetation types and to identify invertebrates as ecological indicators of fynbos restoration post-felling of pine.

Invertebrates warrant inclusion in a biodiversity monitoring programme tracking the recovery of fynbos post-felling of pine, because they respond rapidly to environmental change (Kremen *et al.*, 1993; Andersen *et al.*, 2004; Rohr *et al.*, 2007). Ground-dwelling invertebrates are also a diverse and functionally important component of the biota, and therefore should be included in a monitoring programme in their own right, not simply because they are easy experimental subjects. Moreover, many are short-range (*i.e.* local) Cape Peninsula endemics.

All invertebrate taxa collected in forest, fynbos and pine plantation were scored against selection criteria to identify suitable indicators of the different habitats (Chapter 7). Ants, at both the higher taxon (family) and individual species level, were ranked as the most suitable ground-dwelling invertebrates to use as ecological indicators. Ant communities respond readily to

ecosystem disturbance (Hoffmann & Andersen, 2003) and reflect ecosystem changes (New, 2000). Therefore, ants are the most commonly used terrestrial invertebrate taxon in indicator studies around the world (Majer *et al.*, 2007), especially for monitoring faunal changes associated with mine restoration, agriculture and livestock grazing (Andersen, 1997b; 1999; 2010).

Ants were verified as a suitable indicator taxon by comparing ant communities in clear-felled sites with other neighbouring habitats. Three ant species were identified as potentially suitable ecological indicator species of both fynbos and old clear-felled sites: *Lepisiota capensis*, *Crematogaster* sp., and *Camponotus* sp. 2 (*maculatus* group) (Chapter 7). These species should be targeted as indicators of successful restoration in fynbos. Similar patterns of separation of clear-felled sites were found using ant species and functional groups (Chapter 7). Reliable interpretation of the response of ants to disturbance (clear-felling) and restoration therefore appears possible using ant functional groups (Andersen, 1995; 1997a; 2010). This has the advantage of not relying on accurate species level identification, which is time-consuming and often difficult. Ant functional groups also follow vegetation succession, with opportunists and generalists the first to colonise after a disturbance, such as clear-fell harvesting (Andersen, 1995). As expected, Generalised Myrmicinae and Opportunists were the most abundant functional groups represented in recently clear-felled sites. However, ant functional group succession may be altered by invasive alien species, as was the case with Argentine ants in this study. In older clear-felled sites, Dominant Dolichoderinae (Argentine ants) represented the most abundant functional group, and the relative abundances of other functional groups differed between uninvaded and invaded clear-felled sites.

Disturbance events are known to facilitate the establishment of invasive species (Hobbs & Huenneke, 1992). These alien invasive plants and animals can alter the progress and direction of regeneration following disturbance events, such as clear-felling (Pawson *et al.*, 2006). As such, alien invertebrate species merit special inclusion in invertebrate monitoring programmes (McGeoch *et al.*, in press), because they can act as a measure of restoration success. The relative proportion of alien invertebrates is likely to differ between restored and undisturbed reference sites (Longcore, 2003), as evidenced by Argentine ants that were not abundant in undisturbed fynbos sites. Argentine ant invasion could hamper fynbos restoration efforts, because if they displace or prevent native ants from establishing colonies as restoration proceeds, an altered fynbos plant community might result. Argentine ants are known to displace the abundant native ant species involved in the effective dispersal and below-ground storage of large-seeded proteas in fynbos (De Kock & Giliomee, 1989; Christian, 2001; Witt *et al.*, 2004).

Thus a goal of restoration should be to control, and if possible eliminate, Argentine ants and other invasive alien species as restoration proceeds.

Cautionary notes

This study was confined to ground-dwelling invertebrates and a small section (about 12 km north-south) of the Cape Peninsula, an area renowned for its exceptional invertebrate diversity and endemism (Picker & Samways, 1996; Hamer & Slotow, 2002; Pryke & Samways 2009a). Results should be interpreted only as an indication of the faunal exchanges that have taken place between exotic pine plantations and native forest and fynbos on the eastern slopes of Table Mountain National Park, and may not apply to plantations in other parts of the Cape Floristic Region, or elsewhere, or to other exotic woody species (*e.g. Acacia, Eucalyptus* and *Quercus* spp.). Nevertheless, the impacts of alien species observed in this study are likely to be more important than in many other regions, owing to the exceptional levels of local endemism on the Cape Peninsula and high beta diversity within and between vegetation types.

Conclusions drawn may also be contingent on the year in which sampling took place. High rainfall was experienced during the 2008 winter rainy season prior to sampling (spring-summer 2008/2009). Summer temperatures, especially during pitfall trap sampling in January and February 2009, often exceeded 30°C, with a few days reaching 40°C. High temperatures may have influenced invertebrate activity and consequently trap success. Biotic variation between years resulting from uncontrolled variables, such as precipitation, temperature and competitor/predator pressure, is known to influence community structure (Vaughn & Young, 2010 and references therein). Since sampling was conducted over only one spring-summer season, inter-annual fluctuations in community composition, population demographics and distributions were not accounted for. Therefore, results should be viewed in a short-term context and longer-term changes need to be monitored. This is especially important for Argentine ants, with their dynamic invasion fronts that result in impacts that vary annually and seasonally.

Species accumulation curves for all invertebrate species collected approached, but did not quite reach, sampling saturation in each habitat (Chapters 3 and 7). To have confidence in the validity of findings it is necessary to know the number of species present in the assemblages sampled, and the number of sampling replicates needed to accurately predict the species richness of an area or habitat (Colwell & Coddington, 1994). Comparative studies of different habitats require a near-complete list of species for each habitat (Thompson *et al.*, 2003). However, there is a trade-off between inventory completeness and sampling intensity (*i.e.*

collector effort), and the costs and logistical practicality must be considered. Greater sampling effort may be needed when there is a high proportion of rare species, because species accumulation curves are influenced by the proportion of rare species at a site (Thompson *et al.*, 2003). Capture frequency was low for many of the species collected in this study, with a high proportion of singletons and doubletons. This low abundance (numbers of individuals) and/or low incidence (presence at one or a few sites only) may reflect true rarity, or simply high numbers of 'transient' species that were passing through the area, but were not resident in that habitat. The slope of the latter part of species accumulation curves for assemblages dominated by rare species is often steeper than for sites or habitats with a more even distribution of relatively abundant species (Thompson & Withers, 2003). This might explain why sampling saturation was not achieved, in spite of the relatively high number of collecting replicates per site. The spatial grain at which species accumulation was investigated might further confound matters. Species accumulation is area dependent, and rarity is often greater at coarser spatial scales (Hui, 2008). Curves were plotted for habitats, with sites used as replicates. Site species counts were calculated by pooling all collecting replicates (leaf litter samples, pitfall traps, etc.) to obtain a single value per site. Therefore, habitat heterogeneity across the spatial extent of sites sampled (12 km north-south distance between furthest sites) may partly account for the lack of clear sampling saturation in species accumulation curves for all species combined. Species accumulations for individual taxa (mostly orders) are also contingent on the interpretation of faunal exchange findings (Chapter 4) and the impacts of alien invertebrates on their corresponding native taxa (Chapters 5 and 6).

The sampling design was constrained by the pre-defined harvesting plan of the forestry company (MTO). As such, we had no say in the clear-felling schedule, and it was not possible to foresee the felling of pine plantation Site 11 (Cecilia) during sampling. As far as possible, pine plantation and clear-felled pine sites were deliberately chosen in close proximity to forest and fynbos sites, to reduce unwanted spatial variability between treatments and controls. However, the 'ideal' scenario of all four habitats in each of the eight areas sampled could not be achieved, and the size and proximity of sites to other habitats varied. These constraints put limitations on the statistical power and interpretation of some findings, but extended the scope and value of this study, especially in fynbos, where both vegetation type and disturbance history could be compared within fynbos and between habitats.

Nevertheless, the findings of this study are broadly compatible with invertebrate survey results in plantations locally (Ratsirarson *et al.*, 2002; Rahinjanahary, 2007; Pryke & Samways, 2009b) and world-wide (*e.g.* Stephens & Wagner, 2007). While these findings are naturally most

relevant in the Cape Floristic Region, especially on the Cape Peninsula, they are also broadly applicable in Mediterranean-type ecosystems in other parts of the world, especially where pine plantations have replaced native scrubland vegetation and thereby threaten native biodiversity.

Conclusions

As predicted, pine plantations on the Cape Peninsula do act as a double-edged sword for ground-dwelling invertebrate conservation. Firstly, this study adds to the growing body of evidence, in South Africa and globally, showing that exotic woody plantations support lower faunal species richness, and different community assemblages, compared to neighbouring native forest, although they support similar species richness to non-forested ecosystems, such as fynbos. Pine plantations, however, appear to be dominated by widespread, generalist species. Plantations may further negatively impact fynbos-specialist invertebrate communities, which have lost habitat through afforestation. Secondly, the strong colonial history associated with plantations on the Cape Peninsula, combined with the European origin of all non-ant alien invertebrates identified here, suggests that these plantations have facilitated the spread of alien invertebrates into the surrounding native vegetation. These alien invertebrates, especially the carnivorous molluscs, European wasp and Argentine ant, require further study and careful monitoring. While the impacts of all alien invertebrates identified were not clear, Argentine ant invasion appears to have caused displacement, impoverishment and community disassembly of native ants, especially in fynbos.

Both planting and felling of alien pine trees impact invertebrate assemblages. Recovery of invertebrate communities post-felling is critical to ensure a functioning ecosystem. Ants show potential as the most suitable ground-dwelling invertebrate taxon to use as an ecological indicator for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos, following clear-felling of pine plantations. Individual ant species, especially *Lepisiota capensis* that can resist invasion by Argentine ants (Matilya, 2003; Edge *et al.*, 2008), and the relative abundances of ant functional groups should be monitored as restoration proceeds.

The way forward

Recommendations for monitoring invertebrates

- Invertebrate conservation and management needs to be incorporated into mainstream planning and management processes in South African protected areas (Engelbrecht, 2010).

McGeoch *et al.* (in press) recommend further surveys in protected areas that focus on alien invertebrate species and their associated impacts, control or eradication, and institution of measures for the prevention of further spread and future invasions.

- The extension, or replication, of a successful spatially and temporally replicated ant monitoring program, such as the limbovane project (<http://academic.sun.ac.za/iimbovane>), throughout Table Mountain National Park is needed to deliver long-term data (Braschler *et al.*, 2010) and monitor changes as restoration of clear-felled pine proceeds. Valuable lessons can also be learnt from the adoption and implementation of the invertebrate monitoring programme focussed on ants in Kruger National Park, which is also managed by SANParks (McGeoch *et al.*, in press).
- Genus level identification for ants is suitable for monitoring purposes, given that the functional group approach offers reliable interpretation of the response of ants to disturbance (clear-felling) and restoration, and has universal application (Andersen, 1997a).
- The dynamics between the invasive alien Argentine ant (*Linepithema humile*) and a native ant species (*Lepisiota capensis*) shows promise as an index of restoration success in fynbos, given that *L. capensis* is a fynbos-specialist species that appears to be capable of resisting invasion by Argentine ants (Matilya, 2003; Edge *et al.*, 2008).
- Long-term monitoring of fixed sites across an altitudinal range (in this case, moving up the mountain, away from the suburbs) is needed to track the dynamics of the Argentine ant invasion front. Argentine ants are generally not able to sustain colonies in undisturbed fynbos (Macdonald & Jarman, 1984; De Kock & Giliomee, 1989), or in the absence of permanent water sources (Holway, 2005; Parker-Allie *et al.*, 2008), especially at high altitudes (Rahinjanahary, 2007).
- Alien invertebrate species need to be ranked in terms of their impacts to prioritise management actions (Parker *et al.*, 1999). Argentine ants top the list for priority action. Targeted studies for carnivorous molluscs (such as *Oxychilus* spp.) and the European wasp (*Vespula germanica*) should be extended to include sites outside of the National Park.
- A comparative study of alien invertebrates in other Mediterranean-type ecosystems across the world could advance understanding of invasion pathways and processes, enable early warning systems to be put in place for species that have become invasive elsewhere, and share lessons learnt about impacts and successful eradications. While some of these data are available for well-studied social species, such as Argentine ants and to a lesser degree European wasps, comparative data are urgently needed for other alien invertebrate species.

Recommendations for monitoring restoration progress in fynbos following clear-felling of pine

- Clear-felling of pine plantations is potentially beneficial for invertebrate conservation in light of the findings that pine plantations support almost no known Cape Peninsula endemic species and few unique species, yet support a large number of alien invertebrate species in the litter community.
- The challenge will be to document over time whether restoration ultimately leads to the re-establishment of a functional fynbos-specialist invertebrate community, or simply retains an impoverished community dominated by generalist, widespread species.
- Despite the many recognised challenges involved in monitoring with invertebrates (Lovell *et al.*, 2010), the growing number of successful case studies and range of solutions mean that their advantages are beginning to outweigh perceived and real disadvantages (McGeoch *et al.*, in press). Terrestrial, ground-dwelling invertebrate indicator taxa hold value and potential for monitoring responses to environmental change in the South African protected area context (McGeoch *et al.*, 2002; Botes *et al.*, 2006a, b; Uys *et al.*, 2010).
- Granite Fynbos is not likely to regenerate satisfactorily without fire, since fynbos is both fire-prone and fire-dependent (Forsyth & Bridgett, 2004). Therefore, active intervention through controlled burning post-felling is necessary. Fynbos-specialist species are most likely fire-adapted and might be disadvantaged, or even excluded, by continued fire suppression.
- The remaining Southern Afrotemperate Forest patches, restricted to isolated ravines and fire-protected areas in Sandstone Fynbos, must also be managed and protected during restoration efforts, because they support many of the Cape Peninsula endemic invertebrates (Picker & Samways, 1996) and are a conservation priority (Pryke & Samways, 2009b).
- *Pinus radiata* (Monterey pine) is the most widely planted conifer species for commercial timber production globally (Richardson *et al.*, 1994), and is highly invasive in Mediterranean-type scrubland vegetation outside of its native range in California (Henderson, 2001). Therefore, a comparative study of the impacts of planting and felling exotic pine plantations on invertebrate diversity in different Mediterranean-type regions is thus needed.

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APPENDIX A. Checklist of the 728 species and 112 404 individuals from the 31 sites sampled (Site 11 pine omitted), with the number of individuals in each habitat. C = class, O = order, F = family, SubF = subfamily, A = alien and PE = Cape Peninsula endemic.

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled	
C: TURBELLARIA					
O: Tricladida					
F: Rhynchodemidae					
SubF: Microplaninae					
sp.	34	5	22	2	
C: CLITELLATA					
O: Haplotaxida					
unidentified	1113	75	263	26	
C: GASTROPODA					
O: Eupulmonata					
F: Arionidae					
<i>Arion hortensis</i> aggregate Férussac, 1819	A	106	29	131	5
F: Agriolimacidae					
<i>Deroceras panormitanum</i> (Lesson & Pollonera, 1882)	A	30	4	3	0
F: Limacidae					
<i>Lehmannia valentiana</i> (Férussac, 1821)	A	28	4	23	3
<i>Limax maximus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	A	2	0	0	0
F: Charopidae					
<i>Trachycystis bisculpta</i> (Benson, 1851)		0	24	0	1
<i>Trachycystis perplicata</i> (Benson, 1851)	PE	6	0	0	0
<i>Trachycystis tollini</i> (Benson, 1856)		32	0	0	0
<i>Trachycystis/ Afrodonta/ alien</i> sp.		13	5	1	0
F: Cochlicopidae					
<i>Cochlicopa</i> sp.	A	16	0	0	0
<i>Cochlicopa</i> cf. <i>lubricella</i> Férussac, 1821	A	56	0	3	0
F: Helicidae					
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (Müller, 1774)	A	6	0	0	0
F: Hydrocenidae					
<i>Hydrocena noticola</i> Benson, 1856		254	0	0	0
F: Pristilomatidae					
<i>Vitrea contracta</i> (Westerlund, 1871)	A	13	0	19	2
F: Punctidae					
cf. <i>Punctum</i> sp.	A	35	0	38	1
<i>Paralaoma hottentota</i> (Melvil & Ponsonby, 1891)		18	13	6	3
F: Pupillidae					
<i>Lauria cylindracea</i> (da Costa, 1778)	A	0	0	1	0
F: Rhytididae					
<i>Nata tarachodes</i> (Connolly, 1912)		7	0	0	0

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled	
<i>Nata verrucosa</i> (Krauss, 1848)		2	0	0	0
F: Zonitidae					
<i>Oxychilus draparnaudi</i> (Beck, 1837)	A	60	2	13	0
<i>Oxychilus</i> sp. Fitzinger, 1833	A	9	10	10	16
C: ARACHNIDA					
O: Scorpidion					
F: Buthidae					
<i>Uroplectes insignis</i> Pocock, 1890	PE	9	13	6	1
<i>Uroplectes lineatus</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)		0	9	1	14
O: Pseudoscorpiones					
sp. 1		6	13	3	2
sp. 2		17	0	4	0
sp. 3		0	0	1	1
sp. 4		3	0	0	0
sp. 5		2	1	0	0
O: Solifugae					
F: Solpugidae					
<i>Zeria fusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1842)		0	7	0	1
O: Araneae					
F: Cyrtaucheniidae					
<i>Ancylotrypa</i> sp. 1		1	1	0	0
<i>Ancylotrypa</i> sp. 2		0	1	0	0
F: Migidae					
<i>Moggridgea quercina</i> Simon, 1903		2	0	1	0
<i>Moggridgea teresae</i> Griswold, 1987	PE	8	1	0	0
F: Nemesiidae					
<i>Hermacha brevicauda</i> Purcell, 1903		3	0	0	0
<i>Hermacha</i> sp.		0	1	0	0
F: Amaurobiidae					
<i>Chresiona</i> sp.		7	1	0	0
F: Anapidae					
sp.		2	2	5	0
F: Araneidae					
<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)		0	0	0	1
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)		1	0	0	0
F: Clubionidae					
<i>Cheiramiona</i> sp.		1	2	1	1
<i>Clubiona</i> sp. 1		11	2	1	2

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Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
<i>Clubiona</i> sp. 2	4	0	0	0
<i>Clubiona vachoni</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	0	0	0
F: Corinnidae				
sp. 1	1	4	4	3
sp. 2	4	2	0	1
sp. 3	1	0	0	0
sp. 4	1	0	1	0
F: Ctenidae				
<i>Ctenus</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
F: Cyatholipidae				
<i>Cyatholipus quadrimaculatus</i> Simon, 1894	7	2	7	3
F: Dictynidae				
<i>Dictyna</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
<i>Mashimo leleupi</i> Lehtinen, 1967	0	1	0	0
F: Drymusidae				
<i>Drymusa capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	0	1	0
F: Gnaphosidae				
<i>Asemesthes</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
<i>Camillina</i> sp.	1	2	1	0
<i>Drassodes</i> sp. 1	2	0	0	0
<i>Drassodes</i> sp. 2	1	0	0	0
<i>Zelotes</i> sp. 1	1	2	0	2
<i>Zelotes</i> sp. 2	0	2	0	1
<i>Zelotes</i> sp. 3	0	15	0	10
<i>Zelotes</i> sp. 4	0	0	0	4
<i>Zelowan</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
F: Hahniidae				
<i>Hahnia</i> sp. nov. C.L. Koch, 1841	1	0	0	0
F: Linyphiidae				
<i>Eperigone fradeorum</i> (Berland, 1932)	1	0	0	1
<i>Meioneta</i> sp.	3	0	4	0
<i>Metaleptyphantes</i> sp. 1	17	7	15	7
<i>Metaleptyphantes</i> sp. 2	1	0	1	0
<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (OP-Cambridge, 1879)	1	0	0	1
sp. 1	3	2	20	3
sp. 2	1	1	1	1
F: Liocranidae				
sp. 1	0	2	3	0
sp. 2	1	0	0	0
sp. 3	1	0	0	0
F: Lycosidae				
<i>Pardosa</i> sp. 1	0	0	0	2
<i>Pardosa</i> sp. 2	0	0	0	10
sp. 1	0	0	0	9
sp. 2	0	0	0	10
sp. 3	0	2	0	25

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
F: Mimetidae				
<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	0	0	0
F: Miturgidae				
<i>Phanotea</i> sp. 1	2	0	0	0
<i>Phanotea</i> sp. 2	1	0	0	0
F: Oonopidae				
<i>Gamasomorpha</i> sp.	1	0	0	0
F: Orsolobidae				
sp.	0	0	1	0
F: Oxyopidae				
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp.	0	2	0	0
F: Palpimanidae				
<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	12	0	4	1
F: Philodromidae				
<i>Philodromus vulgaris</i> (Hentz, 1847)	1	4	0	8
F: Pholcidae				
<i>Spermophora gordimerae</i> Huber, 2003	PE	6	3	0
<i>Spermophora peninsulae</i> Lawrence, 1964	PE	1	0	0
<i>Spermophora</i> sp.	4	0	1	0
F: Phyxelididae				
<i>Malaika longipes</i> (Purcell, 1904)	PE	14	2	0
F: Pisauridae				
<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908)	0	0	1	0
F: Prodidomidae				
sp.	1	0	0	0
F: Salticidae				
SubF: Aelurillinae				
<i>Langona</i> sp.	0	8	0	4
<i>Phlegra</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
sp. 1	0	1	0	0
sp. 2	0	1	0	0
SubF: Euophryinae				
<i>Euophrys</i> sp.	1	2	2	1
<i>Thyenula oranjensis</i> Wesolowska, 2001	8	2	6	2
<i>Thyenula</i> sp. 1	0	0	1	0
<i>Thyenula</i> sp. 2	1	0	0	1
SubF: Heliophaninae				
<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.	0	0	0	3
<i>Natta</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
SubF: Hyllinae				
<i>Evarcha</i> sp.	1	1	3	1
<i>Pellenes</i> sp.	3	2	2	2
SubF: Massagrininae				
<i>Massagris</i> sp.	2	3	3	3
SubF: Plexippinae				
<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	0	1	0	0

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Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
<i>Thyene</i> sp.	0	2	0	0
sp.	0	2	1	1
F: Scytodidae				
<i>Scytodes gouldi</i> Purcell, 1904	0	1	0	2
<i>Scytodes montana</i> Purcell, 1904	20	17	3	9
F: Segestriidae				
<i>Ariadna</i> sp.	1	1	0	0
F: Selenopidae				
<i>Anyphops</i> sp.	0	4	0	0
F: Tetragnathidae				
<i>Diphya simoni</i> Kauri, 1950	1	0	2	1
<i>Meta</i> sp.	0	0	1	0
F: Theridiidae				
<i>Achaearanea</i> sp.	0	1	3	0
<i>Dipoena</i> sp.	1	5	2	2
<i>Episinus</i> sp.	1	0	0	0
<i>Euryopsis</i> sp. 1	6	76	22	81
<i>Euryopsis</i> sp. 2	0	3	0	1
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	4	1	0	2
<i>Steatoda</i> sp.	1	0	0	0
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 1	4	1	1	3
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 2	2	0	1	0
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3	4	1	0	1
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 4	1	0	2	0
F: Theridiosomatidae				
sp.	1	1	0	0
F: Thomisidae				
<i>Hewittia gracilis</i> Lessert, 1928	0	1	0	0
<i>Monaeses australis</i> (Lawrence, 1937)	1	0	0	0
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	0	0	0
<i>Ozyptila</i> sp.	1	10	0	2
<i>Simorcus haddadi</i> van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010	0	1	1	5
<i>Stiphropus</i> sp.	0	2	0	0
<i>Synema abnorme</i> Lessert, 1923	0	0	0	1
<i>Thomisops</i> sp.	0	3	0	0
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1941	0	2	0	0
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	0	2	1	0
<i>Xysticus lucifugus</i> Lawrence, 1937	1	7	1	1
F: Zodariidae				
<i>Akyttara</i> sp.	0	6	0	2
<i>Chariobas cylindraceus</i> Simon, 1893	4	0	0	0
<i>Cydrela</i> sp.	5	0	3	0
<i>Diorea simoni</i> O. P.-Cambridge, 1904	1	5	2	8
<i>Diorea</i> sp.	0	10	0	1
<i>Diorea youngai</i> Jocqué, 1990	0	19	2	15

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
<i>Heradida</i> sp.	0	3	0	0
O: Opiliones				
sp. 1	702	10	85	52
sp. 2	11	15	5	0
sp. 3	66	11	8	3
sp. 4	10	12	1	0
sp. 5	15	2	2	0
sp. 6	3	0	0	0
sp. 7	4	0	0	0
O: Acari				
sp. 1	56	3	1	2
sp. 2	44	17	3	2
sp. 3	28	7	64	1
sp. 4	35	0	0	0
sp. 5	1	0	4	0
sp. 6	51	2	46	5
sp. 7	0	9	2	1
sp. 8	58	79	159	29
sp. 9	2	99	8	12
sp. 10	59	0	46	1
sp. 11	0	0	1	0
sp. 12	1	0	0	0
sp. 13	3	12	5	0
sp. 14	5	9	22	1
sp. 15	8	0	4	0
sp. 16	8	12	8	6
sp. 17	0	0	1	0
C: MALACOSTRACA				
O: Isopoda				
F: Armadillidiidae				
<i>Armadillidium</i> sp.	37	0	0	0
F: cf. Oniscidae				
sp. 1	54	65	0	11
sp. 2	0	2	0	0
F: Cylisticidae				
<i>Cylisticus</i> sp.	6	3	53	0
F: Porcellionidae				
<i>Porcellio scaber</i> Latreille, 1804	A	49	99	8
sp.	19	0	0	0
F: Trichoniscidae				
<i>Haplophthalmus</i> sp.	18	0	0	0
O: Amphipoda				
F: Talitridae				
<i>Talitriator cylindripes</i> (Barnard, 1940)	1366	143	184	118
<i>Talitriator setosa</i> (Barnard, 1940)	253	25	51	61
C: COLLEMBOLA				

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Species		Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
O: Entomobryomorpha					
F: Entomobryidae					
<i>Entomobrya nivalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	A	0	0	16	2
<i>Entomobrya</i> sp.		0	0	1	1
<i>Lepidocyrtus</i> sp. 1		1	0	2	0
<i>Lepidocyrtus</i> sp. 2		0	9	18	0
<i>Seira barnardi</i> (Womersley, 1934)		1434	32	41	1
<i>Seira capensis</i> Womersley, 1934		35	12	3	0
<i>Seira dayi</i> (Yosii, 1959)		39	30	172	22
<i>Seira ferrarii</i> Parona, 1888		4	5	0	12
<i>Seira nagatai</i> Yosii, 1959		2	0	2	0
<i>Seira</i> sp. 1		9	3	119	5
<i>Seira</i> sp. 2		0	2	0	0
<i>Seira</i> sp. 3		0	5	0	0
<i>Seira</i> sp. 5		3	5	0	8
<i>Seira</i> sp. 6		0	10	0	3
F: Hypogastruridae					
<i>Ceratophysella</i> sp.		0	0	19	0
O: Poduromorpha					
F: Neanuridae					
<i>Neanura muscorum</i> (Templeton, 1835)	A	1	4	2	2
F: Onychiuridae					
<i>Deuteraphorura</i> sp.		0	3	16	0
<i>Orthonychiurus saasveldensis</i> (Weiner & Najt, 1991)		0	0	33	0
F: Tomoceridae					
<i>Tomocerus minor</i> (Lubbock, 1862)	A	0	1	0	4
C: INSECTA					
O: Thysanura					
F: Lepismatidae					
sp.		0	4	0	0
O: Archaeognatha					
F: Machilidae					
<i>Machiloides obsoletus</i> Silvestri, 1904		167	22	7	2
O: Blattodea					
F: Blaberidae					
<i>Aptera fusca</i> (Thunberg, 1784)		0	3	0	0
<i>Perisphaeria, Poeciloblatta</i> sp.		0	8	0	3
F: Blattellidae					
<i>Anallacta confusa</i> Princis, 1963		23	3	0	0
<i>Diptertrum brinckae</i> Princis 1963	PE	0	53	0	0
<i>Ectobius</i> sp. nov.		1	81	3	62
gen. nov.		1	64	1	2
<i>Hoplophoropyga unicolor</i> (Karny, 1908)	PE	0	32	0	30
<i>Temnopteryx phalerata</i> (Saussure, 1864)		13	127	15	90
<i>Xosablatta caffra</i> (Saussure, 1899)		71	4	1	0
F: Blattidae					

Species		Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
<i>Brinckella hanstroemi</i> (Princis, 1949)		0	0	1	0
cf. <i>Duchailluia</i> sp.		4	1	0	4
<i>Pseudoderopeltis</i> sp.		9	21	3	0
O: Mantodea					
sp. 1		1	0	1	0
sp. 2		0	4	0	0
O: Dermaptera					
sp. 1		91	2	53	10
sp. 2		23	0	10	1
sp. 3		18	3	0	1
sp. 4		2	0	1	0
sp. 5		1	0	0	0
O: Phasmatodea					
sp. 1		0	1	1	1
sp. 2		0	12	0	1
O: Psocoptera					
F: Trogiidae					
<i>Cerobasis guestfalica</i> (Kolbe, 1880)		0	0	4	0
gen. nov.		36	10	33	6
<i>Helenatropos abrupta</i> Lienhard, 2005		0	3	8	0
<i>Lepinotus</i> sp.		0	0	1	0
F: Amphipsocidae					
gen. nov.		8	1	0	0
F: Ectopsocidae					
<i>Ectopsocus briggsi</i> McLachlan, 1899		1	1	7	0
F: Pseudocaeceiliidae					
<i>Pseudocaeceilius</i> sp.		1	0	0	0
F: Elipsocidae					
<i>Elipsocus</i> sp.		1	0	1	0
<i>Propsocus pulchripennis</i> (Perkins, 1899)		0	1	1	0
F: Lesneiidae					
<i>Lesneia</i> sp. 1		0	1	0	0
<i>Lesneia</i> sp. 2		0	1	0	0
O: Thysanoptera					
sp.		2	0	0	0
O: Orthoptera					
F: Acrididae					
sp. 1		0	1	0	0
sp. 2		0	8	0	0
sp. 3		0	2	0	3
F: Anostomatidae					
<i>Henicus brevimucronatus</i> Griffini, 1911		3	0	3	0
<i>Libanasa</i> sp.		4	0	4	0
<i>Onosandridus</i> sp. 1		42	1	1	3
<i>Onosandridus</i> sp. 2		2	4	41	1
sp.		1	16	0	0

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Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
F: Gryllidae				
<i>Cophogryllus</i> sp.	4	61	27	44
<i>Gryllus bimaculatus</i> De Geer, 1773	0	0	0	434
sp.	1	0	0	0
F: Lentulidae				
sp.	0	58	1	0
F: Mogoplistidae				
sp.	96	377	211	767
F: Stenopelmatidae				
<i>Maxentius / Sia</i> sp.	0	3	0	0
F: Tetrigidae				
sp.	0	1	0	0
F: Tettigoniidae				
sp.	1	0	2	0
O: Hemiptera				
F: Miridae				
sp.	0	1	0	0
F: Nabidae				
<i>Prostemma</i> cf. <i>ruficollis</i> Laporte, 1832	0	3	0	1
F: Coreidae				
sp. 1	1	2	0	0
sp. 2	1	0	0	0
F: Anthocoridae				
sp. 1	0	1	0	1
sp. 2	0	0	1	0
sp. 3	1	0	0	0
sp. 4	0	0	3	1
sp. 5	1	0	0	0
sp. 6	0	3	0	3
sp. 7	83	6	21	5
sp. 8	95	0	13	6
sp. 9	0	0	0	1
sp. 10	3	2	0	0
sp. 11	14	0	2	1
sp. 12	4	0	0	0
sp. 13	1	0	0	0
sp. 14	1	0	0	0
F: Enicocephalidae				
sp.	4	0	0	0
F: Lygaeidae				
sp. 1	46	1	0	0
sp. 2	1	0	0	0
sp. 3	1	0	0	0
sp. 4	3	0	1	0
sp. 5	0	0	0	1
sp. 6	0	1	0	1

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
sp. 7	1	2	0	1
sp. 9	0	7	0	2
sp. 10	54	1	1	28
sp. 11	1	0	0	0
sp. 12	0	1	0	0
sp. 13	0	2	0	1
sp. 15	0	2	0	1
sp. 16	2	1	0	1
sp. 17	16	1	8	2
F: Cydnidae				
sp. 1	0	2	0	0
sp. 2	1	1	1	0
sp. 3	0	1	1	0
F: Pyrrhocoridae				
sp. 1	2	0	0	0
sp. 2	3	5	0	0
F: Reduviidae				
<i>Acanthaspis ehrenbergii</i>	15	0	0	0
<i>Baebius</i> sp. nov.	1	0	0	0
<i>Bargyllia</i> sp.	2	0	0	1
<i>Cleptria rufipes</i> Stal, 1856	10	12	44	14
<i>Ploearia</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
<i>Rhynocoris rufus</i> (Thunberg, 1822)	0	5	0	3
<i>Tinna picta</i> Wygodzinsky, 1958	1	4	0	2
cf. <i>Tinna</i> sp.	2	0	0	0
F: Tingidae				
sp. 1	0	0	1	0
F: Aphididae				
sp. 1	9	14	385	94
sp. 2	2	2	341	3
sp. 3	2	7	15	38
sp. 4	0	1	2	11
sp. 5	5	0	0	0
sp. 6	0	0	1	1
F: Cercopidae				
<i>Sepullia</i> sp.	0	0	0	1
F: Cicadellidae				
<i>Capoideus</i> sp.	0	0	0	1
<i>Chiasmus hyalinus</i> (Evans, 1947)	0	0	0	3
gen. nov.	0	0	0	1
<i>Houtbayana</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
<i>Megaulon</i> sp.	0	0	0	2
<i>Platentomus</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
sp.	2	3	0	0
<i>Typhlocybinae</i> sp. 1	1	0	0	0
<i>Typhlocybinae</i> sp. 2	1	0	0	0

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Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
<i>Tzitzikamaia</i> sp.	0	1	0	1
<i>Xestocephalus</i> sp.	0	2	1	0
F: Cixiidae				
sp. 1	2	0	0	0
sp. 2	5	0	0	0
sp. 3	4	1	0	0
F: Delphacidae				
sp. 1	1	1	0	3
sp. 2	1	0	0	0
F: Fulgoroidea				
sp. 1	0	3	0	1
sp. 3	0	1	0	0
sp. 4	0	4	0	2
F: Issidae				
sp.	0	8	0	2
F: Meenoplidae				
sp. 1	45	0	0	0
sp. 2	1	0	0	0
sp. 4	1	0	0	0
sp. 5	1	1	0	0
sp. 7	0	1	1	0
F: Tropiducidae				
<i>Caffrommatissus trimaculatus</i> Fennah, 1967	0	2	0	6
sp.	0	1	0	0
O: Neuroptera				
sp.	0	0	1	2
O: Coleoptera				
F: Carabidae				
<i>Passalidius</i> sp.	20	14	38	45
<i>Thermophilum</i> sp.	0	2	0	0
sp. 1	22	2	78	14
sp. 2	0	0	59	0
sp. 3	0	0	30	0
sp. 4	4	0	6	1
sp. 5	0	3	1	35
sp. 6	17	0	3	3
sp. 7	1	1	6	0
sp. 8	49	17	3	31
sp. 9	0	0	0	1
sp. 10	1	1	0	0
sp. 11	0	4	0	4
sp. 12	0	0	0	1
sp. 13	5	0	0	0
F: Bostrychidae				
sp. 1	0	0	1	0
sp. 2	1	0	0	0

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
F: Byrrhidae				
sp.	0	7	1	0
F: Lampyridae				
sp. 1	14	3	25	3
sp. 2	1	0	0	0
F: Cerambycidae				
sp. 1	0	3	0	2
sp. 2	1	4	0	0
sp. 3	1	1	0	0
F: Chrysomelidae				
sp. 1	4	2	1	0
sp. 2	0	3	0	0
sp. 3	0	0	0	1
sp. 4	0	0	0	1
sp. 5	0	0	0	1
F: Cleridae				
sp. 1	0	0	1	0
sp. 2	0	0	0	1
sp. 3	1	0	0	0
F: Anthicidae				
sp. 1	10	4	7	0
sp. 2	31	70	139	41
sp. 3	0	1	0	0
F: Cerylonidae				
sp.	46	765	43	505
F: Ciidae				
sp.	0	2	0	9
F: Coccinellidae				
sp.	0	1	1	0
F: Colydiidae				
<i>Pycnomerus</i> sp.	15	3	2	11
F: Corylophidae				
sp.	0	0	0	29
F: Cryptophagidae				
sp.	3	0	0	0
F: Cucujidae				
sp. 1	5	0	0	0
sp. 2	0	0	0	1
F: Discolomidae				
sp.	15	1	0	1
F: Lathridiidae				
sp.	0	0	4	0
F: Monotomidae				
cf. <i>Europs</i> sp.	5	7	83	25
F: Mordellidae				
sp. 1	1	0	0	0

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Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
sp. 2	1	1	0	0
sp. 3	0	0	0	1
F: Nitidulidae				
cf. <i>Eपुरaea</i> sp. 1	1	0	0	0
cf. <i>Eपुरaea</i> sp. 2	1	0	0	0
cf. <i>Haptoncus</i> sp.	3	0	0	0
cf. <i>Lasiodactylus</i> sp. 1	31	0	16	11
cf. <i>Lasiodactylus</i> sp. 2	0	0	1	0
F: Phalacridae				
sp.	0	1	0	0
F: Salpingidae				
sp. 1	1	25	7	9
sp. 2	0	0	0	2
F: Scaptiidae				
sp.	3	0	0	0
F: Silvanidae				
sp.	3	0	0	0
F: Tenebrionidae				
sp. 1	21	1	33	1
sp. 2	0	4	0	1
sp. 3	0	15	21	12
sp. 4	0	22	46	17
sp. 5	8	9	2	24
sp. 6	14	1	31	3
sp. 7	5	3	5	1
sp. 8	8	7	11	7
sp. 9	9	15	8	5
sp. 10	1	0	0	0
sp. 11	0	0	0	1
sp. 12	1	1	0	0
sp. 14	1	0	0	0
F: Curculionidae				
sp. 1	0	0	17	1
sp. 2	0	0	0	1
sp. 3	0	2	0	0
sp. 4	16	2	3	3
sp. 5	0	0	0	1
sp. 6	0	0	0	1
sp. 7	0	1	0	0
sp. 8	2	0	0	0
sp. 9	0	0	0	1
sp. 10	12	0	0	1
sp. 11	2	1	0	0
sp. 12	7	0	4	1
sp. 13	8	0	5	0
sp. 14	2	0	0	0

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
sp. 15	1	0	0	0
sp. 16	0	0	1	0
sp. 17	6	1	0	0
sp. 18	5	0	0	0
sp. 19	10	2	2	1
sp. 21	1	0	0	0
sp. 22	0	4	0	1
sp. 23	48	0	0	0
F: Platypodidae				
sp.	0	0	0	1
F: Scolytidae				
sp. 1	0	0	1	7
sp. 2	1	0	10	15
sp. 3	3	0	0	0
sp. 4	1	0	0	2
F: Elateridae				
sp. 1	1	0	1	2
sp. 2	1	0	0	0
sp. 3	6	2	0	0
sp. 4	1	0	1	0
sp. 5	2	1	0	0
sp. 7	2	0	4	1
sp. 8	26	1	1	1
F: Histeridae				
sp.	2	0	1	1
F: Scarabaeidae				
<i>Boheplissus nitidus</i> Balthasar, 1965	PE	115	0	0
<i>Epirhinus hilaris</i> Perringuey, 1901		35	13	195
sp. 1		1	0	0
sp. 2		1	0	0
sp. 3		12	7	1
sp. 4				4
F: Leiodidae				
cf. <i>Colenis</i> sp.		0	1	0
sp. 2		1	0	0
sp. 3		0	0	1
sp. 4		2	3	0
F: Ptiliidae				
sp.		20	12	9
F: Scydmaenidae				
sp. 1		71	16	29
sp. 2		0	0	2
F: Staphylinidae				
SubF: Aleocharinae				
<i>Leucocraspedina</i> sp.		4	0	0
sp. 1		20	4	12
sp. 2		21	6	19

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Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
sp. 3	55	1	2	0
SubF: Omaliinae				
cf. <i>Xylostiba</i> sp.	0	1	2	1
SubF: Oxytelinae				
<i>Thinodromus</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
SubF: Paederinae				
(Euplectini) sp.	0	1	3	0
(Euplectitae) not complete sp.	0	22	0	0
<i>Neoraffraya</i> sp.	60	12	17	0
<i>Neoraffraya variabilis</i> (Raffray, 1897)	4	2	0	0
<i>Novoclaviger joncooteri</i> Hlaváč, 2006	0	1	0	0
<i>Pselaphaulax</i> sp.	0	0	2	0
<i>Pselaphocerus amicus</i> Raffray, 1898	2	0	0	0
<i>Pselaphocerus</i> sp.	1	0	0	0
<i>Pseudotychus nigerrimus</i> Raffray, 1897	4	1	0	0
<i>Raffraya</i> sp.	2	0	0	0
<i>Raffrayidius</i> sp.	17	4	0	0
<i>Raffrayola</i> sp.	3	0	1	0
sp. 4	13	1	73	4
sp. 5	27	4	40	6
<i>Typhloraffraya</i> sp.	0	1	0	0
unidentified	11	1	4	0
<i>Xenogyra</i> sp.	1	6	1	3
SubF: Staphylininae				
cf. <i>Notolinus</i> sp.	0	1	0	1
<i>Quedius</i> sp.	2	0	14	1
<i>Philonthus</i> sp.	18	0	0	0
SubF: Steninae				
<i>Stenus</i> sp.	0	3	1	0
SubF: Tachyporinae				
<i>Mycetoporus</i> sp.	4	0	2	3
<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 1	227	0	9	6
<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 2	90	2	17	1
<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 3	1	3	0	0
<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 4	4	1	1	0
<i>Tachyporus</i> sp.	1	0	0	4
O: Diptera				
F: Asilidae				
sp.	0	0	1	0
F: Calliphoridae				
<i>Lucilia</i> sp.	0	0	1	1
sp.	7	0	0	0
F: Cecidomyiidae				
sp.	1	0	0	0
F: Chironomidae				
sp.	0	2	0	2

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
F: Dolichopodidae				
sp. 1	0	1	0	0
sp. 2	0	4	0	0
F: Drosophilidae				
<i>Drosophila</i> sp. 1	91	1	7	1
<i>Drosophila</i> sp. 2	47	0	21	2
<i>Drosophila</i> sp. 3	0	1	0	3
<i>Zaprionus</i> sp.	6	0	1	0
F: Heliomyzidae				
cf. <i>Suilla</i> sp.	10	0	0	0
F: Neriidae				
<i>Chaetonerius</i> sp.	1	26	0	0
F: Phoridae				
sp.	298	38	301	39
F: Sciaridae				
sp. 1	0	2	1	0
sp. 2	160	132	218	50
F: Tachinidae				
sp.	0	0	0	1
F: Tipulidae				
sp. 1	3	0	0	0
sp. 2	1	328	0	0
F: unidentified				
sp. 3	1	52	0	2
sp. 6	1	5	70	6
sp. 7	13	1	0	0
sp. 8	0	6	0	1
sp. 9	11	0	0	1
sp. 10	5	0	6	0
sp. 11	6	2	2	1
sp. 12	0	1	2	6
sp. 13	4	11	6	4
sp. 14	13	0	5	0
sp. 15	3	1	0	0
sp. 16	2	1	0	0
sp. 17	0	0	0	3
sp. 18	3	0	0	0
sp. 19	1	0	1	0
sp. 20	4	0	0	0
sp. 21	1	0	0	2
sp. 22	0	1	0	1
sp. 23	0	2	0	0
sp. 24	0	2	4	0
sp. 26	0	2	0	0
sp. 27	0	0	2	0
sp. 28	3	0	0	0

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Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
sp. 29	1	0	0	0
sp. 30	2	0	0	0
sp. 31	1	0	0	0
sp. 32	1	0	0	0
sp. 33	0	0	1	0
sp. 34	0	0	1	0
sp. 35	0	1	0	0
sp. 36	0	0	1	0
sp. 37	1	0	0	0
sp. 38	1	0	0	0
sp. 39	1	1	0	0
sp. 41	1	0	0	0
sp. 42	1	0	0	0
sp. 43	1	0	0	0
sp. 44	1	0	0	0
sp. 45	1	0	0	0
sp. 46	0	1	0	0
sp. 47	1	0	0	0
sp. 48	1	0	0	0
sp. 49	1	0	0	0
sp. 50	0	0	1	0
sp. 51	0	0	1	0
sp. 52	0	0	1	0
sp. 53	0	0	1	0
sp. 54	0	0	0	1
sp. 55	0	0	0	1
sp. 56	0	0	0	1
sp. 57	0	0	0	1
sp. 58	1	0	0	0
sp. 59	0	0	0	1
sp. 60	1	0	0	0
sp. 61	0	2	0	0
sp. 62	0	0	1	0
sp. 63	0	0	1	0
sp. 64	0	0	0	1
sp. 65	0	0	0	1
sp. 66	0	3	0	1
O: Lepidoptera				
unidentified	151	14	8	33
O: Hymenoptera				
F: Mutillidae				
sp. 1	0	1	1	0
sp. 3	0	1	0	0
sp. 4	0	1	0	0
F: Bethyliidae				
sp.	0	0	1	0

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
F: Ichneumonidae				
sp. 1	1	0	0	0
sp. 2	1	0	0	0
sp. 3	0	0	1	0
F: Chalcidoidea				
sp. 1	0	0	0	1
sp. 2	0	0	2	0
sp. 3	0	0	1	0
sp. 4	0	0	1	0
F: Sphecidae				
sp.	0	1	0	0
F: Pompilidae				
sp. 1	0	0	1	0
sp. 2	0	1	1	2
sp. 3	0	0	0	1
sp. 4	0	1	0	0
sp. 5	0	0	0	1
sp. 6	0	1	0	1
sp. 7	0	0	0	1
sp. 8	0	0	0	1
sp. 9	1	0	0	0
F: Braconidae				
sp.	5	1	1	0
F: unidentified				
sp. 24	0	2	0	0
sp. 25	3	9	1	9
sp. 26	28	0	1	0
sp. 27	21	0	5	3
sp. 28	22	0	8	1
sp. 29	12	1	13	1
sp. 30	20	0	3	1
sp. 31	42	5	0	0
sp. 32	2	4	1	3
sp. 33	0	1	4	5
sp. 34	4	3	2	1
sp. 35	5	0	3	0
sp. 36	20	1	0	0
sp. 37	2	0	2	1
sp. 38	1	0	1	4
sp. 39	3	1	2	2
sp. 40	5	0	1	9
sp. 41	6	0	0	0
sp. 42	6	0	1	0
sp. 43	2	0	0	14
sp. 44	0	0	6	0
sp. 45	14	0	1	0

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Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
sp. 46	1	2	0	3
sp. 47	0	1	0	4
sp. 48	1	0	1	2
sp. 49	3	0	1	0
sp. 50	1	0	2	0
sp. 51	0	0	6	0
sp. 52	3	0	0	0
sp. 53	3	0	0	0
sp. 54	3	0	0	0
sp. 55	2	0	2	0
sp. 56	2	0	0	0
sp. 57	2	0	0	0
sp. 58	3	0	0	0
sp. 59	4	0	0	0
sp. 60	2	0	0	0
sp. 61	1	0	1	0
sp. 62	2	0	0	0
sp. 63	0	0	0	2
sp. 64	2	0	0	0
sp. 65	2	0	0	0
sp. 66	0	0	1	1
sp. 67	0	1	0	1
sp. 68	0	2	0	0
sp. 69	0	0	0	2
sp. 70	1	0	0	0
sp. 71	1	0	0	0
sp. 72	0	0	1	0
sp. 73	0	1	0	0
sp. 74	0	1	0	0
sp. 75	0	0	1	0
sp. 76	1	0	0	0
sp. 77	1	1	0	0
sp. 78	0	1	0	0
sp. 79	0	1	0	0
sp. 81	1	0	0	0
sp. 82	1	0	0	0
sp. 83	1	0	0	0
sp. 84	1	0	0	0
sp. 85	1	0	0	0
sp. 86	1	0	0	0
sp. 87	1	0	0	0
sp. 88	2	0	0	0
sp. 89	1	0	0	0
sp. 90	1	0	0	0
sp. 91	1	0	0	0
sp. 92	1	0	0	0

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
sp. 93	1	0	0	0
sp. 94	1	0	0	0
sp. 95	1	0	0	0
sp. 96	1	0	0	0
sp. 98	0	0	0	1
sp. 99	1	0	0	0
sp. 100	1	0	0	0
sp. 101	0	1	0	0
sp. 102	0	0	1	0
sp. 103	0	0	1	0
sp. 104	0	0	0	1
sp. 105	0	0	0	1
sp. 106	0	0	0	2
sp. 107	0	0	0	1
sp. 108	1	0	0	0
sp. 109	1	0	0	0
sp. 110	1	0	0	0
sp. 111	1	0	0	0
sp. 112	0	0	1	0
sp. 113	0	0	0	1
sp. 114	0	0	0	1
sp. 115	1	0	0	0
sp. 116	1	0	0	0
sp. 117	0	0	0	1
sp. 118	0	0	0	1
sp. 119	2	0	0	0
sp. 120	1	0	0	0
sp. 121	1	0	0	0
sp. 122	1	0	0	0
sp. 123	1	0	0	0
F: Vespidae				
<i>Vespula germanica</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	15	14	3	0
F: Chrysididae				
SubF: Amiseginae				
<i>Obenbergerella aenigmatica</i> Bridwell, 1919	3	10	15	0
<i>Reidia turneri</i> (hairy) Krombein, 1957	26	14	122	8
<i>Reidia turneri</i> (few hairs) Krombein, 1957	38	0	45	0
F: Apidae				
<i>Apis mellifera</i> Linnaeus, 1758	0	1	0	0
F: Halictidae				
sp. 1	0	2	0	0
sp. 2	0	2	0	0
F: Formicidae				
SubF: Dolichoderinae				
<i>Linepithema humile</i> Mayr, 1868	A 15829	4546	5841	6681
<i>Tapinoma</i> sp.	0	757	265	0

C. Uys, PhD (Jan 2011). Appendix A. Species checklist

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
<i>Technomyrmex pallipes</i> (Smith, 1876)	0	1325	13	11
SubF: Formicinae				
<i>Camponotus bertolinii</i> Emery, 1895	54	371	149	2
<i>Camponotus niveosetosus</i> Mayr, 1862	36	742	12	12
<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 1 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	0	371	0	101
<i>Camponotus</i> sp. 2 (<i>maculatus</i> group)	595	4360	123	161
<i>Lepisiota capensis</i> (Mayr, 1862)	5	9040	25	4824
SubF: Myrmicinae				
<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	806	3465	0	393
<i>Meranoplus</i> sp.	281	474	1	116
<i>Monomorium</i> sp.	3089	891	5278	1253
<i>Myrmecaria nigra</i> (Mayr, 1862)	0	284	0	87
<i>Pheidole capensis</i> Mayr, 1862	0	1545	0	4
<i>Tetramorium grassii</i> Emery, 1895	3994	1099	1687	1043
<i>Tetramorium</i> sp.	2109	319	131	1294
SubF: Ponerinae				
<i>Hagensia peringueyi</i> (Emery, 1899)	0	252	0	121
SubF: Pseudomyrmicinae				
<i>Tetraoponera</i> sp.	21	37	21	6
C: DIPLOPODA				
O: Polyxenida				
F: Synexidae				
<i>Phryssonotus</i> sp. nov.	0	7	11	4
F: Polyxenidae				
<i>Propolyxenus</i> sp. nov.	3	1	0	1
O: Sphaerotheriida				
F: Sphaerotheriidae				
<i>Sphaerotherium capense</i> Schubart	4	0	5	0
<i>Sphaerotherium commune</i> Attems, 1928	2	1	1	0
<i>Sphaerotherium</i> sp.	22	3	6	0
O: Polydesmida				
F: Vaalagonopidae				
<i>Hemiphygoxerotes crinitus</i> Attems, 1944	6	2	11	0
F: Dalodesmidae				
cf. <i>Gnomeskelus</i> sp.	0	2	3	0

Species	Forest	Fynbos	Pine	Felled
O: Spirobolida				
F: Pachybolidae				
<i>Centrobolus diagramus</i>	16	0	0	0
O: Spirostreptida				
F: Iulomorphidae				
<i>Iulomorpha</i> sp.	291	1	66	70
F: Cambalidae				
<i>Ommatoiulus moreletii</i> (Lucas, 1860)	A	508	152	546
C: CHILOPODA				
O: Geophilomorpha				
sp.	51	21	22	9
O: Lithobiomorpha				
F: Henicopidae				
<i>Anopsobius</i> sp.	38	3	0	4
<i>Paralamyctes</i> sp. 1	10	3	4	0
<i>Paralamyctes</i> sp. 2	4	0	2	0
<i>Paralamyctes</i> sp. 3	2	1	0	0
<i>Paralamyctes</i> sp. 4	5	0	1	0
F: unidentified				
sp. 1	1	0	1	1
sp. 2	5	1	12	10
O: Scolopendromorpha				
F: Cryptopsidae				
<i>Cryptops</i> sp.	6	9	4	0
F: Scolopendriidae				
<i>Cormocephalus</i> sp.	12	2	21	7
F: Scutiggerinidae				
<i>Scutiggerina weberi</i> Silvestri, 1903	0	0	7	1
C: UDEONYCHOPHORA				
O: Ontonychophora				
F: Peripatopsidae				
<i>Peripatopsis balfouri</i> (Sedgwick, 1885) spp. complex	6	0	2	2
<i>Peripatopsis stelliporata</i> Sherbon and Walker, 2004	0	0	0	1